

Compendium of scientific publications (year 3)

Deliverable 5.15

Lead Beneficiary: UREAD

Date: September 30, 2024 (month 48)

Submission date: September 27, 2024 (month 48)

Version: 1

Dissemination level: Public

www.re-dwell.eu

RE-DWELL “Delivering affordable and sustainable housing in Europe” has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 956082

The European Commission’s support for the production of this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

RE-DWELL

Deliverable 5.15 Compendium of scientific publications (year 3)

Version 1

Authors:

Mafalda Casais (ISCTE)

Leandro Madrazo (La Salle-URL)

Stephen Gage (UREAD)

Version	Date	Author
0.1	September 30, 2024	Mafalda Casais (ISCTE)
0.2	September 18, 2024	Leandro Madrazo (La Salle-URL)
0.3	September 25, 2024	Stephen Gage (UREAD)
1.0	September 27, 2024	Leandro Madrazo (La Salle-URL)

Table of contents

- Executive summary..... 5
- 1. Introduction..... 6
- 2. Dissemination.....19
- 3. Conclusions.....21
- Annex 1 – Abstracts 1

Executive summary

This is a report of the publications made by early-stage researchers in the third and last year of the RE-DWELL project, between October 2023 and September 2024.

A total of 24 scientific contributions, including conference abstracts, presentations and papers, and journal articles, have been submitted, accepted and/or published during this period. This document contains the list of contributions classified by authors and keywords. The abstracts are included in the annex and published on the project website.

Building from the year 2 report, the introduction includes updated reflections on the interrelationships between the lines of research emerging from the publications. In the conclusion are some suggestions for further research beyond the official life of the programme.

1. Introduction

This is the final in a series of three compendiums of scientific publications produced by early-stage researchers (ESRs) in the course of their PhD research in the RE-DWELL network. In the third year of activity, 24 contributions have been made. This includes 13 conference activities (presentation, abstract, paper, poster), 9 journal articles, 1 white paper, and 1 working paper (see Table 1 and Annex 1). Of particular note is the increase in published journal articles compared to the previous year (5), reflecting the more mature stage of the ESR research and indicates the growing impact of the project as it nears its conclusion.

The scope of the contributions is captured by the diversity of topics in Table 2, which highlights both the breadth of research and the key overarching concerns. Key terms include “participation” and related topics (9 outputs), “sustainability” and related topics (8 outputs), “social housing” (6 outputs), and “affordability”/ “affordable housing” (5 outputs). This list is similar to previous years, though “transdisciplinarity” fails to appear as a key term in year three. This perhaps reflects the increasing specificity of the ESRs’ individual work. Other key terms included “capability approach” (3 outputs), “energy poverty” (4 outputs), “renovation” (3 outputs), and “retrofit” (3 outputs).

Once again, geographical range across Europe was another notable feature of the outputs. The research encompassed: Austria, Croatia, Cyprus, France, Germany, the Netherlands, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, and the UK. Some of these studies focus in-depth on one particular context, such as Zoe Tzika’s work on Catalonia and Barcelona and Marko Horvat’s work on Croatia. Others, such as the work of Alex Fernández and Tijn Croon, directly compared multiple countries to explore how specific issues like energy poverty and social housing financing operate in different contexts. Andreas Panagidis and Effrosyni Roussou produced a collaborative conference paper on the shortfalls of neoliberal planning policies and the infrastructure gap in the context of Southern Europe, carrying on another key regional context from the outputs of previous years.

Building from Panagidis and Roussou’s interest in planning policies, other ESRs are conducting research on how policy shapes the sustainability of housing. This is especially apparent in the work of Marko Horvat, who tackles housing from the perspective of homelessness and housing affordability, with interests in how different models of institutional structure and policy initiatives in these areas can increase social sustainability. Financial policy is also an important concern. Across multiple outputs, Fernández explores the role of financing, pricing, and finance policy in social housing, especially in relation to energy consumption and sustainability.

Design factors are another important way of dissecting the sustainability of housing, apparent in ESR research into energy usage, construction practices and retrofit. Anette Davis, for example, explores the topic of social housing through design for disassembly, life cycle assessment methodologies, and circular economies. Croon’s work explores the importance of retrofit and design factors in improving the energy poverty of social housing tenants, related to Saskia Furman’s research, which centres on retrofit and how to make it more sustainable.

Furman also looks at retrofit from the perspective of resident engagement. Participation and community/citizen engagement was also explored in Roussou’s work on urban commons in Nicosia, and in Pappa’s research into the urban commons phenomenon as a tool for urban regeneration and community participation in Lisbon.

Cutting across many of these categories is an interest in new frameworks which integrate different perspectives and have a strong social angle, especially in relation to the topic of social housing. For example, Mahmoud Alsaeed's work into developing the foundations of a new framework for social housing builds around three pillars of sustainability, processes and perceptions, and the roles of public authorities. Tzika's work on cooperative housing in Barcelona includes the application of a Capability Approach, something theorised more broadly in the journal article of Leonardo Ricaurte, which proposes the Capability Approach as a way to understand social value in housing design. Furman also looks at social housing through the development of a more sustainable framework for social housing retrofit.

Thus, while transdisciplinarity was not as explicit an area of exploration in the year 3 outputs, it can be seen as inherent to almost all the research undertaken. Taken collectively, we can begin to understand the sustainability of affordable housing in new and exciting ways that cuts across disciplinary boundaries, drawing from perspectives on social value, finance, policy, design, energy, and participatory practices.

Table 1. ESRs publications

ESR	References	Contribution type
ESR 1 Anette Davis	Davis, A. (2024). <i>Circular Housing: Insights from Solar Decathlon Europe 2022</i> . Presented at the European Network for Housing Research (ENHR) Conference 2024, Delft, the Netherlands.	Conference presentation
	Davis, A. (2022). <i>Design for Disassembly in housing: the need to adapt LCA to Shearing Layers</i> . In Proceedings of 3rd Valencia International Biennial of Research in Architecture 2022. Changing priorities (pp. 636-647). Valencia: Editorial Universitat Politècnica de València.	Conference paper
ESR 2 Saskia Furman	Furman, S., Martínez, A., & Martín, X. (2024). <i>Social Housing Retrofit: Case studies in resident engagement</i> . Proceedings of the RE-DWELL Conference “Sustainable Living, Affordable Homes”, 16 May 2024, Barcelona, Spain.	Conference abstract
	Furman, S. (2022). <i>Upgrading social housing to meet the socio - economic needs of today’s dwellers, and the environmental needs of the planet: A framework beyond retrofit</i> . In New Housing Researchers Colloquium (NHRC) at the European Network for Housing Research (ENHR) Conference 2022. Barcelona, Spain.	Conference presentation
ESR 5 Mahmoud Alsaeed	Alsaeed, M., Hadjri, H., & Nawratek, K. (2024). <i>Exploring the building blocks of sustainable social housing frameworks</i> . Proceedings of the RE-DWELL Conference “Sustainable Living, Affordable Homes”, 16 May 2024, Barcelona, Spain.	Conference abstract
ESR 6 Marko Horvat	Horvat, M., & Bežovan, G. (2024). <i>Sustainability and Capacity Analysis of Croatian Homeless Service Providers</i> . European Journal of Homelessness, 18(2). 67-94.	Journal article
	Horvat, M. (2024). <i>Improving housing affordability through housing allowances: a pilot project in Croatia</i> . Proceedings of the RE-DWELL Conference “Sustainable Living, Affordable Homes”, 16 May 2024, Barcelona, Spain.	Conference abstract
ESR 8 Andreas Panagidis	Panagidis, A., & Roussou, E. (2024) <i>Clientelism and infrastructural gaps in Southern Europe: The implications on housing and urban governance</i> . Proceedings of the RE-DWELL Conference “Sustainable Living, Affordable Homes”, 16 May 2024, Barcelona, Spain.	Conference abstract

ESR 9 Effrosyni Roussou	Roussou, E., Ricchiardi, A. (2024). <i>Enclaves of commoning across the divide: self-organised spaces against divisions</i> . In AESOP Symposium: “Constructing Peace through Public Space: What publics? Whose commons?”. Nicosia, Cyprus.	Conference abstract
	Panagidis, A., & Roussou, E. (2024) <i>Clientelism and infrastructural gaps in Southern Europe: The implications on housing and urban governance</i> . Proceedings of the RE-DWELL Conference “Sustainable Living, Affordable Homes”, 16 May 2024, Barcelona, Spain.	Conference abstract
ESR 10 Zoe Tzika	Tzika, Z. (2024). <i>Housing as Community Infrastructure: Case Study Analysis of Catalonia’s Grant-of-Use Cooperative Housing</i> . Presented at the European Network for Housing Research (ENHR) Conference 2024, Delft, the Netherlands.	Conference presentation
	Tzika, Z., & Sentieri, C. (accepted, 2024). <i>Housing as Community Infrastructure: Analysis of Senior Cooperative Housing Using the Capability Approach</i> . Journal of Housing and the Built Environment.	Journal article
	Tzika, Z., Sentieri, C. & Martinez, A. (2024) <i>Key topics and challenges for creating community-led, inclusive and sustainable housing: Catalonia’s grant-of-use cooperative housing in Catalonia</i> . Proceedings of the RE-DWELL Conference “Sustainable Living, Affordable Homes”, 16 May 2024, Barcelona, Spain.	Conference abstract
	Tzika, Z., & Sentieri, C. (2023). <i>Towards collective forms of dwelling: Analysis of the characteristics of the emerging grant-of-use housing cooperatives in Catalonia</i> . In 2nd Participatory Design Conference. Transforming the City: Public Space & Environment, Inequalities & Democracy. Athens, Greece.	Conference poster
ESR 11 Tijn Croon	Croon, T. M., Hoekstra, J. S. C. M., & Dubois, U. (2024). <i>Energy poverty alleviation by social housing providers: A qualitative investigation of targeted interventions in France, England, and the Netherlands</i> . Energy Policy, 192, 114247.	Journal article
	Galvin, R., Sunikka-Blank, M., & Croon, T. M. (in print, 2024). <i>Juggling the Basics: How Much Does an Income Increase Affect Energy Spending of Low-Income Households in England</i> . Energy Research & Social Science.	Journal article
	Croon, T. M., Maghsoudi Nia, E., He, S., Qian, Q., Elsinga, M., Hoekstra, J., van Ooij, C., & van der Wal, A. (accepted,	Journal article

	2024). <i>Energy coaching and ‘fix team’ retrofitting to mitigate energy poverty: An ex-post analysis of treatment and interaction effects</i> . Energy Research & Social Science.	
	Croon, T., Hoekstra, J., & Dubois, U. (2023). <i>Addressing Energy Poverty in Social Housing Estates</i> . European Federation for Living.	White paper
ESR 12 Alex Fernández	Fernández, A. (2024). <i>Investigating the impact of housing price increases on consumption: Heterogeneity by age, tenure and housing quality</i> . Journal of European Real Estate Research (2024).	Journal article
	Fernández, A., Haffner, M., & Elsinga, M. (2024). <i>When Land is Not Enough; Drawing in Private Capital to Increase Social Rental Housing in Spain</i> . [Working paper]	Working paper
	Fernández, A., Haffner, M., & Elsinga, M. (2024). <i>Subsidies or green taxes? Evaluating the distributional effects of housing renovation policies among Dutch households</i> . Journal of Housing and the Built Environment, 2024, 1-28.	Journal article
	Fernández, A., Elsinga, M., & Haffner, M. (2023). <i>Investigating the role of ESG bonds and loans in financing housing renovation among social housing providers: a comparative approach to six European countries</i> . In Diaconu, A. (Ed.) Proceedings of the RE-DWELL Grenoble Conference (pp. 84-88). Pacte Social Sciences Research Centre, University Grenoble Alpes, Grenoble, France.	Conference article
	Fernández, A., Elsinga, M., & Haffner, M. (2023). <i>Three contradictions between ESG finance and social housing decarbonisation: a comparison of five European countries</i> . Housing Studies, 2023, 1-27.	Journal article
ESR 13 Androniki Pappa	Pappa, A., & Paio, A. (2023). <i>The role of commons-oriented policies in the transformation of urban governance: The case of the participatory budget BIP/ZIP in Lisbon</i> . In 2nd Conference on Participatory Design. Transforming the City: Public Space & Environment, Inequalities & Democracy. Athens, Greece	Conference poster
ESR 15 Leonardo Ricourte	Dissart, J. C., & Ricourte, L. (2023). <i>Assessing social value in housing design: contributions of the capability approach</i> . Buildings and Cities, 4(1), 867–882.	Journal article

Table 2. Keywords and publications

Added value	Dissart, J. C., & Ricaurte, L. (2023). <i>Assessing social value in housing design: contributions of the capability approach.</i>
Affordability	Fernández, A., Haffner, M., & Elsinga, M. (2024). <i>When Land is Not Enough; Drawing in Private Capital to Increase Social Rental Housing in Spain.</i>
Affordable housing	<p>Horvat, M. (2024). <i>Improving housing affordability through housing allowances: a pilot project in Croatia.</i></p> <p>Tzika, Z. (2024). <i>Housing as Community Infrastructure: Case Study Analysis of Catalonia's Grant-of-Use Cooperative Housing.</i></p> <p>Tzika, Z., & Sentieri, C. (2024). <i>Housing as Community Infrastructure: Analysis of Senior Cooperative Housing Using the Capability Approach.</i></p> <p>Tzika, Z., & Sentieri, C. (2023). <i>Towards collective forms of dwelling: Analysis of the characteristics of the emerging grant-of-use housing cooperatives in Catalonia.</i></p> <p>Furman, S. (2022). <i>Upgrading social housing to meet the socio-economic needs of today's dwellers, and the environmental needs of the planet: A framework beyond retrofit.</i></p>
Age groups	Fernández, A. (2024). <i>Investigating the impact of housing price increases on consumption: Heterogeneity by age, tenure and housing quality.</i>
Built environment	Dissart, J. C., & Ricaurte, L. (2023). <i>Assessing social value in housing design: contributions of the capability approach.</i>
Capability approach	<p>Tzika, Z. (2024). <i>Housing as Community Infrastructure: Case Study Analysis of Catalonia's Grant-of-Use Cooperative Housing.</i></p> <p>Tzika, Z., Sentieri, C. & Martínez, A. (2024) <i>Key topics and challenges for creating community-led, inclusive and sustainable housing: Catalonia's grant-of-use cooperative housing in Catalonia.</i></p> <p>Dissart, J. C., & Ricaurte, L. (2023). <i>Assessing social value in housing design: contributions of the capability approach.</i></p>
Care	Tzika, Z., & Sentieri, C. (2024). <i>Housing as Community Infrastructure: Analysis of Senior Cooperative Housing Using the Capability Approach.</i>
Case studies	Furman, S., Martínez, A., & Martín, X. (2024). <i>Social Housing Retrofit: Case studies in resident engagement.</i>
Circular economy	Davis, A. (2022). <i>Design for Disassembly in housing: the need to adapt LCA to Shearing Layers.</i>

Circular housing	Davis, A. (2024). <i>Circular Housing: Insights from Solar Decathlon Europe 2022</i> .
Civil organisations	Horvat, M., & Bežovan, G. (2024). <i>Sustainability and Capacity Analysis of Croatian Homeless Service Providers</i> .
Co-housing	Tzika, Z., & Sentieri, C. (2024). <i>Housing as Community Infrastructure: Analysis of Senior Cooperative Housing Using the Capability Approach</i> .
Collaborative	Tzika, Z. (2024). <i>Housing as Community Infrastructure: Case Study Analysis of Catalonia's Grant-of-Use Cooperative Housing</i> .
Collaborative housing	Tzika, Z., & Sentieri, C. (2024). <i>Housing as Community Infrastructure: Analysis of Senior Cooperative Housing Using the Capability Approach</i> .
Collective housing	Tzika, Z., Sentieri, C. & Martínez, A. (2024) <i>Key topics and challenges for creating community-led, inclusive and sustainable housing: Catalonia's grant-of-use cooperative housing in Catalonia</i> . Tzika, Z., & Sentieri, C. (2023). <i>Towards collective forms of dwelling: Analysis of the characteristics of the emerging grant-of-use housing cooperatives in Catalonia</i> .
Commoning	Roussou, E., Ricchiardi, A. (2024). <i>Enclaves of commoning across the divide: self-organised spaces against divisions</i> .
Commons-oriented strategy	Pappa, A., & Paio, A. (2023). <i>The role of commons-oriented policies in the transformation of urban governance: The case of the participatory budget BIP/ZIP in Lisbon</i> .
Communal living	Tzika, Z., & Sentieri, C. (2023). <i>Towards collective forms of dwelling: Analysis of the characteristics of the emerging grant-of-use housing cooperatives in Catalonia</i> .
Community	Tzika, Z., & Sentieri, C. (2023). <i>Towards collective forms of dwelling: Analysis of the characteristics of the emerging grant-of-use housing cooperatives in Catalonia</i> .
Community-led	Tzika, Z. (2024). <i>Housing as Community Infrastructure: Case Study Analysis of Catalonia's Grant-of-Use Cooperative Housing</i> .
Comparative policy	Fernández, A., Elsinga, M., & Haffner, M. (2023). <i>Three contradictions between ESG finance and social housing decarbonisation: a comparison of five European countries</i> .
Consumption	Fernández, A. (2024). <i>Investigating the impact of housing price increases on consumption: Heterogeneity by age, tenure and housing quality</i> .

Design for disassembly	<p>Davis, A. (2024). <i>Circular Housing: Insights from Solar Decathlon Europe 2022</i>.</p> <p>Davis, A. (2022). <i>Design for Disassembly in housing: the need to adapt LCA to Shearing Layers</i>.</p>
Distributional impact	Fernández, A., Haffner, M., & Elsinga, M. (2024). <i>Subsidies or green taxes? Evaluating the distributional effects of housing renovation policies among Dutch households</i> .
Ecosocial policy	Galvin, R., Sunikka-Blank, M., & Croon, T. M. (in print, 2024). <i>Juggling the Basics: How Much Does an Income Increase Affect Energy Spending of Low-Income Households in England</i> .
Energy coaching	Croon, T. M., et al. (accepted, 2024). <i>Energy coaching and 'fix team' retrofitting to mitigate energy poverty: An ex-post analysis of treatment and interaction effects</i> .
Energy efficiency	Fernández, A. (2024). <i>Investigating the impact of housing price increases on consumption: Heterogeneity by age, tenure and housing quality</i> .
Energy expenditure	Galvin, R., Sunikka-Blank, M., & Croon, T. M. (in print, 2024). <i>Juggling the Basics: How Much Does an Income Increase Affect Energy Spending of Low-Income Households in England</i> .
Energy poverty	<p>Croon, T. M., Hoekstra, J. S. C. M., & Dubois, U. (2024). <i>Energy poverty alleviation by social housing providers: A qualitative investigation of targeted interventions in France, England, and the Netherlands</i>.</p> <p>Galvin, R., Sunikka-Blank, M., & Croon, T. M. (2024). <i>Juggling the Basics: How Much Does an Income Increase Affect Energy Spending of Low-Income Households in England</i>.</p> <p>Croon, T. M., et al. (2024). <i>Energy coaching and 'fix team' retrofitting to mitigate energy poverty: An ex-post analysis of treatment and interaction effects</i>.</p>
Energy transition	Fernández, A., Elsinga, M., & Haffner, M. (2023). <i>Investigating the role of ESG bonds and loans in financing housing renovation among social housing providers: a comparative approach to six European countries</i> .
English Housing Survey	Galvin, R., Sunikka-Blank, M., & Croon, T. M. (in print, 2024). <i>Juggling the Basics: How Much Does an Income Increase Affect Energy Spending of Low-Income Households in England</i> .
ESG (Environmental, Social and Governance)	<p>Fernández, A., Elsinga, M., & Haffner, M. (2023). <i>Investigating the role of ESG bonds and loans in financing housing renovation among social housing providers: a comparative approach to six European countries</i>.</p> <p>Fernández, A., Elsinga, M., & Haffner, M. (2023). <i>Three contradictions between ESG finance and social housing decarbonisation: a comparison of five European countries</i>.</p>

European policy	Fernández, A., Elsinga, M., & Haffner, M. (2023). <i>Three contradictions between ESG finance and social housing decarbonisation: a comparison of five European countries.</i>
Finance	Fernández, A., Haffner, M., & Elsinga, M. (2024). <i>When Land is Not Enough; Drawing in Private Capital to Increase Social Rental Housing in Spain.</i>
Focus groups	Croon, T. M., Hoekstra, J. S. C. M., & Dubois, U. (2024). <i>Energy poverty alleviation by social housing providers: A qualitative investigation of targeted interventions in France, England, and the Netherlands.</i>
Framework	Alsaeed, M., Hadjri, H., & Nawratek, K. (2024). <i>Exploring the building blocks of sustainable social housing frameworks.</i> Davis, A. (2024). <i>Circular Housing: Insights from Solar Decathlon Europe 2022.</i>
Grant-of-use	Tzika, Z., & Sentieri, C. (2024). <i>Housing as Community Infrastructure: Analysis of Senior Cooperative Housing Using the Capability Approach.</i>
Green finance	Fernández, A., Elsinga, M., & Haffner, M. (2023). <i>Investigating the role of ESG bonds and loans in financing housing renovation among social housing providers: a comparative approach to six European countries.</i>
Green taxes	Fernández, A., Haffner, M., & Elsinga, M. (2024). <i>Subsidies or green taxes? Evaluating the distributional effects of housing renovation policies among Dutch households.</i>
Homeless	Horvat, M., & Bežovan, G. (2024). <i>Sustainability and Capacity Analysis of Croatian Homeless Service Providers.</i>
House prices	Fernández, A. (2024). <i>Investigating the impact of housing price increases on consumption: Heterogeneity by age, tenure and housing quality.</i>
Housing	Dissart, J. C., & Ricaurte, L. (2023). <i>Assessing social value in housing design: contributions of the capability approach.</i>
Housing allocation	Croon, T. M., Hoekstra, J. S. C. M., & Dubois, U. (2024). <i>Energy poverty alleviation by social housing providers: A qualitative investigation of targeted interventions in France, England, and the Netherlands.</i>
Housing allowance	Horvat, M. (2024). <i>Improving housing affordability through housing allowances: a pilot project in Croatia.</i>
Housing design	Dissart, J. C., & Ricaurte, L. (2023). <i>Assessing social value in housing design: contributions of the capability approach.</i>
Housing policy	Horvat, M. (2024). <i>Improving housing affordability through housing allowances: a pilot project in Croatia.</i>

Housing value	Fernández, A., Haffner, M., & Elsinga, M. (2024). <i>Subsidies or green taxes? Evaluating the distributional effects of housing renovation policies among Dutch households.</i>
Inclusion	Tzika, Z., Sentieri, C. & Martínez, A. (2024) <i>Key topics and challenges for creating community-led, inclusive and sustainable housing: Catalonia's grant-of-use cooperative housing in Catalonia</i>
Income elasticity	Galvin, R., Sunikka-Blank, M., & Croon, T. M. (in print, 2024). <i>Juggling the Basics: How Much Does an Income Increase Affect Energy Spending of Low-Income Households in England.</i>
Industrialised constructions	Davis, A. (2024). <i>Circular Housing: Insights from Solar Decathlon Europe 2022.</i>
Land	Fernández, A., Haffner, M., & Elsinga, M. (2024). <i>When Land is Not Enough; Drawing in Private Capital to Increase Social Rental Housing in Spain.</i>
Life Cycle Assessment	Davis, A. (2022). <i>Design for Disassembly in housing: the need to adapt LCA to Shearing Layers.</i>
Low income	Galvin, R., Sunikka-Blank, M., & Croon, T. M. (in print, 2024). <i>Juggling the Basics: How Much Does an Income Increase Affect Energy Spending of Low-Income Households in England.</i>
MPC (Marginal Propensity to Consume)	Fernández, A. (2024). <i>Investigating the impact of housing price increases on consumption: Heterogeneity by age, tenure and housing quality.</i>
Netherlands	Croon, T. M., et al. (accepted, 2024). <i>Energy coaching and 'fix team' retrofitting to mitigate energy poverty: An ex-post analysis of treatment and interaction effects.</i>
Nicosia	Roussou, E., Ricchiardi, A. (2024). <i>Enclaves of commoning across the divide: self-organised spaces against divisions.</i>
Participation	<p>Panagidis, A., & Roussou, E. (2024) <i>Clientelism and infrastructural gaps in Southern Europe: The implications on housing and urban governance</i></p> <p>Tzika, Z., & Sentieri, C. (2024). <i>Housing as Community Infrastructure: Analysis of Senior Cooperative Housing Using the Capability Approach.</i></p> <p>Tzika, Z., Sentieri, C. & Martínez, A. (2024) <i>Key topics and challenges for creating community-led, inclusive and sustainable housing: Catalonia's grant-of-use cooperative housing in Catalonia.</i></p> <p>Tzika, Z., & Sentieri, C. (2023). <i>Towards collective forms of dwelling: Analysis of the characteristics of the emerging grant-of-use housing cooperatives in Catalonia.</i></p>

Participatory budget	Pappa, A., & Paio, A. (2023). <i>The role of commons-oriented policies in the transformation of urban governance: The case of the participatory budget BIP/ZIP in Lisbon.</i>
Placemaking	Dissart, J. C., & Ricaurte, L. (2023). <i>Assessing social value in housing design: contributions of the capability approach.</i>
PPP (Public-Private Partnerships)	Fernández, A., Haffner, M., & Elsinga, M. (2024). <i>When Land is Not Enough; Drawing in Private Capital to Increase Social Rental Housing in Spain.</i>
Qualitative research	Davis, A. (2024). <i>Circular Housing: Insights from Solar Decathlon Europe 2022.</i>
Quality of life	Dissart, J. C., & Ricaurte, L. (2023). <i>Assessing social value in housing design: contributions of the capability approach.</i>
Renovation	Croon, T. M., Hoekstra, J. S. C. M., & Dubois, U. (2024). <i>Energy poverty alleviation by social housing providers: A qualitative investigation of targeted interventions in France, England, and the Netherlands.</i> Fernández, A., Haffner, M., & Elsinga, M. (2024). <i>Subsidies or green taxes? Evaluating the distributional effects of housing renovation policies among Dutch households.</i> Fernández, A., Elsinga, M., & Haffner, M. (2023). <i>Three contradictions between ESG finance and social housing decarbonisation: a comparison of five European countries.</i>
Rent setting	Croon, T. M., Hoekstra, J. S. C. M., & Dubois, U. (2024). <i>Energy poverty alleviation by social housing providers: A qualitative investigation of targeted interventions in France, England, and the Netherlands.</i>
Resident engagement	Furman, S., Martínez, A., & Martín, X. (2024). <i>Social Housing Retrofit: Case studies in resident engagement.</i>
Residential comfort	Croon, T. M., et al. (accepted, 2024). <i>Energy coaching and 'fix team' retrofitting to mitigate energy poverty: An ex-post analysis of treatment and interaction effects.</i>
Residents	Furman, S., Martínez, A., & Martín, X. (2024). <i>Social Housing Retrofit: Case studies in resident engagement.</i> Dissart, J. C., & Ricaurte, L. (2023). <i>Assessing social value in housing design: contributions of the capability approach.</i>
Retrofit	Croon, T. M., et al. (2024). <i>Energy coaching and 'fix team' retrofitting to mitigate energy poverty: An ex-post analysis of treatment and interaction effects.</i> Furman, S., Martínez, A., & Martín, X. (2024). <i>Social Housing Retrofit: Case studies in resident engagement.</i>

	Furman, S. (2022). <i>Upgrading social housing to meet the socio-economic needs of today's dwellers, and the environmental needs of the planet: A framework beyond retrofit.</i>
Self-organised	Roussou, E., Ricchiardi, A. (2024). <i>Enclaves of commoning across the divide: self-organised spaces against divisions.</i>
Service providers	Horvat, M., & Bežovan, G. (2024). <i>Sustainability and Capacity Analysis of Croatian Homeless Service Providers.</i>
Shearing layers	Davis, A. (2022). <i>Design for Disassembly in housing: the need to adapt LCA to Shearing Layers.</i>
Spatial mapping	Roussou, E., Ricchiardi, A. (2024). <i>Enclaves of commoning across the divide: self-organised spaces against divisions.</i>
Social housing	<p>Alsaeed, M., A., Hadjri, H., & Nawratek, K. (2024). <i>Exploring the building blocks of sustainable social housing frameworks.</i></p> <p>Croon, T. M., Hoekstra, J. S. C. M., & Dubois, U. (2024). <i>Energy poverty alleviation by social housing providers: A qualitative investigation of targeted interventions in France, England, and the Netherlands.</i></p> <p>Fernández, A., Haffner, M., & Elsinga, M. (2024). <i>When Land is Not Enough; Drawing in Private Capital to Increase Social Rental Housing in Spain.</i></p> <p>Furman, S., Martínez, A., & Martín, X. (2024). <i>Social Housing Retrofit: Case studies in resident engagement.</i></p> <p>Fernández, A., Elsinga, M., & Haffner, M. (2023). <i>Investigating the role of ESG bonds and loans in financing housing renovation among social housing providers: a comparative approach to six European countries.</i></p> <p>Fernández, A., Elsinga, M., & Haffner, M. (2023). <i>Three contradictions between ESG finance and social housing decarbonisation: a comparison of five European countries.</i></p>
Social impact	Dissart, J. C., & Ricaurte, L. (2023). <i>Assessing social value in housing design: contributions of the capability approach.</i>
Social service	Horvat, M., & Bežovan, G. (2024). <i>Sustainability and Capacity Analysis of Croatian Homeless Service Providers.</i>
Social value	Dissart, J. C., & Ricaurte, L. (2023). <i>Assessing social value in housing design: contributions of the capability approach.</i>
Sustainability	<p>Alsaeed, M., Hadjri, H., & Nawratek, K. (2024). <i>Exploring the building blocks of sustainable social housing frameworks.</i></p> <p>Horvat, M., & Bežovan, G. (2024). <i>Sustainability and Capacity Analysis of Croatian Homeless Service Providers.</i></p> <p>Tzika, Z. (2024). <i>Housing as Community Infrastructure: Case Study Analysis of Catalonia's Grant-of-Use Cooperative Housing.</i></p>

	<p>Fernández, A., Elsinga, M., & Haffner, M. (2023). <i>Investigating the role of ESG bonds and loans in financing housing renovation among social housing providers: a comparative approach to six European countries.</i></p> <p>Furman, S. (2022). <i>Upgrading social housing to meet the socio-economic needs of today's dwellers, and the environmental needs of the planet: A framework beyond retrofit.</i></p>
Sustainable behaviour	<p>Croon, T. M., et al. (accepted, 2024). <i>Energy coaching and 'fix team' retrofitting to mitigate energy poverty: An ex-post analysis of treatment and interaction effects.</i></p>
Sustainable housing	<p>Davis, A. (2022). <i>Design for Disassembly in housing: the need to adapt LCA to Shearing Layers.</i></p> <p>Tzika, Z., & Sentieri, C. (accepted, 2024). <i>Housing as Community Infrastructure: Analysis of Senior Cooperative Housing Using the Capability Approach.</i></p>
Urban governance	<p>Pappa, A., & Paio, A. (2023). <i>The role of commons-oriented policies in the transformation of urban governance: The case of the participatory budget BIP/ZIP in Lisbon.</i></p>
User costs	<p>Fernández, A., Haffner, M., & Elsinga, M. (2024). <i>Subsidies or green taxes? Evaluating the distributional effects of housing renovation policies among Dutch households.</i></p>

2. Dissemination

The abstracts included in the Annex of this report have been published on the project website section “Dissemination: Publications” (Figure 1). Each publication on the website contains the abstract and keywords, as well as associated concepts, case studies and blog posts. In addition, a relational graph shows the links between the publication and the related items (Figure 2).

The screenshot shows the 'Publications' page on the RE-DWELL website. The page is structured as follows:

- Navigation Bar:** RE-DWELL logo, About, Training, Knowledge base, Dissemination, Blog, News, Contact.
- Page Header:** Home > Publications
- Main Section:**
 - Publications** (Large heading)
 - Contributions to conferences and journals made by ESRs in the course of their research** (Subtitle)
- Publication Cards:**
 - Card 1:** Eghandour, A., & Hadji, K. (2023, July). *Design as an advocate for households' health and wellbeing* [Conference paper]. UIA World Congress 2023, Sustainable Futures Leave No One Behind. A.Eghandour (ESR4), K.Hadji (Supervisor). [Read more](#)
 - Card 2:** Fernández, A., Haffner, M., & Elings, M. (2022, August-September). *Understanding the impact of energy efficiency on the housing costs to income ratio: an Instrumental Variable approach* [Conference paper]. European Network for Housing Research (ENHR) Conference 2022, Barcelona, Spain. M.Elings (Supervisor), A.Fernandez (ESR12), M.Haffner (Supervisor). [Read more](#)
 - Card 3:** *housing future past or present* [conference paper], architecture, Barcelona. A.Davis (ESR1). [Read more](#)
 - Card 4:** Tzika, Z., & Sentieri, C. (2022, February). *Understanding co-creation in the transdisciplinary research of sustainable and affordable housing* [Conference abstract]. Reinventing the city, Scientific conference AMS Institute, Amsterdam. C.Sentieri (Supervisor), Z.Tzika (ESR10). [Read more](#)
- Right Sidebar:**
 - affordable housing** x **community engagement** x
 - CATEGORIES** (dropdown)
 - ESRS** (dropdown)
 - SUPERVISORS** (dropdown)
 - TAGS** (dropdown): active citizenship (1), affordability (2), affordable housing (3), BIM (2), circular economy (2), civil organisations (1), co-creation (2), commons (1), community-engaged design (1), comparative housing (2), community power (1).
- Footer:**
 - RE-DWELL logo
 - European Commission logo
 - Text: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 995022.
 - Quick links: Network, Work packages, Training, Programs, Projects
 - Legal information: Privacy policy, Terms & conditions, Cookies policy
 - Follow us: Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram, Facebook, Youtube
 - © Design and programming by ABC Engineering and Architecture La Salla

Figure 1. View of Publications in RE-DWELL website

The screenshot displays the RE-DWELL website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for 'About', 'Training', 'Knowledge base', 'Classification', 'Blog', 'News', and 'Contact'. Below this, the main content area features the title 'Energy poverty alleviation by social housing providers: A qualitative investigation of targeted interventions in France, England, and the Netherlands' with a URL and a posting date of 28-09-2024. The 'Authors' section lists T. Ossen (ORCID). A sidebar on the left contains tags for 'Energy poverty', 'Social housing', 'Social groups', 'Renovation', 'Rent setting', and 'Housing allocation', along with a 'Share it' section. The main text area contains an abstract starting with 'Decisions made by social housing providers (SHPs) profoundly affect their tenants' energy affordability...'. Below the abstract are sections for 'Related case studies' (No articles), 'Related vocabulary' (Energy Poverty), 'Blogposts' (No articles), and 'Relational graph'. The relational graph is a network diagram with nodes representing different types of content: Case Study (green), Concept (blue), Publication (orange), and Blogpost (red). The central node is 'Energy Poverty: The in-depth study of energy p...'. Other nodes include 'Targeting energy efficiency...', 'Efficiency: A Combined Energy Efficiency A...', 'Energy Poverty: The in-depth study of energy p...', 'Summer in the City...', 'Collaboration transcending the...', 'The Social Climate Fund: More...', 'Greater than the sum of its pa...', 'Lisbon as a role model...', 'Bringing research-led projects...', 'Crown, T. (2022, August, The ...)', and 'Pre-1919 Middle Road Revolt...'. A legend at the top of the graph identifies the node types: Case Study (green square), Concept (blue square), Publication (orange square), and Blogpost (red square).

Figure 2. View of a publication on the RE-DWELL website

3. Conclusions

This compendium has provided a detailed description of the contributions made by the ESRs in the final year of the project. The year 2 report noted the increase in published scientific output, and that continues in this final compendium, with 9 published works: 6 published journal articles and 3 in print, and a published white paper.

The key terms continue to indicate the increasing specificity and diversity of the research within the broad concerns of the project. As noted, broad concerns around sustainability, participation, affordability, and social value continue to be the drivers. Within sustainability, the topics are widely varied; more specific interests include “circular economy”, “design for disassembly”, “ecosocial policy”, “energy poverty”, “green finance”, “life cycle assessment”, and “sustainable behaviour”. The interest in participation also reflects many viewpoints: “co-housing”, “collaborative housing” and “collective housing”, “commoning”, “community-led”, “focus groups”, “participatory budget”, and “urban governance”.

The lack of collaborative efforts between the ESRs compared to year 2 (only 1 collaborative paper in year 3) is perhaps understandable given the ESRs will be completing their individual PhDs. However, this suggests that there is much room for future collaborations beyond the life of the programme. Shared interests such as developing new frameworks, transdisciplinary methodologies, and comparison of different contexts within Europe all offer potentially exciting ways forward for future collaborations that can carry on the life of the programme beyond the official end date.

Annex 1 – Abstracts

Alsaeed, M., Hadjri, H., & Nawratek, K. (2024). *Exploring the building blocks of sustainable social housing frameworks*. Proceedings of the RE-DWELL Conference “Sustainable Living, Affordable Homes”, 16 May 2024, Barcelona, Spain

Abstract: The nexus between housing and sustainability is a multi-layered discourse often characterised by its ambiguity and complexity (Matthews, 2016). The realisation of large-scale, sustainable social housing projects is therefore associated with various challenges which require a comprehensive and systematic approach that transcends disciplinary boundaries. At the centre of this approach are frameworks that serve as fundamental constructs for planning and decision-making processes (Moghayedi et al., 2021). These frameworks embody a structured system of rules and ideologies that act as a supportive scaffold on which decisions are formulated. They also facilitate the formulation of standardised practices, principles, and detailed operational guidelines for sustainable housing provisions.

The development of a robust framework, regardless of its nature, requires the definition of a core set of pillars with careful attention to their structuring, organisation and interlinkage. Furthermore, these pillars are crucial in addressing real-world challenges that arise from both theoretical and practical perspectives in the delivery of sustainable social housing. To this end, the parameters that define social housing and sustainable housing frameworks are first examined through an exploratory literature review. Then, the challenges associated with the delivery of sustainable housing are identified through a synthesis of literature and semi-structured interviews with various actors such as housing associations, designers, and sustainability specialists.

A trilogy of pillars needed for the development of sustainable social housing frameworks is proposed; this is established around three thematic areas: Sustainability and its dimensions, social housing processes and perceptions, and the roles and responsibilities of public authorities. It is important to note that while this mapping represents a first step for housing researchers and industry professionals seeking to develop operational frameworks for sustainable social housing projects, it is not itself a framework. Instead, it lays the foundation for a common understanding of future sustainable social housing frameworks.

References:

Fokaides, P. A., Polycarpou, K., & Kalogirou, S. (2017). The impact of the implementation of the European Energy Performance of Buildings Directive on the European building stock: The case of the Cyprus Land Development Corporation. *Energy policy*, 111, 1-8.

Granath Hansson, A., & Lundgren, B. (2019). Defining social housing: A discussion on the suitable criteria. *Housing, Theory and Society*, 36(2), 149-166.

Harriott, S., Matthews, L., & Grainger, P. (2004). *Introducing social housing*. Chartered Institute of Housing.

Joffe, H., & Yardley, L. (2003). Chapter four: content and thematic analysis. *Research Methods for Clinical and Health Psychology*. Marks D, Yardley L (ed): Sage Publications, London, 56-68.

Knox, N. (2015). *What is WELL? The WELL Building Standard*. WELL Building Institute (IWBI).

Kruger, A., & Seville, C. (2012). *Green building: principles and practices in residential construction*. Cengage Learning.

Kubba, S. (2012). *Handbook of green building design and construction: LEED, BREEAM, and Green Globes*. Butterworth-Heinemann.

Malpass, P., & Victory, C. (2010). The modernisation of social housing in England. *International Journal of Housing Policy*, 10(1), 3-18.

Matthews, P. (2016, 2016/05/18). What is housing studies for and what impact does it have? *Housing Studies*, 31(4), 490-493. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02673037.2016.1152028>

Moghayedi, A., Awuzie, B., Omotayo, T., Le Jeune, K., Massyn, M., Ekpo, C. O., Braune, M., & Byron, P. (2021). A critical success factor framework for implementing sustainable innovative and affordable housing: a systematic review and bibliometric analysis. *Buildings*, 11(8), 317.

Murphy, R. (2012). Sustainability: A wicked problem. *Sociologica*, 6(2).

Oyebanji, A. O. (2014). Development of a framework for sustainable social housing provision (SSHP) in England University of Central Lancashire].

Peters, R. W. (2013). Green building, principles and practices in residential construction. Wiley Online Library.

Poveda, C. A., & Lipsett, M. G. (2011). A review of sustainability assessment and sustainability/environmental rating systems and credit weighting tools. *Journal of Sustainable Development*, 4(6), 36.

Priemus, H. (2013). The future of social housing. The Dutch case. *International Journal of co-operative management*, 6(2), 13-24.

Stephens, M. (2013). Social housing in the United Kingdom. In *The future of public housing* (pp. 199-213). Springer.

Udomiaye, E., Okon, I. U., Uzodimma, O. C., & Patrick, N. (2018). Eco-friendly buildings: the architect's perspectives. *International Journal of Civil Engineering, Construction and Estate Management*, 6(2), 14-26.

UKGBC. (2021). The New Homes Policy Playbook: driving sustainability in new homes. UK Green Building Council. <https://ukgbc.org/resources/new-homes-policy-playbook/>

Keywords: Social Housing, Sustainability, Frameworks

Croon, T. M., Hoekstra, J. S. C. M., & Dubois, U. (2024). *Energy poverty alleviation by social housing providers: A qualitative investigation of targeted interventions in France, England, and the Netherlands*. *Energy Policy*, 192, 114247.

Abstract: Decisions made by social housing providers (SHPs) profoundly affect their tenants' energy affordability, a group characterised by above-average energy poverty rates. Concentrated deprivation in this tenure has intensified due to policy-driven 'residualisation', compelling SHPs to serve almost exclusively low-income and marginalised households. Despite this, research exploring the potential of SHPs to tackle energy poverty through targeted interventions for their most vulnerable tenants remains sparse. The 2021–2022 energy price crisis offers a unique context to investigate this issue, given its substantial impact on household energy affordability. This study delves into insights of social housing professionals through focus groups conducted in France, England, and the Netherlands. It examines their views on the effectiveness of interventions and assesses their feasibility within the respective institutional contexts. We find that SHPs generally favour retrofit prioritisation and behavioural interventions as effective means of supporting at-risk tenants, whereas alterations in rent setting or housing allocation are considered potentially impactful but often undesirable or impracticable. We identify institutional barriers and lack of data as key obstacles to SHPs' adoption of more targeted

interventions. To empower SHPs in tackling energy poverty, housing policy reforms must acknowledge and address the significant impact of energy costs within total housing expenses.

References:

Amzallag, M., Taffin, C., 2010. Social Rental Housing in France, 62497. World Bank. Aruta, G., Ascione, F., Bianco, N., Iovane, T., Mastellone, M., Maria Mauro, G., 2023.

Optimizing the energy transition of social housing to renewable nearly zero-energy community: the goal of sustainability. *Energy Build.* 282 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2023.112798>.

Avanzini, M., Pinheiro, M.D., Gomes, R., Rolim, C., 2022. Energy retrofit as an answer to public health costs of fuel poverty in Lisbon social housing. *Energy Pol.* 160 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2021.112658>.

Barrella, R., Linares, J.I., Romero, J.C., Arenas, E., Centeno, E., 2021. Does cash money solve energy poverty? Assessing the impact of household heating allowances in Spain. *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 80 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2021.102216>.

Bednar, D.J., Reames, T.G., 2020. Recognition of and response to energy poverty in the United States. *Nat. Energy* 5 (6), 432–439. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-020-0582-0>.

Bessa, S., Gouveia, J.P., 2022. A framework for policy mix analysis: assessing energy poverty policies. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Policy* 12 (4), 438–454. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21606544.2022.2153744>.

Best, R., Hammerle, M., Mukhopadhaya, P., Silber, J., 2021. Targeting household energy assistance. *Energy Econ.* 99 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2021.105311>.

Boardman, B., 1991. *Fuel Poverty: from Cold Homes to Affordable Warmth*. Pinter Pub Limited.

Bouzarovski, S., Burbidge, M., Sarpotdar, A., Martiskainen, M., 2022. The diversity penalty: domestic energy injustice and ethnic minorities in the United Kingdom. *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 91 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102716>.

Breukers, S., Mourik, R.M., Van Summeren, L.F.M., Verbong, G.P.J., 2017. Institutional 'lock-out' towards local self-governance? Environmental justice and sustainable transformations in Dutch social housing neighbourhoods. *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 23, 148–158. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2016.10.007>.

Bridgen, P., Robinson, C., 2023. A decade of fuel poverty in England: a spatio-temporal analysis of needs-based targeting of domestic energy efficiency obligations. *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 101 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2023.103139>.

Broers, W., Kemp, R., Vasseur, V., Abujidi, N., Vroon, Z., 2022. Justice in social housing: towards a people-centred energy renovation process. *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 88 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102527>.

Clarke, A., Cheshire, L., Parsell, C., Morris, A., 2022. Reified scarcity & the problem space of 'need': unpacking Australian social housing policy. *Hous. Stud.* 39 (2), 565–583. Cowan, D., McDermont, M., 2021. *Regulating Social Housing: Governing Decline*. Taylor & Francis.

Croon, T.M., Hoekstra, J.S.C.M., Elsinga, M.G., Dalla Longa, F., Mulder, P., 2023. Beyond headcount statistics: exploring the utility of energy poverty gap indices in policy design. *Energy Pol.* 177 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2023.113579>.

Czischke, D., van Bortel, G., 2018. An exploration of concepts and policies on 'affordable housing' in England, Italy, Poland and The Netherlands. *J. Hous. Built Environ.* 38(1), 283–303. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10901-018-9598-1>.

De Feijter, F.J., van Vliet, B.J.M., Chen, Y., 2019. Household inclusion in the governance of housing retrofitting: analysing Chinese and Dutch systems of energy retrofit provision. *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 53, 10–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2019.02.006>.

Della Valle, N., D'Arcangelo, C., Faillo, M., 2024. Promoting pro-environmental choices while addressing energy poverty. *Energy Pol.* 186 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2023.113967>.

DellaValle, N., Czako, V., 2022. Empowering energy citizenship among the energy poor. *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 89 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102654>.

DellaValle, N., Sareen, S., 2020. Nudging and boosting for equity? Towards a behavioural economics of energy justice. *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 68 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101589>.

DESNZ, 2023. Annual Fuel Poverty Statistics in England, 2023 (2022 data).

<https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/63fcdcaa8fa8f527fe30db41/annual-fuel-poverty-statistics-lilee-report-2023-2022-data.pdf>.

Desvallees, L., 2022. Low-carbon retrofits in social housing: energy efficiency, multidimensional energy poverty, and domestic comfort strategies in southern Europe. *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 85

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2021.102413>.

Devereux, S., Masset, E., Sabates-Wheeler, R., Samson, M., Rivas, A.-M., te Lintelo, D., 2017. The targeting effectiveness of social transfers. *J. Dev. Effect.* 9 (2), 162–211.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/19439342.2017.1305981>.

Dewilde, C., 2022. How housing affects the association between low income and living conditions-deprivation across Europe. *Soc. Econ. Rev.* 20 (1), 373–400. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ser/mwab003>.

Directive (EU) 2023/1791 on energy efficiency, 2023. https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficiency-targets-directive-and-rules/energy-efficiency-directive_en.

Dubois, U., 2012. From targeting to implementation: the role of identification of fuel poor households. *Energy Pol.* 49, 107–115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2011.11.087>.

Dubois, U., Sinea, A., 2023. Methodological challenges in energy poverty research. *Int. J. Mark. Res.* 65 (2–3), 340–358. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14707853231155393>.

Egmond, C., Jonkers, R., Kok, G., 2005. A strategy to encourage housing associations to invest in energy conservation. *Energy Pol.* 33 (18), 2374–2384. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2004.05.007>.

Elsinga, M., Van der Heijden, H., Donoso Gomez, R., 2020. Impact of social housing on the social structure of the Randstad. In: *The Randstad*. Routledge, pp. 188–206. EPAH, 2023a. Energy poverty advisory hub (EPAH) handbook 1: a guide to energy poverty diagnosis, march 2023. https://energy-poverty.ec.europa.eu/document/download/048ecbe6-8f2e-4880-97f2-3b238eb1eedc_en?filename=EPAHhandbook_diagnosis_finalpdf.pdf.

https://energy-poverty.ec.europa.eu/document/download/048ecbe6-8f2e-4880-97f2-3b238eb1eedc_en?filename=EPAHhandbook_diagnosis_finalpdf.pdf.

EPAH, 2023b. Energy poverty. National indicators. Uncovering new possibilities for expanded knowledge. Energy Poverty Advisory Hub. October 2023. https://energy-poverty.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-10/EPAH2023_2nd-20Indicators-20Report_Final_0.pdf.

Finney, N., Harries, B., Rhodes, J., Lympelopoulou, K., 2018. The roles of social housing providers in creating 'integrated' communities. *J. Ethnic Migrat. Stud.* 45 (17), 3207–3224.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/1369183x.2018.1480997>.

Fizaine, F., Kahouli, S., 2019. On the power of indicators: how the choice of fuel poverty indicator affects the identification of the target population. *Appl. Econ.* 51 (11).

- Galvin, R., 2023. An under-developed dimension in upgrading energy-inefficient German rental buildings: corporate social responsibility as a hybrid form of governance. *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 101 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2023.103148>.
- Granath Hansson, A., Lundgren, B., 2018. Defining social housing: a discussion on the suitable criteria. *Hous. Theor. Soc.* 36 (2), 149–166. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14036096.2018.1459826>.
- Grosh, M., Leite, P., Wai-Poi, M., Tesliuc, E., 2022. Revisiting Targeting in Social Assistance: A New Look at Old Dilemmas. World Bank Publications.
- Grossmann, K., Jiglau, G., Dubois, U., Sinea, A., Martín-Consuegra, F., Dereniowska, M., Franke, R., Guyet, R., Horta, A., Katman, F., Papamikrouli, L., Castañó-Rosa, R., Sandmann, L., Stojilovska, A., Varo, A., 2021. The critical role of trust in experiencing and coping with energy poverty: evidence from across Europe. *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 76 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2021.102064>.
- Haffner, M., Hoekstra, J., Oxley, M., Heijden, H.V.D., 2010. Universalistic, particularistic and middle way approaches to comparing the private rental sector. *International Journal of Housing Policy* 10 (4), 357–377. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616718.2010.526400>.
- Hoekstra, J., 2017. Reregulation and residualization in Dutch social housing: a critical evaluation of new policies. *Critical Housing Analysis* 4 (1), 31–39. <https://doi.org/10.13060/23362839.2017.4.1.322>.
- Housing Europe, 2021. The State of Housing in Europe in 2021. <https://www.housingeurope.eu/resource-1540/the-state-of-housing-in-europe-in-2021>.
- Kearns, A., Whitley, E., Curl, A., 2019. Occupant behaviour as a fourth driver of fuel poverty (aka warmth & energy deprivation). *Energy Pol.* 129, 1143–1155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2019.03.023>.
- Kholodilin, K.A., Kohl, S., Müller, F., 2022. The rise and fall of social housing? Housing decommodification in long-run comparison. *J. Soc. Pol.* 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0047279422000770>.
- Kodousková, H., Ilavská, A., Stašáková, T., David, D., Osička, J., 2023. Energy transition for the rich and energy poverty for the rest? Mapping and explaining district heating transition, energy poverty, and vulnerability in Czechia. *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 100 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2023.103128>.
- Kodousková, H., Lehotský, L., 2021. Energy poverty in the Czech Republic: individual responsibility or structural issue? *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 72 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101877>.
- Lausberg, P., Croon, T.M., 2023. Europe must fight energy poverty more effectively. <https://www.epc.eu/en/publications/-Europe-must-fight-energy-poverty-more-effectively~4da8dc>.
- L'Évy-Vroelant, C., Reinprecht, C., Robertson, D., Wassenberg, F., 2014. Learning from history: path dependency and change in the social housing sectors of Austria, France, The Netherlands and Scotland, 1889–2013. In: Scanlon, K., Whitehead, C., Arrigoitia, M.F. (Eds.), *Social Housing in Europe*. Wiley, pp. 123–142.
- Liddell, C., Morris, C., 2010. Fuel poverty and human health: a review of recent evidence. *Energy Pol.* 38 (6), 2987–2997. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2010.01.037>.
- Liu, X., Yang, D., Arentze, T., Wielders, T., 2023. The willingness of social housing tenants to participate in natural gas-free heating systems project: insights from a stated choice experiment in The Netherlands. *Appl. Energy* 350. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2023.121706>.
- Longhurst, N., Hargreaves, T., 2019. Emotions and fuel poverty: the lived experience of social housing tenants in the United Kingdom. *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 56 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2019.05.017>.
- Maestre-Andres, S., Drews, S., Savin, I., van den Bergh, J., 2021. Carbon tax acceptability with information provision and mixed revenue uses. *Nat. Commun.* 12 (1), 7017. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-27380-8>.

Middlemiss, L., 2017. A critical analysis of the new politics of fuel poverty in England. *Crit. Soc. Pol.* 37 (3), 425–443. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0261018316674851C>.

Moore, R., 2012. Definitions of fuel poverty: implications for policy. *Energy Pol.* 49, 19–26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2012.01.057>.

Mulder, P., Dalla Longa, F., Straver, K., 2023. Energy poverty in The Netherlands at the national and local level: a multi-dimensional spatial analysis. *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 96 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102892>.

Murray, A.G., Mills, B.F., 2014. The impact of low-income home energy assistance program participation on household energy insecurity. *Contemp. Econ. Pol.* 32 (4), 811–825. <https://doi.org/10.1111/coep.12050>.

Analyses rétrospectives de la précarité énergétique à partir de l'exploitation des Enquêtes Nationales Logement de 2006 et de 2013. <https://onpe.org/documents/rapports-de-l-onpe>.

Pearce, J., Vine, J., 2013. Quantifying residualisation: the changing nature of social housing in the UK. *J. Hous. Built Environ.* 29 (4), 657–675. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10901-013-9372-3>.

Poggio, T., Whitehead, C., 2017. Social housing in Europe: legacies, new trends and the crisis. *Critical Housing Analysis* 4 (1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.13060/23362839.2017.3.1.319>.

Preece, J., Hickman, P., Pattison, B., 2019. The affordability of “affordable” housing in England: conditionality and exclusion in a context of welfare reform. *Hous. Stud.* 35 (7), 1214–1238. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02673037.2019.1653448>.

Reeves, P., 2013. *Affordable and Social Housing: Policy and Practice*. Routledge. Sareen, S., Thomson, H., Tirado Herrero, S., Gouveia, J.P., Lippert, I., Lis, A., 2020.

European energy poverty metrics: scales, prospects and limits. *Global Transitions* 2, 26–36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.glt.2020.01.003>.

Scanlon, K., Fernández Arrigoitia, M., Whitehead, C., 2015. Social housing in Europe. *European Policy Analysis* (17), 1–12.

Schuck, P.H., Zeckhauser, R.J., 2007. *Targeting in Social Programs: Avoiding Bad Bets, Removing Bad Apples*. Rowman & Littlefield.

Sdei, A., Gloriant, F., Tittlein, P., Lassue, S., Hanna, P., Beslay, C., Gournet, R., McEvoy, M., 2015. Social housing retrofit strategies in England and France: a parametric and behavioural analysis. *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 10, 62–71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2015.07.001>.

Sen, A., 1998. The political economy of targeting. *Publ. Choice* 95 (1/2), 177–200. <https://doi.org/10.1023/a:1005023531490>.

Shirani, F., Groves, C., Henwood, K., Pidgeon, N., Roberts, E., 2020. ‘I’m the smart meter’: perceptions of smart technology amongst vulnerable consumers. *Energy Pol.* 144 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2020.111637>.

Simcock, N., Bouzarovski, S., 2023. A cure-all for energy poverty? Thinking critically about energy advice. *Crit. Soc. Pol.* <https://doi.org/10.1177/02610183231219185>.

Simshauser, P., 2021. Vulnerable households and fuel poverty: measuring the efficiency of policy targeting in Queensland. *Energy Econ.* 101 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2021.105405>.

Simshauser, P., 2023. The 2022 energy crisis: fuel poverty and the impact of policy interventions in Australia’s National Electricity Market. *Energy Econ.* 121 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2023.106660>.

Van Bortel, G., Gruis, V., Nieuwenhuijzen, J., Pluijmers, B., 2018. Introduction. In: Van Bortel, G., Gruis, V., Nieuwenhuijzen, J., Pluijmers, B. (Eds.), *Affordable Housing Governance and Finance: Innovations, Partnerships and Comparative Perspectives*. Routledge, pp. 1–23.

Van de Walle, D., 1998. Targeting revisited. *World Bank Res. Obs.* 13 (2), 231–248.

Van der Schoor, Y., Duyndam, J., Witte, T., Machielse, A., 2021. 'What's important to me is to get people moving.' Fostering social resilience in people with severe debt problems. *Eur. J. Soc. Work* 25 (4), 592–604. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13691457.2021.1997930>.

Van Deursen, H., 2023. The people's housing: woning corporaties and the Dutch social housing system. Part 2: The Mechanics. https://www.jchs.harvard.edu/sites/default/files/research/files/harvard_jchs_the_peoples_housing_mechanics_van_deursen_2023.pdf.

Wahlund, M., Palm, J., 2022. The role of energy democracy and energy citizenship for participatory energy transitions: a comprehensive review. *Energy Res. Social Sci.* 87 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2021.102482>.

Walker, G., Day, R., 2012. Fuel poverty as injustice: integrating distribution, recognition and procedure in the struggle for affordable warmth. *Energy Pol.* 49, 69–75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2012.01.044>.

Keywords: Energy Poverty, Social Housing, Focus Groups, Renovation, Rent Setting, Housing Allocation

Croon, T. M., Maghsoudi Nia, E., He, S., Qian, Q., Elsinga, M., Hoekstra, J., van Ooij, C., & van der Wal, A. (accepted, 2024). *Energy coaching and 'fix team' retrofitting to mitigate energy poverty: An ex-post analysis of treatment and interaction effects.* *Energy Research & Social Science*.

Abstract: Rising energy prices across Europe have increased concerns over energy poverty. Despite significant scholarly focus on financial relief measures instituted by national governments, locally tailored crisis measures have remained overlooked. This study delves into the Dutch context, where part of the government's response to the energy crisis was decentralised, allowing municipalities considerable discretion in experimenting with energy poverty interventions. It compares two strategies: 'energy coaching' services – offering advice on sustainable energy practices – and shallow retrofitting by 'fix teams' – installing minor energy-saving measures in homes. The impact of these interventions on residential comfort, sustainable behaviour adoption, and (financial concerns regarding) energy bills is assessed through an extensive survey involving treatment and control groups coupled with detailed administrative data on households and dwellings. Results indicate that, on an aggregate level, local interventions significantly enhanced perceived comfort and reduced energy bills among the treatment groups. Comparing individual interventions, notably, more extensive ones such as fix teams and comprehensive energy coaching were significantly more impactful than those involving a single visit, highlighting the importance of continuous engagement. Additionally, we found that energy poverty status significantly amplified the effectiveness of these interventions, thereby stressing the importance of targeting interventions on vulnerable households.

References:

Middlemiss, L. and R. Gillard, Fuel poverty from the bottom-up: Characterising household energy vulnerability through the lived experience of the fuel poor. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 2015. 6: p. 146-154.

Mundaca, L., S. Rotmann, K. Ashby, B. Karlin, D. Butler, M.M. Sequeira, J.P. Gouveia, P. Palma, A. Realini, S. Maggiore, and M. Feenstra, Hard-to-reach energy users: An ex-post cross-country assessment of behavioural-oriented interventions. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 2023. 104.

Reames, T.G., Targeting energy justice: Exploring spatial, racial/ethnic and socioeconomic disparities in urban residential heating energy efficiency. *Energy Policy*, 2016. 97: p. 549-558.

Walker, G. and R. Day, Fuel poverty as injustice: Integrating distribution, recognition and procedure in the struggle for affordable warmth. *Energy Policy*, 2012. 49: p. 69-75.

Simcock, N. and S. Bouzarovski, A cure-all for energy poverty? Thinking critically about energy advice. *Critical Social Policy*, 2023.

DellaValle, N. and V. Czako, Empowering energy citizenship among the energy poor. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 2022. 89.

Green, J., S. Darby, C. Maby, and B. Boardman, Advice into Action. 1998: EAGA Charitable Trust.

Schneider, P.T., A. van de Rijt, C. Boele, and V. Buskens, Are visits of Dutch energy coach volunteers associated with a reduction in gas and electricity consumption? *Energy Efficiency*, 2023. 16(5).

Boardman, B. and S.J. Darby, Effective Advice: Energy Efficiency and the Disadvantaged. 2000: Environmental Change Institute, University of Oxford.

Ambrose, A., W. Baker, E. Batty, and A. Hawkins, Reaching the 'Hardest to Reach' with Energy Advice. 2019, Sheffield Hallam University.

Malier, H., Greening the poor: the trap of moralization. *Br J Sociol*, 2019. 70(5): p. 1661-1680.

Royston, S., J. Selby, and E. Shove, Invisible energy policies: A new agenda for energy demand reduction. *Energy Policy*, 2018. 123: p. 127-135.

Hall, S.M., Energy justice and ethical consumption: comparison, synthesis and lesson drawing. *Local Environment*, 2013. 18(4): p. 422-437.

Chen, C.-f., X. Xu, and J.K. Day, Thermal comfort or money saving? Exploring intentions to conserve energy among low-income households in the United States. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 2017. 26: p. 61-71.

Semprini, G., R. Gulli, and A. Ferrante, Deep regeneration vs shallow renovation to achieve nearly Zero Energy in existing buildings. *Energy and Buildings*, 2017. 156: p. 327-342.

Barrella, R., J.C. Romero, A. Laguillo, and E. Sevilla, Assessing the Impact of Shallow Renovation on Energy Poverty: A Primary Data Study. *Energies*, 2023. 16(21).

Elnagar, E., S. Gendebien, E. Georges, U. Berardi, S. Doutreloup, and V. Lemort, Framework to assess climate change impact on heating and cooling energy demands in building stock: A case study of Belgium in 2050 and 2100. *Energy and Buildings*, 2023. 298.

Milne, G. and B. Boardman, Making cold homes warmer: the effect of energy efficiency improvements in low-income homes. *Energy Policy*, 2000. 28: p. 411-424.

Baker, K.J., R. Mould, F. Stewart, S. Restrict, H. Melone, and B. Atterson, Never try and face the journey alone: Exploring the face-to-face advocacy needs of fuel poor householders in the United Kingdom. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 2019. 51: p. 210-219.

Pierse, N., M. White, J. Ombler, C. Davis, E. Chisholm, M. Baker, and P. Howden-Chapman, Well Homes Initiative: a home-based intervention to address housing-related ill health. *Health Education & Behavior*, 2020. 47(6): p. 836-844.

Reeves, A., Exploring Local and Community Capacity to Reduce Fuel Poverty: The Case of Home Energy Advice Visits in the UK. *Energies*, 2016. 9(4).

Ahern, C. and B. Norton, Energy savings across EU domestic building stock by optimizing hydraulic distribution in domestic space heating systems. *Energy and Buildings*, 2015. 91: p. 199-209.

- Darby, S., Energy advice–what is it worth. Proceedings, European Council for an Energy-Efficient Economy Summer Study, paper III, 1999. 5: p. 3-15.
- Feenstra, M., L. Middlemiss, M. Hesselman, K. Straver, and S. Tirado Herrero, Humanising the Energy Transition: Towards a National Policy on Energy Poverty in the Netherlands. *Frontiers in Sustainable Cities*, 2021. 3.
- Mulder, P., F. Dalla Longa, and K. Straver, Energy poverty in the Netherlands at the national and local level: A multi-dimensional spatial analysis. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 2023. 96.
- Croon, T.M., J.S.C.M. Hoekstra, M.G. Elsinga, F. Dalla Longa, and P. Mulder, Beyond headcount statistics: Exploring the utility of energy poverty gap indices in policy design. *Energy Policy*, 2023. 177.
- Devenish, A. and M. Lockwood, Locally-led governance of residential heat transitions: Emerging experience of and lessons from the Dutch approach. *Energy Policy*, 2024. 187.
- Sgaravatti, G., S. Tagliapietra, C. Trasi, and G. Zachmann, National fiscal policy responses to the energy crisis [Dataset]. 2023.
- Maghsoudi Nia, E., Q.K. Qian, and H.J. Visscher, Occupants' inquiries for energy efficiency retrofitting in the Netherlands. *Energy and Buildings*, 2024. 308.
- Ministerie van Binnenlandse Zaken en Koninkrijksrelaties, Kamerbrief versnelling aanpak energiearmoede gebouwde omgeving. 2023.
- Ramsden, S., Tackling fuel poverty through household advice and support: Exploring the impacts of a charity-led project in a disadvantaged city in the United Kingdom. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 2020. 70.
- Boomsma, C., S. Pahl, R.V. Jones, and A. Fuertes, "Damp in bathroom. Damp in back room. It's very depressing!" exploring the relationship between perceived housing problems, energy affordability concerns, and health and well-being in UK social housing. *Energy Policy*, 2017. 106: p. 382-393.
- Bashir, N., A.C.d. Chavez, J. Gilbertson, A. Tod, E. Sanderson, and I. Wilson, An evaluation of the FILT Warm Homes Service 2013.
- Ringel, M., Energy advice in Germany: a market actors' perspective. *International Journal of Energy Sector Management*, 2018. 12(4): p. 656-674.
- Lomas, K.J., Carbon reduction in existing buildings: a transdisciplinary approach. *Building Research & Information*, 2010. 38(1): p. 1-11.
- Abrahamse, W. and L. Steg, Social influence approaches to encourage resource conservation: A meta-analysis. *Global Environmental Change*, 2013. 23(6): p. 1773-1785.
- Revell, K.M. and N.A. Stanton, Case studies of mental models in home heat control: searching for feedback, valve, timer and switch theories. *Appl Ergon*, 2014. 45(3): p. 363-78.
- Mahapatra, K., G. Nair, and L. Gustavsson, Swedish energy advisers' perceptions regarding and suggestions for fulfilling homeowner expectations. *Energy Policy*, 2011. 39(7): p. 4264-4273.
- Bouzarovski, S., M. Burbidge, A. Sarpotdar, and M. Martiskainen, The diversity penalty: Domestic energy injustice and ethnic minorities in the United Kingdom. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 2022. 91.
- Mahapatra, K. and L. Gustavsson, Innovative approaches to domestic heating: homeowners' perceptions and factors influencing their choice of heating system. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 2007. 32(1): p. 75-87.
- Revell, K.M.A. and N.A. Stanton, When energy saving advice leads to more, rather than less, consumption. *International Journal of Sustainable Energy*, 2017. 36(1): p. 1-19.

Berkhout, P.H.G., J.C. Muskens, and J.W. Velthuis, Defining the rebound effect. *Energy Policy*, 2000. 28: p. 425-432.

Sunikka-Blank, M. and R. Galvin, Introducing the prebound effect: the gap between performance and actual energy consumption. *Building Research & Information*, 2012. 40(3): p. 260-273.

Rabaa, S., R. Wilken, and S. Geisendorf, Does recalling energy efficiency measures reduce subsequent climate-friendly behavior? An experimental study of moral licensing rebound effects. *Ecological Economics*, 2024. 217.

Straver, K., A. Siebenga, and M. Van Lidth de Jeude, Effectieve interventies om energie efficiëntie te vergroten en energiewaarde te verlagen. 2017.

Forster, N., P. Hodgson, and C. Bailey, Energy advice for Traveller Communities in the context of ethnic and spatial premiums: 'paying the price' for other people's choices. *Journal of Poverty and Social Justice*, 2019. 27(1): p. 61-78.

Hernandez, D., D. Phillips, and E.L. Siegel, Exploring the Housing and Household Energy Pathways to Stress: A Mixed Methods Study. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*, 2016. 13(9).

Jessel, S., S. Sawyer, and D. Hernandez, Energy, Poverty, and Health in Climate Change: A Comprehensive Review of an Emerging Literature. *Front Public Health*, 2019. 7: p. 357.

Statistics Netherlands, Monitor Energiearmoede 2020 [Non-public]. 2023.

Statistics Netherlands, Documentatierapport Energiearmoede [In Dutch]. 2023.

Deller, D., G. Turner, and C. Waddams Price, Energy poverty indicators: Inconsistencies, implications and where next? *Energy Economics*, 2021. 103.

Bruderer Enzler, H. and A. Diekmann, All talk and no action? An analysis of environmental concern, income and greenhouse gas emissions in Switzerland. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 2019. 51: p. 12-19.

Roth, L., J. Lowitzsch, Ö. Yildiz, and A. Hashani, Does (Co-)ownership in renewables matter for an electricity consumer's demand flexibility? Empirical evidence from Germany. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 2018. 46: p. 169-182.

Mudombi, S., C. Ochieng, F.X. Johnson, G. von Maltitz, D. Luhanga, E.B. Dompok, C. Romeu-Dalmau, and A. Gasparatos, Fuelling rural development? The impact of biofuel feedstock production in southern Africa on household income and expenditures. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 2021. 76.

MacNaughton, P., J. Spengler, J. Vallarino, S. Santanam, U. Satish, and J. Allen, Environmental Perceptions and Health before and after Relocation to a Green Building. *Build Environ*, 2016. 104: p. 138-144.

Chen, W.-A., C.-f. Chen, M. Liu, and R. Rickard, Unraveling the complexities: Impacts of energy burden on the built environment challenges among assistance-dependent populations in the United Kingdom. *Building and Environment*, 2024. 254.

Hatch, M.E. and M. Graff, Housing costs are not a monolith: The association between neighborhood energy burdens and eviction filing rates. *Cities*, 2024. 150.

Teli, D., T. Dimitriou, P.A.B. James, A.S. Bahaj, L. Ellison, and A. Waggott, Fuel poverty-induced 'prebound effect' in achieving the anticipated carbon savings from social housing retrofit. *Building Services Engineering Research and Technology*, 2015. 37(2): p. 176-193.

Palm, J., K. Reindl, and A. Ambrose, Understanding tenants' responses to energy efficiency renovations in public housing in Sweden: From the resigned to the demanding. *Energy Reports*, 2020. 6: p. 2619-2626.

Brounen, D., N. Kok, and J.M. Quigley, Residential energy use and conservation: Economics and demographics. *European Economic Review*, 2012. 56(5): p. 931-945.

Bajo-Buenestado, R., Welfare implications of capacity payments in a price-capped electricity sector: A case study of the Texas market (ERCOT). *Energy Economics*, 2017. 64: p. 272-285.

Garcia, A. and E. Stacchetti, Investment dynamics in electricity markets. *Economic Theory*, 2009. 46(2): p. 149-187.

Dao, M.C., A. Dizioli, C. Jackson, P.-O. Gourinchas, and D. Leigh, Unconventional Fiscal Policy in Times of High Inflation [ECB Forum on Central Banking Working Paper]. 2023.

Frilingou, N., G. Xexakis, K. Koasidis, A. Nikas, L. Campagnolo, E. Delpiazzi, A. Chiodi, M. Gargiulo, B. McWilliams, T. Koutsellis, and H. Doukas, Navigating through an energy crisis: Challenges and progress towards electricity decarbonisation, reliability, and affordability in Italy. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 2023. 96.

Broers, W., R. Kemp, V. Vasseur, M. Markantoni, N. Abujidi, and Z. Vroon, Crossing multiple solar energy gaps: A Dutch case study on intermediation for building-integrated photovoltaics. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 2023. 102.

Hofman, P., M. Stapper, and M. Groenleer, Exploring the Role of Intermediaries in the Acceleration Stage of the Energy Transition: A Comparative Case Study of Two Local Energy Projects. *European Journal of Risk Regulation*, 2023. 14(3): p. 549-563.

De Wilde, M., The sustainable housing question: On the role of interpersonal, impersonal and professional trust in low-carbon retrofit decisions by homeowners. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 2019. 51: p. 138-147.

Grossmann, K., G. Jiglau, U. Dubois, A. Sinea, F. Martín-Consuegra, M. Dereniowska, R. Franke, R. Guyet, A. Horta, F. Katman, L. Papamikrouli, R. Castaño-Rosa, L. Sandmann, A. Stojilovska, and A. Varo, The critical role of trust in experiencing and coping with energy poverty: Evidence from across Europe. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 2021. 76.

Keywords: Energy Poverty, Energy Coaching, Retrofitting, Residential Comfort, Sustainable Behaviour, Netherlands

Galvin, R., Sunikka-Blank, M., & Croon, T. M. (in print, 2024). *Juggling the Basics: How Much Does an Income Increase Affect Energy Spending of Low-Income Households in England.* *Energy Research & Social Science*.

Abstract: European governments have deployed targeted and untargeted financial support to protect vulnerable households from the impacts of the recent energy crisis. However, there is little knowledge of income elasticity of energy expenditure among households experiencing energy poverty. We therefore examine the link between energy expenditure and household income levels, considering a spectrum of factors including energy poverty status, energy efficiency of homes, and socio-demographics. We use England's official energy poverty definition, 'Low-income, low-energy-efficiency', and analyse the government's 'Fuel Poverty Dataset' from 2019. We find that, for all income groups, by far the greatest impact on energy expenditure is the dwelling's energy-efficiency rating, followed by floor area. An increase in income has negligible effects on energy expenditure for all income groups, but greatest for those in energy poverty, suggesting that even though most of their energy-oriented financial support is used for other pressing needs, this still offers some relief from energy poverty. We conclude that energy-efficiency improvements in homes would yield the most substantial and enduring financial benefits for these households, highlighting the need for targeted

retrofitting policies. Additionally, older homeowners in energy poverty may need help to move into smaller, energy-efficient homes that are less expensive to heat.

References:

S.N. Champagne, J.I. Macdiarmid, E. Phimister, A.M. Guntupalli, Hungry and warm; cold and fed? The intersection of food and fuel poverty, *Eur. J. Pub. Health* 33 (2) (2023).

B.K. Sovacool, P. Upham, M. Martiskainen, K.E.H. Jenkins, G.A. Torres

Contreras, N. Simcock, Policy prescriptions to address energy and transport poverty in the United Kingdom, *Nat. Energy* 8 (3) (2023) 273–283.

Department of Energy Security, Net Zero, Annual Fuel Poverty Statistics in England, 2024 (2023 Data), 2024.

M. Sunikka-Blank, R. Galvin, Single parents in cold homes in Europe: how intersecting personal and national characteristics drive up the numbers of these vulnerable households, *Energy Policy* 150 (2021).

B. Boardman, *Fuel Poverty: From Cold Homes to Affordable Warmth*, Pinter Pub Limited, London, 1991.

Z. Guevara, D. Mendoza-Tinoco, D. Silva, The theoretical peculiarities of energy poverty research: a systematic literature review, *Energy Res. Soc. Sci.* 105 (2023).

R. Galvin, Reducing poverty in the UK to mitigate energy poverty by the 10% and LIHC indicators: what tax changes are needed, and what are the consequences for CO2 emissions? *Ecol. Econ.* 217 (2024).

T.M. Croon, J.S.C.M. Hoekstra, M.G. Elsinga, F. Dalla Longa, P. Mulder, Beyond headcount statistics: exploring the utility of energy poverty gap indices in policy design, *Energy Policy* 177 (2023).

L. Middlemiss, Who is vulnerable to energy poverty in the Global North, and what is their experience? *WIREs Energy Environ.* 11 (6) (2022).

S. Tirado Herrero, Energy poverty indicators: a critical review of methods, *Indoor Built Environ.* 26 (7) (2017) 1018–1031.

J. Schleich, Energy efficient technology adoption in low-income households in the European Union – what is the evidence? *Energy Policy* 125 (2019) 196–206.

H. Meier, T. Jamasb, L. Orea, Necessity or luxury good? Household energy spending and income in Britain 1991–2007, *Energy J.* 34 (4) (2013) 109–128.

B. Boardman, *Fixing Fuel Poverty: Challenges and Solutions*, Routledge, London, 2010.

R. Galvin, Energy poverty research: a perspective from the poverty side, in: R. Galvin (Ed.), *Inequality and Energy*, Academic Press, 2020, pp. 221–248.

J.D. Healy, *Housing, Fuel Poverty and Health*, Routledge, London, 2004.

C. Liddell, C. Morris, Fuel poverty and human health: a review of recent evidence, *Energy Policy* 38 (6) (2010) 2987–2997.

L. Middlemiss, A critical analysis of the new politics of fuel poverty in England, *Crit. Soc. Policy* 37 (3) (2017) 425–443.

A. Feicht, Schriftliche Frage an die Bundesregierung. Antwort von Andreas Feicht, Staatssekretär BMWi, an Bundesabgeordnete Dr Rainer Kraft, 2019.

R. Castaño-Rosa, J. Solís-Guzmán, C. Rubio-Bellido, M. Marrero, Towards a multiple-indicator approach to energy poverty in the European Union: a review, *Energy Build.* 193 (2019) 36–48.

- J. Gao, B. Peng, R. Smyth, On income and price elasticities for energy demand: a panel data study, *Energy Econ.* 96 (2021).
- P. Heindl, Measuring fuel poverty: general considerations and application to German household data, *FinanzArchiv* 71 (2) (2015).
- X. Labandeira, J.M. Labeaga, X. López-Otero, A meta-analysis on the price elasticity of energy demand, *Energy Policy* 102 (2017) 549–568.
- A.F. Erias, E.M. Iglesias, Price and income elasticity of natural gas demand in Europe and the effects of lockdowns due to Covid-19, *Energ. Strat. Rev.* 44 (2022).
- D. Borozan, Unveiling the heterogeneous effect of energy taxes and income on residential energy consumption, *Energy Policy* 129 (2019) 13–22.
- J.M. Fry, L. Farrell, J.B. Temple, Energy poverty and food insecurity: is there an energy or food trade-off among low-income Australians? *Energy Econ.* 123 (2023).
- A. Scott, The economics of house heating, *Energy Econ.* 2 (3) (1980) 130–141.
- R. Gillingham, R.P. Hagemann, Household demand for fuel oil, *Appl. Econ.* 16 (1984) 475–482.
- R. Nesbakken, Price sensitivity of residential energy consumption in Norway, *Energy Econ.* 21 (1999) 493–515.
- P. Baker, R. Blundell, The microeconomic approach to modelling energy demand: some results for UK households, *Oxf. Rev. Econ. Policy* 7 (2) (1991).
- J. Harold, J. Cullinan, S. Lyons, The income elasticity of household energy demand: a quantile regression analysis, *Appl. Econ.* 49 (54) (2017) 5570–5578.
- I. Schulte, P. Heindl, Price and income elasticities of residential energy demand in Germany, *Energy Policy* 102 (2017) 512–528.
- D. Romero-Jordán, P. del Río, C. Peñasco, An analysis of the welfare and distributive implications of factors influencing household electricity consumption, *Energy Policy* 88 (2016) 361–370.
- W.Q. Manalo-Macua, Distributional implications of power sector reforms in the Philippines, *Philipp. Rev. Econ.* 44 (1) (2007) 65–97.
- A. Alberini, W. Gans, D. Velez-Lopez, Residential consumption of gas and electricity in the U.S.: the role of prices and income, *Energy Econ.* 33 (5) (2011) 870–881.
- P. Bolton, I. Stewart, Research briefing: domestic energy prices, in: House of Commons Library, 2024.
- Ofgem, Self-disconnection and Self-rationing: Decision, 2020.
- M. Sunikka-Blank, R. Galvin, Introducing the prebound effect: the gap between performance and actual energy consumption, *Build. Res. Inf.* 40 (3) (2012) 260–273.
- T. Berger, A. Hörtl, Thermal insulation of rental residential housing: do energy poor households benefit? A case study in Krems, Austria, *Energy Policy* 127 (2019) 341–34.
- R. Galvin, How prebound effects compromise the market premium for energy efficiency in German house sales, *Build. Res. Inf.* 51 (5) (2023) 501–517.
- D. Teli, T. Dimitriou, P.A.B. James, A.S. Bahaj, L. Ellison, A. Waggott, Fuel poverty-induced ‘prebound effect’ in achieving the anticipated carbon savings from social housing retrofit, *Build. Serv. Eng. Res. Technol.* 37 (2) (2015) 176–193.

R. Douthitt, An economic analysis of the demand for residential space heating fuel in Canada, *Energy* 14 (4) (1989) 187–197.

J. Harold, S. Lyons, J. Cullinan, The determinants of residential gas demand in Ireland, *Energy Econ.* 51 (2015) 475–483.

E. Sardianou, Estimating space heating determinants: an analysis of Greek households, *Energy Build.* 40 (6) (2008) 1084–1093.

F.G. Braun, Determinants of households' space heating type: a discrete choice analysis for German households, *Energy Policy* 38 (10) (2010) 5493–5503.

P. Van den Brom, A.R. Hansen, K. Gram-Hanssen, A. Meijer, H. Visscher, Variances in residential heating consumption – importance of building characteristics and occupants analysed by movers and stayers, *Appl. Energy* 250 (2019) 713–728.

A.R. Hansen, The social structure of heat consumption in Denmark: new interpretations from quantitative analysis, *Energy Res. Soc. Sci.* 11 (2016) 109–118.

L. Karpinska, S. Śmiech, Multiple faces of poverty. Exploring housing-costs- induced energy poverty in Central and Eastern Europe, *Energy Res. Soc. Sci.* (2023) 105.

A. Rhiger Hansen, K. Gram-Hanssen, Over- and underconsumption of residential heating: analyzing occupant impacts on performance gaps between calculated and actual heating demand, *J. Phys. Conf. Ser.* 2654 (2023).

S. Sorrell, J. Dimitropoulos, M. Sommerville, Empirical estimates of the direct rebound effect: a review, *Energy Policy* 37 (4) (2009) 1356–1371.

N. Bergman, T.J. Foxon, Reframing policy for the energy efficiency challenge: insights from housing retrofits in the United Kingdom, *Energy Res. Soc. Sci.* 63 (2020).

J. Rosenow, R. Platt, B. Flanagan, Fuel poverty and energy efficiency obligations – a critical assessment of the supplier obligation in the UK, *Energy Policy* 62 (2013) 1194–1203.

D. Charlier, S. Kahouli, From residential energy demand to fuel poverty: income- induced non-linearities in the reactions of households to energy price fluctuations, *Energy J.* 40 (2) (2019) 101–138.

H. Thomson, C. Snell, Quantifying the prevalence of fuel poverty across the European Union, *Energy Policy* 52 (2013) 563–572.

M. Economidou, V. Todeschi, P. Bertoldi, D. D'Agostino, P. Zangheri, L. Castellazzi, Review of 50 years of EU energy efficiency policies for buildings, *Energy Build.* 225 (2020).

S. Bouzarovski, H. Thomson, M. Cornelis, Confronting energy poverty in Europe: a research and policy agenda, *Energies* 14 (4) (2021).

HM Government, *Sustainable Warmth: Protecting Vulnerable Households in England*, 2021.

J. Palmer, B. Boardman, N. Terry, T. Fawcett, U. Narayan, in: U.o.O. Cambridge Architectural Research and Environmental Change Institute (Ed.), *Finding the Fuel Poor and Framing Better Policy*, 2023.

E. Zapata-Webborn, C. Hanmer, T. Oreszczyn, G. Huebner, E. McKenna, J. Few,

S. Elam, M. Pullinger, C. Cheshire, D. Friel, H. Masters, A. Whittaker, Winter demand falls as fuel bills rise: understanding the energy impacts of the cost-of- living crisis on British households, *Energy Build.* 305 (2024).

ONS, *Impact of Increased Cost of Living on Adults Across Great Britain [Dataset]*, 2023.

D. Papantonis, D. Tzani, M. Burbidge, V. Stavrakas, S. Bouzarovski, A. Flamos, How to improve energy efficiency policies to address energy poverty? Literature and stakeholder insights for private rented housing in Europe, *Energy Res. Soc. Sci.* 93 (2022).

B. Faith, K. Hernandez, J. Beecher, Policy Briefing: Digital Poverty in the UK, 2022.

R. Bull, C. Miles, E. Newbury, A. Nichols, T. Weekes, G. Wyld, Hunger in the UK, 2023.

C. Dewilde, Explaining the declined affordability of housing for low-income private renters across Western Europe, *Urban Stud.* 55 (12) (2018) 2618–2639.

C. Skidmore, Mission Zero: Independent Review of Net Zero, 2023.

Ministry of Housing, C.L.G., English Housing Survey 2018–2019, 2020.

Department of Business, E., and Industrial Strategy (BEIS), Fuel Poverty Dataset Documentation, 2021.

J. Hills, Getting the Measure of Fuel Poverty: Final Report of the Fuel Poverty Review, Centre for Analysis of Social Exclusion, London, UK, 2012.

S. Meyer, H. Laurence, D. Bart, L. Middlemiss, K. Maréchal, Capturing the multifaceted nature of energy poverty: lessons from Belgium, *Energy Res. Soc. Sci.* 40 (2018) 273–283.

I. Antepara, L. Papada, J.P. Gouveia, N. Katsoulakos, D. Kaliampakos, Improving energy poverty measurement in Southern European Regions through equalization of modeled energy costs, *Sustainability* 12 (14) (2020).

F. Betto, P. Garengo, A. Lorenzoni, A new measure of Italian hidden energy poverty, *Energy Policy* 138 (2020).

R. Barrella, J.C. Romero, J.I. Linares, E. Arenas, M. Asín, E. Centeno, The dark side of energy poverty: who is underconsuming in Spain and why? *Energy Res. Soc. Sci.* 86 (2022).

L. Bagnoli, S. Bertoméu-Sánchez, How effective has the electricity social rate been in reducing energy poverty in Spain? *Energy Econ.* 106 (2022).

G. García Alvarez, R.S.J. Tol, The impact of the Bono Social de Electricidad on energy poverty in Spain, *Energy Econ.* (2021) 103.

R. Barrella, J.I. Linares, J.C. Romero, E. Arenas, E. Centeno, Does cash money solve energy poverty? Assessing the impact of household heating allowances in Spain, *Energy Res. Soc. Sci.* 80 (2021).

A. Baniassadi, J. Heusinger, P.I. Gonzalez, S. Weber, H.W. Samuelson, Co- benefits of energy efficiency in residential buildings, *Energy* 238 (2022).

A. Bisello, Assessing multiple benefits of housing regeneration and smart city development: the European Project SINFONIA, *Sustainability* 12 (19) (2020).

M. Reuter, M.K. Patel, W. Eichhammer, B. Lapillonne, K. Pollier, A comprehensive indicator set for measuring multiple benefits of energy efficiency,

F. Farnood, C. Jones, Has the revival in the Scottish private rented sector since the millennium achieved maturity? *Hous. Stud.* 38 (6) (2021) 963–984.

T.M. Croon, J.S.C.M. Hoekstra, U. Dubois, Energy poverty alleviation by social housing providers: a qualitative investigation of targeted interventions in France, England, and the Netherlands, *Energy Policy* 192 (2024).

Keywords: Income Elasticity, Energy Expenditure, Energy Poverty, Low Income, Ecosocial Policy, English Housing Survey

Croon, T., Hoekstra, J., & Dubois, U. (2023). Addressing Energy Poverty in Social Housing Estates [White Paper]. European Federation for Living.

Executive Summary: This report addresses the pressing concern of energy poverty in social housing and offers strategic solutions to advance an inclusive energy transition. Energy poverty has become a prominent issue, disproportionately affecting vulnerable households with limited financial means and energy inefficient dwellings. The surge in energy prices and the ongoing transition towards low-carbon energy sources contribute to this challenge.

The report emphasises the significance of short-term measures to mitigate the impact of energy price surges on tenants. Empowering residents with energy coaches, distributing energy-saving boxes, deploying ‘fix teams’, establishing warm hubs, and offering financial leniency are practical steps to support vulnerable households during challenging periods.

Furthermore, long-term strategies are crucial to enhancing tenant resilience and preventing energy poverty from the outset. Social housing providers can prioritise renovation for homes occupied by households at risk of energy poverty and reform housing (re)allocation policies to allocate energy-efficient dwellings to vulnerable tenants. Targeted information campaigns can also influence energy consumption behavior and foster energy-saving practices among residents.

To support the energy efficiency of social housing stock, social housing providers can leverage funding opportunities offered by the European Investment Bank (EIB) and the upcoming Social Climate Fund (SCF). Initiatives like the EIB's Affordable Housing Initiative and ELENA program provide financial support for social housing renovation projects. The SCF, commencing in 2026, will inject approximately 86 billion euros to fund renovation projects for vulnerable Europeans and provide direct income support to households in need, with a focus on reducing energy poverty.

The core message of this whitepaper is that an inclusive energy transition in social housing requires a multifaceted approach that combines short-term measures and long-term strategies. Social housing providers play a vital role in addressing energy poverty, and by optimizing operations, reforming allocation policies, and launching targeted information campaigns, they can make a significant impact in promoting sustainable living conditions for vulnerable tenants. Leveraging funding opportunities from the EIB and the SCF, social housing providers can take proactive steps towards alleviating energy poverty and ensuring a brighter future for their residents.

Davis, A. (2024). Circular Housing: Insights from Solar Decathlon Europe 2022. Presented at the European Network for Housing Research (ENHR) Conference 2024, Delft, the Netherlands.

Abstract: This study investigates the circular economy transition in housing, providing lessons learnt and best practices demonstrated at the Solar Decathlon Europe competition 2022 in Wuppertal, Germany. The competition build challenge provided a unique opportunity to examine the practical application of circular principles in affordable, urban housing solutions, leveraging both design for disassembly and industrialised construction approaches. The interdisciplinary teams provided valuable knowledge in circular construction, having gained hands-on experience in collaboration with industry professionals. The insights provided by this study are based on interviews with fifteen competing teams' mid-way through the assembly phase. This was complemented by observation of team Azalea's disassembly process in Spain, prior to attending the competition in Germany. The results contribute towards the development of a circular housing framework and provides transferrable knowledge for industry practitioners and housing providers. This doctoral research is part of the Horizon 2020 project RE-DWELL.

Keywords: Circular Housing, Design for Disassembly, Industrialised Construction, Qualitative research, Framework

Davis, A. (2022). *Design for Disassembly in housing: the need to adapt LCA to Shearing Layers*. In *Proceedings of 3rd Valencia International Biennial of Research in Architecture 2022. Changing priorities* (pp. 636-647). Valencia: Editorial Universitat Politècnica de València.

Abstract: The current lack of sustainable and affordable housing is a global issue which has reached a crisis point. Traditional construction approaches used to solve sustainability issues in housing are often in tension with affordability, where the achieving one of these two aims is often to the detriment to the other. The application of Design for Disassembly (DfD) in combination with Industrialised Construction (IC) can simultaneously provide environmentally and economically sustainable solutions to these ongoing housing challenges. However, the application of DfD and the planning of varying lifespans for different building components raises issues with the conventional Whole Building Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology, which is used to quantify environmental impacts of the construction.

This paper covers three theoretical objectives: (1) to provide an overview of DfD and IC and how these can be combined to provide resource efficient, affordable housing (2) examine how the Shearing Layers concept can extend the building lifespan and better ensure a sustainable End-of-Life, and (3) a preliminary outline proposal as to how the Whole Building LCA methodology, based on existing standards, can be adapted to align with the Shearing Layers. These objectives will be achieved through a literature review, covering the theoretical principles of DfD and the key ISO standards related to LCA. Based on the literature and applied theory, a preliminary aggregated LCA methodology is proposed that will be further developed and tested using case studies in future investigations by the author.

The result of the discussion reveals potential conflict between construction in practice and applying Shearing Layers and the adapted Whole Building LCA and the need for further investigation to establish the number of years assumed for each layer of the LCA. Whilst inventory data for materials and processes follow conventional practices, it is the proposed organisation of information into layers illustrates to designers the need to design housing for disassembly to remove and replace building components.

References:

Acharya, Devni, Richard Boyd, and Olivia Finch. 2020. "From Principles to Practices: Realising the Value of Circular Economy in Real Estate." Ellen MacArthur Foundation & Arup.

BAMB. 2020. "Reversible Building Design." 2020. <https://www.bamb2020.eu/topics/reversible-building-design/>.

BLP. 2000. Building Services Component Life Manual: Building Life Plans 1st Edition. Wiley-Blackwell.

BPG. 1999. The BPG Building Fabric Component Life Manual. CRC Press.

Braakman, Linda, Silu Bhochhibhoya, and Robin de Graaf. 2021. "Exploring the Relationship between the Level of Circularity and the Life Cycle Costs of a One-Family House." *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 164 (January). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2020.105149>.

Brand, Stewart. 1994. *How Buildings Learn: What Happens after They're Built*. New York: Viking.

BRE. 2018. "BREEAM – Why Whole Building Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)? | BREEAM." 2018. <https://www.breeam.com/news/breeam-why-building-lca/>.

BREEAM. 2018. "Building LCA Benchmarks – BREEAM UK New Construction 2018." 2018. <https://www.breeam.com/news/building-lca-benchmarks-breeam-uk-new-construction-2018/>.

———. 2022. “Circularity and BREEAM.” 2022.

CEN. 2011. “CEN/TC 350 - Sustainability of Construction Works.” 2011.

Charef, Rabia, and Weisheng Lu. 2021. “Factor Dynamics to Facilitate Circular Economy Adoption in Construction.” *Journal of Cleaner Production* 319 (October).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.128639>.

CIBSE. 2000. *CIBSE Guide to Ownership, Operation and Maintenance of Building Services (CIBSE Guide)*. The Chartered Institute of Building Service Engineers.

Crowther, Philip. 2005. “RAIA/BDP Environment Design Guide: Design for Disassembly - Themes and Principles.”

Cruz Rios, Fernanda, and David Grau. 2019. “Circular Economy in the Built Environment: Designing, Deconstructing, and Leasing Reusable Products.” In *Encyclopedia of Renewable and Sustainable Materials*, 338–43. Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-803581-8.11494-8>.

Duffy, Francis. 1992. *The Changing Workplace*. London: Phaidon Press.

European Commission. 2010. “ILCD Handbook - General Guide for Life Cycle Assessment: Detailed Guidance.” 1st ed. Luxemburg: Publications Office of the European Union.

———. 2020a. “Construction and Demolition Waste (CDW).” 2020.

https://ec.europa.eu/environment/topics/waste-and-recycling/construction-and-demolition-waste_en.

———. 2020b. “First Circular Economy Action Plan.”

https://ec.europa.eu/environment/topics/circular-economy/first-circular-economy-action-plan_es.

Gervasio, H, and S Dimova. 2018. “Model for Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of Buildings.”

<https://doi.org/10.2760/10016>.

Grant, Aneurin, Robert Ries, and Charles Kibert. 2014. “Life Cycle Assessment and Service Life Prediction: A Case Study of Building Envelope Materials.” *Journal of Industrial Ecology* 18 (2): 187–200.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.12089>.

Guinée, Jeroen B., Reinout Heijungs, Gjalt Huppes, Alessandra Zamagni, Paolo Masoni, Roberto Buonamici, Tomas Ekvall, and Tomas Rydberg. 2011. “Life Cycle Assessment: Past, Present, and Future.” *Environmental Science and Technology* 45 (1): 90–96. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es101316v>.

Guy, Brad, and Nicholas Ciarimboli. 2008. “Design for Disassembly in the Built Environment: A Guide to Closed-Loop 646_block 8: sustainability and climate crisis Design and Building.”

<https://www.lifecyclebuilding.org/docs/DfDseattle.pdf>.

Hossain, Md Uzzal, and S. Thomas Ng. 2018. “Critical Consideration of Buildings’ Environmental Impact Assessment towards Adoption of Circular Economy: An Analytical Review.” *Journal of Cleaner Production* 205 (December): 763–80. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.09.120>.

Housing Europe. 2021. “The State of Housing in Europe 2021.” <https://www.stateofhousing.eu/#p=6>.

ISO. 2006. “ISO 14040:2006(En).” 2006. <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso:14040:ed-2:v1:en>.

———. 2017. “ISO 15686-5:2017(En) Buildings and Constructed Assets — Service Life Planning — Part 5: Life-Cycle Costing.” 2017.

Jensen, K.G, and Sommer, J. 2019. *Building a Circular Future*. 3rd ed. Vol. 3. Denmark: KLS PurePrint.

Joensuu, Tuomo, Roosa Leino, Jukka Heinonen, and Arto Saari. 2022. “Developing Buildings’ Life Cycle Assessment in Circular Economy-Comparing Methods for Assessing Carbon Footprint of Reusable Components.” *Sustainable Cities and Society* 77 (February). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2021.103499>.

Timberlake, Kieran. 2008. "How Can We Create a House That Holistically Advances Architecture through Agendas of On-Site Assembly, Design for Disassembly, and Reuse of Materials?" 2008. <https://kierantimberlake.com/page/cellophane-house>.

LETI. 2020. "LETI Embodied Carbon Primer." www.LETI.london.

McKinsey. 2020. "The next Normal in Construction: How Disruption is Reshaping the World's Largest Ecosystem." McKinsey & Company.

Morgan, Chris, John Gilbert Architects, and Fionn Stevenson. 2005. "Design for Deconstruction: SEDA Design Guides for Scotland." <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/303231874>.

Rios, Fernanda Cruz, Wai K. Chong, and David Grau. 2015. "Design for Disassembly and Deconstruction - Challenges and Opportunities." In *Procedia Engineering*, 118:1296–1304. Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2015.08.485>.

Sartori, Igor, Håvard Bergsdal, Daniel B. Muller, and Helge Brattembø. 2008. "Towards Modelling of Construction, Renovation and Demolition Activities: Norway's Dwelling Stock, 1900–2100." *Building Research and Information* 36 (5): 412–25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09613210802184312>.

Sartori, Thais, Robin Drogemuller, Sara Omrani, and Fiona Lamari. 2021. "A Schematic Framework for Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Green Building Rating System (GBRS)." *Journal of Building Engineering* 38 (June): 102180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2021.102180>.

Smith, Ryan E. 2010. *Prefab Architecture: A Guide to Modular Design and Construction*. Hoboken, N.J: John Wiley & Sons.

TED Talks. 2013. "Architecture for the People by the People." WikiHouse. 2013. https://www.ted.com/talks/alastair_parvin_architecture_for_the_people_by_the_people?language=en.

The Ellen Macarthur Foundation. 2015. "Founding Partners of the TOWARDS THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY Economic and Business Rationale for an Accelerated Transition."

Tingley, Danielle Densley. 2012. "Design for Deconstruction: An Appraisal." The University of Sheffield. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/279440677>.

UN. 2017. "Towards a Zero-Emission, Efficient, and Resilient Buildings and Construction Sector." *Global Status Report 2017* by the UN Environment and the International Energy Agency.

USGBC. 2022. "LEED v4.1." 2022. <https://www.usgbc.org/leed/v41>.

Wolf, Catherine de, Endrit Hoxha, and Corentin Fivet. 2020. "Comparison of Environmental Assessment Methods When Reusing Building Components: A Case Study." *Sustainable Cities and Society* 61 (October). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2020.102322>.

Keywords: Sustainable housing, Design for Disassembly (DfD), Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Circular Economy (CE), shearing layers

Dissart, J. C., & Ricaurte, L. (2023). *Assessing social value in housing design: contributions of the capability approach*. *Buildings and Cities*, 4(1), 867–882.

Abstract: A conceptualisation of social value in the built environment is provided from the perspective of the capability approach (CA). The CA is a theoretical framework that has been used to assess inequality and poverty, particularly in less-developed countries; its multidimensionality and flexibility make it a useful approach in advanced economies as well. The CA can be a theoretical underpinning to

assess the social value created in the built environment, particularly in its spatial dimension. Its use is explored to assess the design features of housing schemes and the wider environment as a fundamental conversion factor in creating capabilities and achieving valued functionings. In addition to theoretical considerations, a capability-based assessment of social value is presented for housing design.

References:

- Alexander, L., & Moore M. (2021). Deontological ethics. In E. N. Zalta (Ed.), *The Stanford encyclopedia of philosophy*. Metaphysics Research Lab, Stanford University.
- Alexiou, K., Hale, V., & Zamenopoulos, T. (2022). Design capital: Unearthing the design capabilities of community groups. *International Journal of Design*, 16(2), 33–46. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.57698/v16i2.03>
- Blečić, I., Bibo Cecchini, A., & Talu, V. (2013). The capability approach in urban quality of life and urban policies: Towards a conceptual framework. In S. Serreli (Ed.), *City project and public space* (pp. 269–288). Springer. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-6037-0_17
- Caprotti, F., Cowley, R., Datta, A., Broto, V. C., Gao, E., Georgeson, L., Herrick, C., Odendaal, N., & Joss, S. (2017). The new urban agenda: Key opportunities and challenges for policy and practice. *Urban Research & Practice*, 10(3), 367–378. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17535069.2016.1275618>
- Clapham, D., & Foye, C. (2019). How should we evaluate housing outcomes? UK Collaborative Centre for Housing Evidence.
- Clark, D. A., Biggeri, M., & Frediani, A. A. (2019). *The capability approach, empowerment and participation: Concepts, methods and applications*. Palgrave Macmillan. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1057/978-1-137-35230-9>
- Clark, G., & HOK. (2019). *Sustainable outcomes guide*. The Royal Institute of British Architects (RIBA). <https://www.architecture.com/knowledge-and-resources/resources-landing-page/sustainable-outcomes-guide>
- Coates, D., Anand, P., & Norris, M. (2015). A capabilities approach to housing and quality of life: The evidence from Germany. In *Open discussion papers in economics* (Issue 78). The Open University, Economics Department. <https://www.econstor.eu/handle/10419/147529>
- Courlet, C. (2007). Du développement économique situé. In H. Gumuchian & B. Pecqueur (Eds.), *La ressource territoriale* (pp. 32–44). *Economica, Anthropolos*.
- Crocker, D. A. (2008). *Ethics of global development: Agency, capability, and deliberative democracy*. Cambridge University Press. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511492594>
- Deneulin, S. (2008). Beyond individual freedom and agency: Structures of living together in Sen's capability approach to development. In S. Alkire, F. Comim & M. Qizilbash (Eds.), *The capability approach: Concepts, measures and application* (pp. 105–124). Cambridge University Press. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511492587>
- Deneulin, S., & Stewart, F. (2002). Amartya Sen's contribution to development thinking. *Studies in Comparative International Development*, 37(2), 61–70. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02686262>
- Durosaiye, I. O., Hadjri, K., & Liyanage, C. L. (2019). A critique of post-occupancy evaluation in the UK. *Journal of Housing and the Built Environment*, 34(1), 345–352. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10901-019-09646-2>
- Ferrero Y de Loma-Osorio, G., & Zepeda, C. S. (2014). Rethinking development management methodology: Towards a 'process freedoms approach'. *Journal of Human Development and Capabilities*, 15(1), 28–46. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/19452829.2013.877425>

Foye, C. (2021). Ethically-speaking, what is the most reasonable way of evaluating housing outcomes? *Housing, Theory and Society*, 38(1), 115–131. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14036096.2019.1697356>

Frediani, A. (2019). Participatory research methods and the capability approach: Researching the housing dimensions of squatter upgrading initiatives in Salvador da Bahia, Brazil. In D. A. Clark, M., Biggeri & A. A. Frediani (Eds.), *The capability approach, empowerment and participation: Concepts, methods and applications* (pp. 261–288). Palgrave Macmillan UK. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1057/978-1-137-35230-9_10

Frediani, A. (2021). *Cities for human development: A capability approach to city-making*. Practical Action. <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=tdWazgEACAAJ>

Frediani, A., & Hansen, J. (2015). The capability approach in development planning and urban design. Development Planning Unit. https://www.ucl.ac.uk/bartlett/development/sites/bartlett/files/wp_173-178_special_issue_on_capability_approach_final.pdf

Fujiwara, D., & Campbell, R. (2011). Valuation techniques for social cost–benefit analysis: Stated preference, revealed preference and subjective well-being approaches: A discussion of the current issues. HM Treasury. https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/209107/greenbook_valuationtechniques.pdf

Green, G. P., & Haines, A. (2012). *Asset building and community development*, 3rd ed. Sage.

Groat, L. N., & Wang, D. (2013). *Architectural research methods*. Wiley.

HACT. (2023). *UK Social Value Bank: Demonstrating social value*. Housing Associations' Charitable Trust (HACT). <https://hact.org.uk/tools-and-services/uk-social-value-bank/>

Hadjri, K., & Crozier, C. (2009). Post-occupancy evaluation: Purpose, benefits and barriers. *Facilities*, 27(1–2), 21–33. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/02632770910923063>

Haffner, M. E. A., & Elsinga, M. G. (2019). Housing deprivation unravelled: Application of the capability approach. *European Journal of Homelessness*, 13(1), 13. <https://repository.tudelft.nl/islandora/object/uuid%3Af612e3ac-ce6f-4b5e-9b14-0fad4338ed30>

Hay, R., Bradbury, S., Dixon, D., Martindale, K., Samuel, F., & Tait, A. (2016). *Pathways to POE*. The Royal Institute of British Architects (RIBA).

Hay, R., Samuel, F., Watson, K. J., & Bradbury, S. (2017). Post-occupancy evaluation in architecture: Experiences and perspectives from UK practice. *Building Research & Information*, 46(6), 698–710. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09613218.2017.1314692>

Kimhur, B. (2020). How to apply the capability approach to housing policy? Concepts, theories and challenges. *Housing, Theory and Society*, 37(3), 257–277. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14036096.2019.1706630>

Loubet, F., Dissart, J.-C., & Lallau, B. (2011). Contribution de l'approche par les capacités à l'évaluation du développement territorial. *Revue d'Économie Régionale & Urbaine*, 2011/4 (October), 681–703. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3917/reru.114.0681>

MacDonald, P. (2020). *RIBA post occupancy evaluation: An essential tool to improve the built environment*. The Royal Institute of British Architects (RIBA).

Morgan, M., & Salih, H. (2023). Resident review: Assessing the impact of new homes on people's health and wellbeing. *Perspectives in Public Health*, 143(2), 71–72. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/17579139231157530>

Nussbaum, M. C. (2006). *Frontiers of justice: Disability, nationality, species membership* (The Tanner Lectures on Human Values). Belknap/Harvard University Press. DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv1c7zftw>

Paquot, T. (2011). Qu'est-ce qu'un 'territoire'? *Vie sociale*, 2011/2, 23–32. DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.3917/vsoc.112.0023>

Quality of Life Foundation & URBED. (2021). *The quality of life framework*. URBED & Quality of Life Foundation. <https://www.qolf.org/framework/>

Raiden, A., & King, A. (2021a) *Social value in practice*. Routledge. DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003024910>

Raiden, A., & King, A. (2021b). Social value, organisational learning, and the sustainable development goals in the built environment. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 172. DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.105663>

Raiden, A. & King, A. (2023). Added value and numerical measurement of social value: A critical enquiry. *Buildings & Cities*, 4(1), 767–782. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5334/bc.330>

Raiden, A., Loosemore, M., King, A., & Gorse, C. (2018). *Social value in construction*. Routledge. DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.1201/9781315100807>

Robeyns, I. (2005). The capability approach: A theoretical survey. *Journal of Human Development*, 6(1), 93–117. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/146498805200034266>

Robeyns, I. (2006). The capability approach in practice. *Journal of Political Philosophy*, 14(3), 351–376.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9760.2006.00263.x>

Robeyns, I., & Byskov, M. F. (2021). The capability approach. In E. N. Zalta (Ed.), *The Stanford encyclopedia of philosophy*. <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/win2021/entries/capability-approach/>. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429020612-9>

Samuel, F. (2020). *RIBA social value toolkit for architecture*. The Royal Institute of British Architects (RIBA). <https://www.architecture.com/-/media/GatherContent/Social-Value-Toolkit-for-Architecture/Additional-Documents/RIBAUoR-Social-Value-Toolkit-2020pdf.pdf>

Samuel, F. (2022). Measuring wellbeing and social value. In *Housing for hope and wellbeing* (pp. 73–82). Routledge. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003031888-7>

Sen, A. (1987). *Commodities and capabilities*, Oxford University Press.

Sen, A. (1992). *Inequality reexamined*. Russell Sage Foundation.

Sen, A. (1999). *Development as freedom*. Oxford University Press.

Sen, A. (2005). Human rights and capabilities. *Journal of Human Development*, 6(2), 151–166. DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.1080/14649880500120491>

Sen, A. (2009). *The idea of justice*. Penguin. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4159/9780674054578882>

Serin, B., Kenny, T., White, J., & Samuel, F. (2018). *Design value at the neighbourhood scale: What does it mean and how do we measure it?* UK Collaborative Centre for Housing Evidence. DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16049.43360>

Social Value Portal. (2023, February 10). *The national toms*. Social Value Portal.

<https://socialvalueportal.com/solutions/national-toms/>

Social Value UK. (2023, April 5). *What is social value and why does it matter?* Social Value UK.

<https://socialvalueuk.org/what-is-social-value/>

UK Government. (2012). Public Services (Social Value) Act 2012. UK Government.
<https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2012/3>

UKGBC. (2020). Delivering social value: Measurement. UK Green Building Council (UKGBC).
<https://www.ukgbc.org/ukgbc-work/delivering-social-value-measurement/>

UKGBC. (2021). Framework for defining social value. UK Green Building Council (UKGBC).
<https://www.ukgbc.org/ukgbc-work/framework-for-defining-social-value/>

UN. (2017). New urban agenda. United Nations (UN). <https://habitat3.org/wp-content/uploads/NUA-English.pdf>

UN General Assembly. (2015). Transforming our world: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, 21 October 2015 (A/RES/70/1). United Nations. <https://documents-dds-ny.un.org/doc/UNDOC/GEN/N15/291/89/PDF/N1529189.pdf?OpenElement>

Watson, K. J., Evans, J., Karvonen, A., & Whitley, T. (2016). Capturing the social value of buildings: The promise of Social Return on Investment (SROI). *Building and Environment*, 103, 289–301. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2016.04.007>

Watson, K. J., & Whitley, T. (2017). Applying social return on investment (SROI) to the built environment. *Building Research & Information*, 45(8), 875–891. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09613218.2016.1223486>

Keywords: Added Value, Built Environment, Capability Approach, Housing, Housing Design, Placemaking, Quality of Life, Residents, Social Impact, Social Value

Fernández, A. (2024). *Investigating the impact of housing price increases on consumption: Heterogeneity by age, tenure and housing quality*. *Journal of European Real Estate Research* (2024).

Abstract: Purpose – The purpose of this paper is to understand the distributional impact of house price increases on consumption in the context of the energy transition.

Design/methodology/approach – This study draws from two micro cross-sectional datasets, the English Housing Survey (EHS) and the Living Costs and Food Survey (LCFS) to study the Marginal Propensity to Consume (MPC) out of changes in house prices. By employing pseudo-panel regressions, the paper examines the impact of house price changes on consumption among diverse household types.

Findings – This paper finds varying consumption responses to house price changes across age and tenure groups. Older homeowners tend to increase consumption when house prices rise. In contrast, middle-aged individuals, often renters or mortgage holders, reduce consumption in response to price increases. The youngest age group also experiences increased consumption but to a lesser degree than the oldest group. Energy-efficient homes are related to lower consumption across all tenure levels. However, when interacted with house prices and age, the estimates are positive, pointing to an unequal accrual of property premiums depending on housing market positions.

Research limitations/implications – The main limitations stem from data constraints. First, using a pseudo-panel approach hinders control for unobservable selection bias. Additionally, while robust under cross-validation and specifications tests, the energy efficiency variable imputation results in a low number of energy-efficient homes. Due to heterogeneous responses to rising house prices, this paper contends that an energy transition model that subsidises homeowners' renovation is likely to produce a negative impact on consumption among younger and middle-aged households.

Originality/value – This paper contributes to the MPC literature by incorporating energy efficiency as a key variable. It draws from recent data to obtain new estimates. By highlighting shifts in consumption patterns the paper contributes to a well-established body of literature with renewed policy relevance regarding housing retrofit.

References:

Attanasio, O.P., Blow, L., Hamilton, R. and Leicester, A. (2009), “Booms and Busts: consumption, house prices and expectations”, *Economica*, Vol. 76 No. 301, pp. 20-50, available at: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/40071768> (accessed 5 July 2024).

Attanasio, O., Leicester, A. and Wakefield, M. (2011), “Do house prices drive consumption growth? The coincident cycles of house prices and consumption in the UK”, *Journal of the European Economic Association*, Vol. 9 No. 3, pp. 399-435, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1542-4774.2011.01021.x>.

Ayala, A.D., Galarraga, I. and Spadaro, J.V. (2016), “The price of energy efficiency in the Spanish housing market”, *Energy Policy*, Vol. 94, pp. 16-24, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2016.03.032>.

BEIS (2019a), “UK becomes first major economy to pass net zero emissions law”, available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/uk-becomes-first-major-economy-to-pass-net-zero-emissions-law>

BEIS (2019b), “Government response to the committee’s twenty-first report of session 2017-19”, available at: <https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm201919/cmselect/cmbeis/124/12403.htm>

BEIS (2020), “2019 UK greenhouse gas emissions, provisional figures”, p. 20, available at: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5e7b6b28e90e0706f68327a3/2019_UK_greenhouse_gas_emissions_provisional_figures_statistical_release.pdf

Berger, D., Guerrieri, V., Lorenzoni, G. and Vavra, J. (2018), “House prices and consumer spending”, *Review of Economic Studies*, Vol. 85 No. 3, pp. 1502-1542, <https://doi.org/10.1093/restud/rdx060>.

Bernanke, B.S., Gertler, M. and Gilchrist, S. (1999), “Chapter 21 the financial accelerator in a quantitative business cycle framework”, in *Handbook of Macroeconomics*, Elsevier, Vol. 1, pp. 1341-1393, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1574-0048\(99\)10034-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1574-0048(99)10034-X).

Bielecki, M., Brzoza-Brzezina, M. and Kolasa, M. (2022), “Intergenerational redistributive effects of monetary policy”, *Journal of the European Economic Association*, Vol. 20 No. 2, pp. 549-580, <https://doi.org/10.1093/jeea/jvab032>.

Bridgeman, T. (2020), “Ofgem energy consumer archetypes: final report”, p. 72, Ofgem-Centre for Sustainable Energy, available at: https://www.ofgem.gov.uk/sites/default/files/docs/2020/05/ofgem_energy_consumer_archetypes_-_final_report_0.pdf

Brom, P.van den, Meijer, A. and Visscher, H. (2019), “Actual energy saving effects of thermal renovations in dwellings—longitudinal data analysis including building and occupant characteristics”, *Energy and Buildings*, Vol. 182, pp. 251-263, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2018.10.025>.

Brounen, D. and Kok, N. (2011), “On the economics of energy labels in the housing market”, *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, Vol. 62 No. 2, pp. 166-179, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeem.2010.11.006>.

Browning, M., Gørtz, M. and Leth-Petersen, S. (2013), “Housing wealth and consumption: a micro panel study”, *The Economic Journal*, Vol. 123 No. 568, pp. 401-428, <https://doi.org/10.1111/ecoj.12017>.

Buiter, W. (2008), “Housing wealth isn’t wealth”, *National Bureau of Economic Research*, p. w14204, <https://doi.org/10.3386/w14204>.

- Caloia, F.G. and Mastrogiacomo, M. (2022), “The housing wealth effect: the role of renovations and home improvements”, *Real Estate Economics*, Vol. 50 No. 6, pp. 1540-6229, <https://doi.org/10.1111/1540-6229.12383>.
- Campbell, J.Y. and Cocco, J.F. (2007), “How do house prices affect consumption? Evidence from micro data”, *Journal of Monetary Economics*, Vol. 54 No. 3, pp. 591-621, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmoneco.2005.10.016>.
- Carroll, C., Otsuka, M. and Slacalek, J. (2006), “How large is the housing wealth effect? A new approach”, *National Bureau of Economic Research*, p. w12746, <https://doi.org/10.3386/w12746>.
- Case, K., Shiller, R. and Quigley, J. (2001), “Comparing wealth effects: the stock market versus the housing market”, *National Bureau of Economic Research*, p. w8606, <https://doi.org/10.3386/w8606>.
- Causa, O., Woloszko, N. and Leite, D. (2019), “Housing, wealth accumulation and wealth distribution: evidence and stylized facts”, *OECD Economics Department Working Papers* No. 1588, <https://doi.org/10.1787/86954c10-en>.
- Cazcarro, I., Garcia-Gusano, D., Iribarren, D., Linares, P., Romero, J.C., Arocena, P., Arto, I., Banacloche, S., Lechon, Y., Miguel, L.J., Zafrilla, J., Lopez, L.-A., Langarita, R. and Cadarso, M.-A. (2022), “Energy-socio-economic-environmental modelling for the EU energy and post-COVID-19 transitions”, *Science of The Total Environment*, Vol. 805, 150329, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.150329>.
- Cerin, P., Hassel, L.G. and Semenova, N. (2014), “Energy performance and housing prices”, *Sustainable Development*, Vol. 22 No. 6, pp. 404-419, <https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.1566>.
- Chetty, R. (2009), “Sufficient statistics for welfare analysis: a bridge between structural and reduced-form methods”, *Annual Review of Economics*, Vol. 1 No. 1, pp. 451-488, <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.economics.050708.142910>.
- Cloyne, J., Ferreira, C., Surico, P., Gertler, M., Hohmann, S., Iacoviello, M., McMahon, M., Monacelli, T., Ragot, X., Reis, R., Romer, D., Thomas, R., Violante, G. and Young, G. (2016), “Monetary policy when households have debt: new evidence on the transmission mechanism”, *Bank of England Working Paper* No. 589, available at: <https://ssrn.com/abstract52765415>
- Deaton, A. (1985), “Panel data from time series of cross-sections”, *Journal of Econometrics*, Vol. 30 Nos 1-2, pp. 109-126, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-4076\(85\)90134-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-4076(85)90134-4).
- Disney, R., Gathergood, J. and Henley, A. (2010), “House price shocks, negative equity, and household consumption in the United Kingdom 4”, *Journal of the European Economic Association*, Vol. 8 No. 6, pp. 1179-1207, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1542-4774.2010.tb00552.x>.
- Ebrahimigharehbaghi, S., Qian, Q.K., Vries, G.de and Visscher, H.J. (2022), “Application of cumulative prospect theory in understanding energy retrofit decision: a study of homeowners in The Netherlands”, *Energy and Buildings*, Vol. 261, 111958, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2022.111958>.
- Engelhardt, G.V. (1996), “House prices and home owner saving behavior”, *Regional Science and Urban Economics*, Vol. 24 Nos 3-4, pp. 313-336, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0166-0462\(95\)02118-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0166-0462(95)02118-3).
- Fatica, S. and Prammer, D. (2018), “Housing and the tax system: how large are the distortions in the Euro area?”, *Fiscal Studies*, Vol. 39 No. 2, pp. 299-342, <https://doi.org/10.1111/1475-5890.12159>.
- Ferentinos, K., Gibberd, A. and Guin, B. (2021), “Climate policy and transition risk in the housing market”, *Bank of England Working Paper* No. 918, doi: 10.2139/ssrn.3838700, available at: <https://ssrn.com/abstract53838700>
- Fotiou, V., Capros and Capros, P. (2019), “Economic-engineering modelling of the buildings sector to study the transition towards deep decarbonisation in the EU”, *Energies*, Vol. 12 No. 14, p. 2745, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en12142745>.

- Fotiou, T., Capros, P. and Fragkos, P. (2022), “Policy modelling for ambitious energy efficiency investment in the EU residential buildings”, *Energies*, Vol. 15 No. 6, p. 2233, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15062233>.
- Fuerst, F., McAllister, P., Nanda, A. and Wyatt, P. (2015), “Does energy efficiency matter to home-buyers? An investigation of EPC ratings and transaction prices in England”, *Energy Economics*, Vol. 48, pp. 145-156, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2014.12.012>.
- Fuerst, F., Haddad, M.F.C. and Adan, H. (2020), “Is there an economic case for energy-efficient dwellings in the UK private rental market?”, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Vol. 245, 118642, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.118642>.
- Guren, A., McKay, A., Nakamura, E. and Steinsson, J. (2018), “Housing Wealth Effects: the Long View”, National Bureau of Economic Research, p. w24729, <https://doi.org/10.3386/w24729>.
- HMLR, L.R. (2022), “Average house prices”, HM Land Registry, available at: https://landregistry.data.gov.uk/app/qonsole?query5_localstore
- Huo, Z. and Rios-Rull, J.-V. (2016), Financial Frictions, Asset Prices, and the Great Recession, [Preprint], Staff Report, <https://doi.org/10.21034/sr.526>.
- Kaplan, G., Mitman, K., Violante, G.L., Berger, D., Cloyne, J., Cocco, J., Kiyotaki, N., Luetticke, R., Mankart, J., Rendahl, P., Riechlin, P., Sims, C., Sufi, A., Uhlig, H. and Van, S. (2017), NBER Working Paper Series the Housing Boom and Bust: Model Meets Evidence, available at: <http://www.nber.org/papers/w23694.ack>
- King, M. (1990), “Discussion of J. Muellbauer and A. Murphy; is the U.K. balance of payments sustainable?”, *Economic Policy*, Vol. 11, pp. 383-387.
- Li, W. and Yao, R. (2007), “The life-cycle effects of house price changes”, *Journal of Money, Credit and Banking*, Vol. 39 No. 6, pp. 36-1409, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1538-4616.2007.00071.x>.
- McCoy, D. and Kotsch, R.A. (2021), “Quantifying the distributional impact of energy efficiency measures”, *The Energy Journal*, Vol. 42 No. 01, pp. 121-144, <https://doi.org/10.5547/01956574.42.6.dmcc>.
- Meen, G. and Whitehead, C. (2020), *Understanding Affordability: The Economics of Housing Markets*, Bristol University Press, Bristol.
- Mian, A., Rao, K. and Sufi, A. (2013), “Household balance sheets, consumption, and the economic slump”, *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, Vol. 128 No. 4, pp. 1687-1726, <https://doi.org/10.1093/qje/qjt020>.
- Ministry of Housing (MHCLG) (2021), “EHSEnglish housing survey, 2008-English housing survey, 2017: housing stock data”, [Data set], 1st ed., UK Data Service, <https://doi.org/10.5255/UKDA-SN-8494-1>.
- Muellbauer, J. (2018), “Housing, debt and the economy: a tale of two countries”, *National Institute Economic Review*, Vol. 245, pp. R20-R33, <https://doi.org/10.1177/002795011824500112>.
- Muellbauer, J., Murphy, A., King, M. and Pagano, M. (1990), “Is the UK balance of payments sustainable?”, *Economic Policy*, Vol. 5 No. 11, p. 347, <https://doi.org/10.2307/1344481>.
- Mundlak, Y. (1978), “On the pooling of time series and cross section data”, *Econometrica*, Vol. 46 No. 1, p. 69, <https://doi.org/10.2307/1913646>.
- NAO, N.A.O. (2021), *Green Homes Grant Voucher Scheme*, p. 52, available at: <https://www.nao.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/Green-Homes-Grant-Vouch-er-Scheme.pdf>
- Office For National Statistics (ONS), & Department For Environment, F (2022), “LCFS Living costs and food survey, 2001-living costs and food survey, 2019-2020”, 2nd ed., UK Data Service, [Data set], <https://doi.org/10.5255/UKDA-SN-8803-2>.

ONS (2020), Energy Efficiency of Housing in England and Wales, p. 16, available at: <https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/housing/articles/energyefficiencyofhousinginenglandandwales/2020-09-23>

Paiella, M. and Pistaferri, L. (2017), “Decomposing the wealth effect on consumption”, *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, Vol. 99 No. 4, pp. 710-721, https://doi.org/10.1162/REST_a_00629.

Poterba, J.M. (1984), “Tax subsidies to owner-occupied housing: an asset-market approach”, *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, Vol. 99 No. 4, pp. 729-752, <https://doi.org/10.2307/1883123>.

Rosen, S. (1974), “Hedonic prices and implicit markets: product differentiation in pure competition”, *Journal of Political Economy*, Vol. 82 No. 1, pp. 34-55, <https://doi.org/10.1086/260169>.

Santiago-Rodriguez, E.D. (2021), “The eresee 2020 rehabilitation strategy: an opportunity for a model change in the Spanish housing sector”, *Ciudad y Territorio Estudios Territoriales*, Vol. 53, pp. 239-276, <https://doi.org/10.37230/CyTET.2021.M21.14.1>.

Sinai, T. and Souleles, N.S. (2005), “Owner-occupied housing as a hedge against rent risk”, *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, Vol. 120, pp. 763-789.

Suari-Andreu, E. (2021), “Housing and household consumption: an investigation of the wealth and collateral effects”, *Journal of Housing Economics*, Vol. 54, 101786, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhe.2021.101786>.

Sunikka-Blank, M. and Galvin, R. (2012), “Introducing the prebound effect: the gap between performance and actual energy consumption”, *Building Research and Information*, Vol. 40 No. 3, pp. 260-273, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09613218.2012.690952>.

Wilkinson, S.J. and Sayce, S. (2020), “Decarbonising real estate: the evolving relationship between energy efficiency and housing in Europe”, *Journal of European Real Estate Research*, Vol. 13 No. 3, pp. 387-408, <https://doi.org/10.1108/JERER-11-2019-0045>.

Keywords: Keywords MPC, Consumption, House prices, Age groups, Energy efficiency

Fernández, A., Haffner, M., & Elsinga, M. (2024). *Subsidies or green taxes? Evaluating the distributional effects of housing renovation policies among Dutch households. Journal of Housing and the Built Environment*, 2024, 1-28.

Abstract: Despite persistent housing affordability issues, energy policy and housing renovation are usually investigated separately from housing costs other than energy. Researchers have examined the financial viability of renovation attending to building conditions and the socio-economic characteristics of their occupants. However, the distributional impacts of renovation incentives and the potential of fiscal policy to redistribute housing costs remain understudied. Dutch fiscal policy, favouring homeownership, offers a relevant context to evaluate how property taxation can boost renovation rates. The novelty of this paper resides in investigating the impact of two policies, the current direct subsidy and a proposal for a green tax, on both the financial viability of renovation and the subsequent distribution of housing costs. The proposed green tax combines energy efficiency and taxation of property revenue. We employ a model considering marginal costs of housing renovation, obtained from a government dataset, and marginal benefits, drawn from a hedonic regression. We assess the distributional impacts of different policy scenarios by examining changes in user costs across income deciles. Our findings indicate that existing renovation subsidies exacerbate the regressive distributional impacts resulting from the current housing taxation system in the Netherlands. Introducing energy-efficiency-linked property taxation can make homeownership fiscality less regressive while incentivising housing renovation. Ultimately, this study highlights the importance of

incorporating housing affordability as a fundamental element in renovation policies to balance environmental and distributional objectives.

References:

Allers, M. (2020). Belasting op grond is efficiënt, rechtvaardig én uitvoerbaar. *ESB* 105(4783).

<https://esb.nu/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/U1ZVsgdjZ8ird2W1lgAHqipoSg8.pdf>

Angrist, J., & Kolesar, M. (2021). One instrument to rule them all. NBER Working Paper 29417, 26. Angrist, J. D., & Pischke, J.-S. (2009). *Mostly harmless econometrics: An empiricist's companion*. Princeton University Press.

Arundel, R., & Lennartz, C. (2019). Housing market dualization: Linking insider-outsider divides in employment and housing outcomes. *Housing Studies*, 35(8), 1390–1414.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/02673037.2019.1667960>

Ayala, A. D., Galarraga, I., & Spadaro, J. V. (2016). The price of energy efficiency in the Spanish housing market. *Energy Policy*, 94, 16–24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2016.03.032>

Aydin, E., Brounen, D., & Kok, N. (2020). The capitalization of energy efficiency: Evidence from the housing market. *Journal of Urban Economics*, 117, 103243. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jue.2020.103243>

Backe, S., Pinel, D., Askeland, M., Lindberg, K. B., Korpås, M., & Tomasgard, A. (2023). Exploring the link between the EU emissions trading system and net-zero emission neighbourhoods. *Energy and Buildings*, 281, 112731. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2022.112731>

Berkovec, J., & Fullerton, D. (1992). A general equilibrium model of housing, taxes, and portfolio choice. *Journal of Political Economy*, 100(2), 390–429.

Bertoldi, P., Economidou, M., Palermo, V., Boza-Kiss, B., & Todeschi, V. (2021). How to finance energy renovation of residential buildings: Review of current and emerging financing instruments in the EU. *Wires Energy and Environment*, 10(1), e384. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wene.384>

Bonifaci, P., & Copiello, S. (2018). Incentive policies for residential buildings energy retrofit: An analysis of tax rebate programs in Italy. In A. Bisello, D. Vettorato, P. Laconte, & S. Costa (Eds.), *Smart and sustainable planning for cities and regions* (pp. 267–279). Springer International Publishing.

Bourguignon, F., & Spadaro, A. (2006). Microsimulation as a tool for evaluating redistribution policies. *The Journal of Economic Inequality*, 4(1), 77–106. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10888-005-9012-6>

Brounen, D., & Kok, N. (2011). On the economics of energy labels in the housing market. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, 62(2), 166–179. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeem.2010.11.006>

Castellazzi, L., Zangheri, P., Paci, D., Economidou, M., Labanca, N., Ribeiro, S., Panev, V., Zancanella, P., & Broc, J. S. (2019). Assessment of second long-term renovation strategies under the Energy Efficiency Directive. Joint Research Centre. <https://doi.org/10.2760/973672>

Central Bureau voor Statistiek (2022). Dutch house price increase among EU top four. Retrieved Nov 2023. <https://www.cbs.nl/en-gb/news/2022/28/dutch-house-price-increase-among-eu-top-four>

Cerin, P., Hassel, L. G., & Semenova, N. (2014). Energy performance and housing prices. *Sustainable Development*, 22(6), 404–419. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.1566>

Cheshire, P., & Sheppard, S. (1998). Estimating the demand for housing, land and neighbourhood characteristics. *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics*, 60(3), 357–382.

Chetty, R., Looney, A., & Kroft, K. (2009). Saliency and taxation: Theory and evidence. *American Economic Review*, 99(4), 1145–1177. <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.99.4.1145>

- Clark, T., & Leicester, A. (2005). Inequality and two decades of British tax and benefit reforms. *Fiscal Studies*, 25(2), 129–158. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-5890.2004.tb00100.x>
- Copiello, S., & Donati, E. (2021). Is investing in energy efficiency worth it? Evidence for substantial price premiums but limited profitability in the housing sector. *Energy and Buildings*, 251, 111371. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2021.111371>
- Davis, P., McCord, M. J., McCluskey, W., Montgomery, E., Haran, M., & McCord, J. (2017). Is energy performance too taxing?: A CAMA approach to modeling residential energy in housing in Northern Ireland. *Journal of European Real Estate Research*, 10(2), 124–148. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JERER-06-2016-0023>
- Ebrahimigharehbaghi, S., Qian, Q. K., de Vries, G., & Visscher, H. J. (2022). Application of cumulative prospect theory in understanding energy retrofit decision: A study of homeowners in the Netherlands. *Energy and Buildings*, 261, 111958. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2022.111958>
- Economidou, M., Todeschi, V., Bertoldi, P., D'Agostino, D., Zangheri, P., & Castellazzi, L. (2020). Review of 50 years of EU energy efficiency policies for buildings. *Energy and Buildings*, 225, 110322. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2020.110322>
- Ernould, E. (2022). Revision of the energy performance of buildings directive (EU Legislation in Progress). European Parliament.
- Eryzhenskiy, I., Giraudet, L.-G., Segú, M., Dastgerdi, M. (2022). Zero-interest green loans and home energy retrofits: Evidence from France. <https://cnrs.hal.science/hal-03585110/>
- Fatica, S., & Prammer, D. (2018). Housing and the tax system: How large are the distortions in the euro area? *Fiscal Studies*, 39(2), 299–342. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1475-5890.12159>
- Figari, F., Hollan, K., Matsaganis, M., Zolyomi, E. (2019). Recent changes in housing policies and their distributional impact across Europe (No. EM12/19). EUROMOD Working Paper.
- Fuerst, F., McAllister, P., Nanda, A., & Wyatt, P. (2015). Does energy efficiency matter to home-buyers? An investigation of EPC ratings and transaction prices in England. *Energy Economics*, 48, 145–156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2014.12.012>
- Groh, A., Kuhlwein, H., & Bienert, S. (2022). Does retrofitting pay off? An analysis of German multifamily building data. *Journal of Sustainable Real Estate*, 14(1), 95–112. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19498276.2022.2135188>
- Haffner, M. (2003). Tenure neutrality, a financial-economic interpretation. *Housing Theory and Society*, 20, 72–85. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14036090310001903>
- Haffner, M., & Heylen, K. (2011). User costs and housing expenses. Towards a more comprehensive approach to affordability. *Housing Studies*, 26(4), 593–614. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02673037.2011.559754>
- Haffner, M. E. A., & Oxley, M. J. (1999). Housing subsidies: Definitions and comparisons. *Housing Studies*, 14(2), 145–162. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02673039982894>
- Haffner, M., & Winters, S. (2016). Homeownership taxation in Flanders: Moving towards 'optimal taxation'? *International Journal of Housing Policy*, 16(4), 473–490. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616718.2015.1085214>
- Havlinova, J., van Voss, B. H., Zhang, L., van der Molen, R., & Caloia, F. (2022). Financiering voor de verduurzaming van de woningvo. De Nederlandsche Bank.
- Heylen, K. (2013). The distributional impact of housing subsidies in Flanders. *International Journal of Housing Policy*, 13(1), 45–65. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616718.2013.764660>

Howard, C. (1997). *The hidden welfare state: Tax expenditures and social policy in the United States*. Princeton University Press.

Jakob, M. (2006). Marginal costs and co-benefits of energy efficiency investments. The case of the Swiss residential sector. *Fuel and Energy Abstracts*, 47(3), 193–194. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6701\(06\)81299-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6701(06)81299-3)

Kholodilin, K. A., Kohl, S., Korzhenevych, A., & Pfeiffer, L. (2022). The hidden homeownership welfare state: An international long-term perspective on the tax treatment of homeowners. *Journal of Public Policy*, 1–29. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0143814X2200023X>

Kemeny, J. (1981). *The myth of home ownership: Private versus public choices in housing tenure*. Routledge.

Leodolter, A., Princen, S., & Rutkowski, A. (2022). Immovable property taxation for sustainable & inclusive growth. European Commission Directorate-General for Economic and Financial Affairs. <https://doi.org/10.2765/431531>

Maier, S., & Ricci, M. (2022). The Redistributive Impact of Consumption Taxation in the EU: Lessons from the post-financial crisis decade (No. 10; JRC Working Papers on Taxation and Structural Reforms).

McCoy, D., & Kotsch, R. A. (2021). Quantifying the distributional impact of energy efficiency measures. *The Energy Journal*, 42(01). <https://doi.org/10.5547/01956574.42.6.dmcc>

Millar-Powell. (2022). Measuring Effective Taxation of Housing: Building the foundations for policy reform (OECD Taxation Working Papers No. 56; OECD Taxation Working Papers, Vol. 56). <https://doi.org/10.1787/Oa7e36f2-en>

Ministerie van Binnenlandse Zaken en Koninkrijksrelaties—BZK, (Ministry of Interior), & Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek—CBS. (2022). Thematische collectie: Onderzoeken naar de woningmarkt (WoON en WBO). <https://doi.org/10.17026/dans-27e-r9y3>

Ministry of Economic Affairs, Policy and Climate (2019). *Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan*. Mirrlees, J. A., & Adam, S. (2011). *Tax by design: The Mirrlees review*. Oxford University Press. Muellbauer, J. (2018). Housing, debt and the economy: A tale of two countries. *National Institute Economic Review*, 245, R20–R33. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002795011824500112>

Neveu, A. R., & Sherlock, M. F. (2016). An evaluation of tax credits for residential energy efficiency. *Eastern Economic Journal*, 42(1), 63–79. <https://doi.org/10.1057/eej.2014.35>

OECD Directorate of Employment, Labour and Social Affairs - Social Policy Division. (2022). Affordable Housing Database. HC1–2-Housing-costs-over-income.pdf. <https://www.oecd.org/els/family/HC1-2-Housing-costs-over-income.pdf>

Poterba, J. M. (1984). Tax subsidies to owner-occupied housing: An asset-market approach. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 99(4), 729–752.

Poterba, J. M., & Sinai, T. (2011). Revenue costs and incentive effects of the mortgage interest deduction for owner-occupied housing. *National Tax Journal*, 64(2), 531–564.

Rooijers, F., & Kruit, K. (2018). Incentives voor de warmtetransitie Hoe wordt klimaatneutraal verwarmen voor de energiegebruiker een reële optie? CE Delft.

Rosen, S. (1974). Hedonic prices and implicit markets: Product differentiation in pure competition. *Journal of Political Economy*, 82(1), 34–55.

Rosenow, J., Thomas, S., Gibb, D., Baetens, R., De Brouwer, A., & Cornillie, J. (2023). Clean heating: Reforming taxes and levies on heating fuels in Europe. *Energy Policy*, 173, 113367. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2022.113367>

Skinner, J. (1996). The dynamic efficiency cost of not taxing housing. *Journal of Public Economics*, 59, 397–417.

Sunikka-Blank, M., & Galvin, R. (2012). Introducing the prebound effect: The gap between performance and actual energy consumption. *Building Research and Information*, 40(3), 260–273.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/09613218.2012.690952>

van den Brom, P., Meijer, A., & Visscher, H. (2019). Actual energy saving effects of thermal renovations in dwellings—Longitudinal data analysis including building and occupant characteristics. *Energy and Buildings*, 182, 251–263. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2018.10.025>

Wilhelmsson, M. (2019). Energy performance certificates and its capitalization in housing values in Sweden. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11216101>

Witte, A. D., Sumka, H. J., & Erekson, H. (1979). An estimate of a structural hedonic price model of the housing market: An application of rosen's theory of implicit markets. *Econometrica*, 47(5), 1151.

<https://doi.org/10.2307/1911956>

Keywords: Housing Renovation, Green Taxes, User Costs, Housing Value, Distributional Impact

Fernández, A., Haffner, M., & Elsinga, M. (2024). *When Land is Not Enough; Drawing in Private Capital to Increase Social Rental Housing in Spain.* [Working paper]

Abstract: Across Northwestern Europe, non-state parties play central roles in maintaining and expanding social housing provision. In Spain, the social rental sector has remained underdeveloped as a result of a historical focus on homeownership. Against the current affordability crisis, a new housing law has banned the sale of public land zoned for social housing. In turn, Private-Public Partnerships have emerged as an alternative where public land is leased to a third party to build and manage social housing. Despite low-cost access to land, social housing development remains financially challenging with some tenders failing to attract private sector interest. This paper delves into a PPP by the Catalan Land Institute to tackle the question: How does the interaction of institutional dynamics and financial constraints influence the provision of social rental housing in Spain? A mixed-methods approach is used, combining insights from interviews with a sensitivity analysis of parameters in a Discounted-Cash-Flow (DCF) model. Evidence from this case underscore high financing costs, weak social protection for renters, and fiscal policies misaligned with social objectives as the main obstacles for social housing provision. This paper suggests future research about the impact of tackling these weaknesses through public-backed guarantors, housing allowances, and fiscal incentives.

References:

Aalbers, M. B., Loon, J. V., & Fernandez, R. (2017). The Financialization of a Social Housing Provider. *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research*, 41(4), 572–587. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2427.12520>

Akintoye, A. (Ed.). (2016). *Public private partnerships: A global review*. Routledge/Taylor & Francis Group.

Barker, K. (2004). *Review of housing supply: Delivering stability: securing our future housing needs : final report : recommendations*. H.M.S.O.

Bellod Redondo, J. F. (2011). Techo de Gasto y Estabilidad Presupuestaria. *Presupuesto y Gasto Público*, 65, 97–111.

Burgués, V. A., & de Molina, E. G. (2019). La colaboración público-privada como vector de innovación: Casos de éxito en España. *Revista Vasca de Gestión de Personas y Organizaciones Públicas*, 3.

Carbajal, F. (2003). La política de vivienda en España durante el franquismo. Ciudad y territorio: Estudios territoriales, 138, 639–654.

Deutsche Bundesbank. (2023). The growing significance of central government's off-budget entities (June 2023).

<https://www.bundesbank.de/resource/blob/912872/Od125114f70966ec6467151fc367fba5/mL/2023-06-extrahaushalte-data.pdf>

Droste, C., & Knorr-Siedow, T. (2014). Social Housing in Germany. In K. Scanlon, C. Whitehead, & M. F. Arrigoitia (Eds.), *Social Housing in Germany* (pp. 183–202). John Wiley & Sons, Ltd.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118412367.ch11>

Elsinga, M., & Wassenberg, F. (2014). Social Housing in the Netherlands. In K. Scanlon, C. Whitehead, & M. F. Arrigoitia (Eds.), *Social Housing in Europe* (pp. 21–40). John Wiley & Sons, Ltd.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118412367.ch2>

Fernández, A., Haffner, M., & Elsinga, M. (2023). Three contradictions between ESG finance and social housing decarbonisation: A comparison of five European countries. *Housing Studies*, 1–27.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/02673037.2023.2290516>

Gifreu i Font, J. (2023). Mecanismes de col·laboració públicoprivada per a la provisió i l'explotació econòmica d'habitatge assequible: Un joc de suma positiva. *Revista Catalana de Dret Públic*, 66, 56–85. <https://doi.org/10.58992/rcdp.i66.2023.3998>

Gil García, J., & Martínez López, M. A. (2023). State-Led Actions Reigniting the Financialization of Housing in Spain. *Housing, Theory and Society*, 40(1), 1–21.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/14036096.2021.2013316>

Hodkinson, S. (2011). Housing Regeneration and the Private Finance Initiative in England: Unstitching the Neoliberal Urban Straitjacket. *Antipode*, 43(2), 358–383. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8330.2010.00819.x>

Instituto Nacional de Estadística. (2023). Encuesta de Características Esenciales de la Población y Viviendas (ECEPOV) Año 2021. Datos definitivos. https://www.ine.es/prensa/ecepov_2021_feb.pdf

Janoschka, M., Alexandri, G., Ramos, H. O., & Vives-Miró, S. (2020). Tracing the socio-spatial logics of transnational landlords' real estate investment: Blackstone in Madrid. *European Urban and Regional Studies*, 27(2), 125–141. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0969776418822061>

Jofre-Monseny, J., Martínez-Mazza, R., & Segú, M. (2023). Effectiveness and supply effects of high-coverage rent control policies. *Regional Science and Urban Economics*, 101, 103916.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.regsciurbeco.2023.103916>

Kappeler, A., & Nemoz, M. (n.d.). Economic and Financial Report 2010/04 July 2010.

Kemp, P. A. (2012). Access and Affordability: Housing Allowances. In *International Encyclopedia of Housing and Home* (pp. 23–29). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-047163-1.00205-8>

Kersbergen, K. V., & Waarden, F. V. (2004). 'Governance' as a bridge between disciplines: Cross-disciplinary inspiration regarding shifts in governance and problems of governability, accountability and legitimacy. *European Journal of Political Research*, 43(2), 143–171. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-6765.2004.00149.x>

Kholodilin, K. A., López, F. A., Rey Blanco, D., & Gonzalez Arbués, P. (2022). Lessons from an Aborted Second-Generation Rent Control in Catalonia. *SSRN Electronic Journal*.

<https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4159469>

- Lawson, J., & Ruonavaara, H. (2020). Land policy for affordable and inclusive housing. Smartland, Finnish Academy of Sciences, University of Turku and RMIT University. <https://smartland.fi/wp-content/uploads/Land-policy-for-affordable-and-inclusivehousing-aninternational-review.pdf>
- Lawson, J., Troy, L., & van den Nouwelant, R. (2022). Social housing as infrastructure and the role of mission driven financing. *Housing Studies*, 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02673037.2022.2056152>
- Lerbs, O., & Nobbe, L. (2021). Wie wirtschaftlich sind private Investitionen in öffentlich geförderten Mietwohnungsbau? *Zeitschrift für Immobilienökonomie*, 7(2), 121–144. <https://doi.org/10.1365/s41056-021-00054-8>
- Lévy-Vroelant, C., Schaefer, J.-P., & Tutin, C. (2014). Social Housing in France. In K. Scanlon, C. Whitehead, & M. F. Arrigoitia (Eds.), *Social Housing in Europe* (pp. 123–142). John Wiley & Sons, Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118412367.ch8>
- Lima, V. (2020). The financialization of rental housing: Evictions and rent regulation. *Cities*, 105, 102787. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2020.102787>
- Ling, D. C., & Archer, W. R. (2021). *Real estate principles: A value approach* (Sixth edition). McGraw Hill LLC.
- Monras, J., & Montalvo, J. G. (n.d.). The effect of second-generation rent controls: New evidence from Catalonia.
- Mulford, J. E., Weiner, G. D., & McDowell, J. L. (1980). How Allowance Recipients adjust housing consumption. 1456.
- National Markets and Competition Authority. (2015). Análisis de la contratación Pública en España: Oportunidades de Mejora desde el punto de vista de la competencia (PRO/CNMC/001/15). Comision Nacional De los Mercados y La Competencia. <https://www.cnmc.es/file/123729/download>
- Observatorio de vivienda y suelo. (2022). Boletín especial Alquiler residencial (NIPO: 796-20-148-8). Ministerio de Transportes, Movilidad y Agenda Urbana. <https://www.mitma.gob.es/arquitectura-vivienda-y-suelo/urbanismo-y-politica-desuelo/estudios-y-publicaciones/observatorio-de-vivienda-y-suelo>
- Observatorio de vivienda y suelo. (2023). Boletín 45 T1-2023. Ministerio de Transportes, Movilidad y Agenda Urbana. <https://www.mitma.gob.es/arquitectura-vivienda-y-suelo/urbanismo-y-politica-desuelo/estudios-y-publicaciones/observatorio-de-vivienda-y-suelo>
- OECD Directorate of Employment, Labour and Social Affairs - Social Policy Division. (2022). Affordable Housing Database. HC1-2-Housing-costs-over-income.pdf. <https://www.oecd.org/els/family/HC1-2-Housing-costs-over-income.pdf>
- Palomera, J. (2014). How Did Finance Capital Infiltrate the World of the Urban Poor? Homeownership and social fragmentation in a Spanish neighborhood. *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research*, 38(1), 218–235. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2427.12055>
- Pareja Eastaway, M., & Varo, I. S. M. (2002). The Tenure Imbalance in Spain: The Need for Social Housing Policy. *Urban Studies*, 39(2), 283–295. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00420980120102975>
- Pareja-Eastaway, M., & Sánchez-Martínez, T. (2022). Private rented market in Spain: Can regulation solve the problem? *International Journal of Housing Policy*, 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19491247.2022.2089080>
- Pevevini, M. (2021). Grounding Urban Governance on Housing Affordability: A Conceptual Framework for Policy Analysis. Insights from Vienna (1.0) [dataset]. University of Salento. <https://doi.org/10.1285/I20356609V14I2P848>

- Picazo-Ruiz, F. (2021). Porcentajes de reserva de suelo para vivienda sometida a algún régimen de protección pública. *Ciudad y Territorio Estudios Territoriales*, 2021 MONO. <https://doi.org/10.37230/CyTET.2021.M21.13>
- Poovey, M. (2015). On ‘the limits to financialization.’ *Dialogues in Human Geography*, 5(2), 220–224. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2043820615588159>
- Raco, M., Freire Trigo, S., & Webb, A.-M. (2023). The rise of polycentric regulation and its impacts on the governance of housing associations in England. *Housing Studies*, 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02673037.2022.2156984>
- Ramió Matas, C. (2016). Una Administración pública de futuro sostenible económicamente e innovadora en el contexto de la globalizació. *Cuadernos de Gobierno y Administración Pública*, 3(2), 103–122. <https://doi.org/10.5209/CGAP.55083>
- Savas, E. S. (2000). *Privatization and public-private partnerships*. Chatham House.
- Schwartz, A. F. (2021). *Housing policy in the United States (Fourth edition)*. Routledge.
- Simon, H. (2023). La evolución constitucional de la función social de la propiedad y el nuevo régimen del derecho de propiedad sobre una vivienda en la Ley por el derecho a la vivienda. *Derecho Privado y Constitución*, 42, 139–177.
- Taltavull de la Paz, P. (2001). *Economía de la construcción (1a. ed)*. Civitas.
- Wainwright, T., & Manville, G. (2017). Financialization and the third sector: Innovation in social housing bond markets. *Environment and Planning A: Economy and Space*, 49(4), 819–838. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0308518X16684140>
- Whitehead, C. (2014). Financing Social Rented Housing in Europe. In K. Scanlon, C. Whitehead, & M. F. Arrigoitia (Eds.), *Social Housing in Europe* (pp. 315–330). John Wiley & Sons, Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118412367.ch18>
- Whitehead, C. M. E. (1999). The Provision of Finance for Social Housing: The UK Experience. *Urban Studies*, 36(4), 657–672. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0042098993385>
- Whitehead, C. M. E. (2007). Planning policies and affordable housing: England as a successful case study? *Housing Studies*, 22(1), 25–44. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02673030601024580>
- Wijburg, G., Aalbers, M. B., & Heeg, S. (2018). The Financialisation of Rental Housing 2.0: Releasing Housing into the Privatised Mainstream of Capital Accumulation. *Antipode*, 50(4), 1098–1119. <https://doi.org/10.1111/anti.12382>
- Wilson, W., & Barton, C. (2017). Local Housing Allowance caps and the social rented sector (Briefing Paper 07833). House of Commons Library. <https://researchbriefings.files.parliament.uk/documents/CBP-7833/CBP-7833.pdf>

Keywords: Social Housing, Affordability, Finance, Land, PPP

Fernández, A., Elsinga, M., & Haffner, M. (2023). *Investigating the role of ESG bonds and loans in financing housing renovation among social housing providers: a comparative approach to six European countries*. In Diaconu, A. (Ed.) *Proceedings of the RE-DWELL Grenoble Conference* (pp. 84–88). Pacte Social Sciences Research Centre, University Grenoble Alpes, Grenoble, France.

Abstract: The energy transition across Europe’s built environment will probably be one of the main financial challenges of the coming decades. Renovating the social housing stock to attain the built

fabric standards introduced in the European Directive on Energy Performance of Building (EPBD) will require the mobilisation of both public and private funding as envisioned by the European Commission in the Renovation Wave. In this landscape of increased investment needs, Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) standards have risen to a prominent position as the main indicators of sustainable investment. While ESG-earmarked funds have grown significantly in the last years, there is widespread concern about the real impact of ESG-funded projects and whether these are in fact bringing additional investment into key transitional activities such as the renovation of the social housing stock. This project poses two questions, first, How does ESG funding interlock with the renovation strategies of social housing providers? And second, How do institutional factors affect the uptake of ESG funding? To answer these questions, this project draws from semi-structured interviews with finance officers from housing providers across six European countries with large social housing stocks: Austria, Germany, The Netherlands, France, Sweden, and the UK. The main objective of this paper is to critically assess the contributions of ESG funding to the energy transition and contextualise it within traditional forms of private and public financing of social housing.

Sustainability transition and its financial implications have become an area of legislative focus for European institutions. For instance, the Strategy for financing the transition to a sustainable economy has proposed a set of voluntary standards for European Green Bonds (EUGBS). This standard requires bond issuers to align with the EU Taxonomy, a classification of environmentally sustainable economic activities. When it comes to building renovation, the Taxonomy requires a 30% reduction in primary energy consumption to characterize an investment as “green” and thus be financed through a green bond. For new constructions, the green requirements are even more stringent with primary energy demands set at least 10% lower than national nearly-zero-energy requirements. The introduction of ESG standards does not only target borrowers at the project level but also the information investment funds release to end-investors. The Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation (“SFDR”) imposes a set of information disclosure requirements on funds so these are comparable and clearly labelled. For asset managers, these regulations result in increased transparency requirements, updated prospectus and the release of more granular information. The SFDR also details indicators to identify green assets. In the case of real estate, a formula has been proposed for the identification of those energy inefficient assets by taking into account the value of buildings under EPC C and nearly zero-energy (NZEB) in proportion to overall stock value. These indicators serve to assess how Taxonomy-aligned are different investment funds. The EU’s legislation on ESG has so far focused on environmental indicators and the social Taxonomy is yet to be finalised, as a result, while green financing is becoming more tightly regulated, social indicators remain less stringent.

Real estate is one of the areas where Taxonomy-alignment is supposed to be higher and willingness for investment is stronger. However, transitional risks in real estate are deeper since banking and the wider financial sector are reliant on property valuations, albeit with major divergences by country. The Joint Research Centre (JRC) (Alessi & Battiston, 2022), has estimated that while a 100% of real estate activities are taxonomy-eligible only 15% of them are taxonomy-aligned, despite the existence of widespread transitional risks for 70% of the sector. The goals of the EU legislation and guidance are to serve as labels directing investment towards sustainable activities and signalling which areas are under higher environmental risks. Ultimately, the objective of ESG finance is to increase the pool of investors into aligned activities resulting in more favourable lending conditions such as lower interest rates and broader investor bases. Traditionally, the academic literature on Green finance has focused on the question of additionally, that is whether ESG brings additional funding into aligned sectors. Some researchers highlight Green Bonds as not generating additional capital for environmental protection, as these usually refinance conventional ones at more advantageous rates (Bongaerts & Schoenmaker, 2019). Research on Green Bonds (Fatica & Panzica, 2021) has found that ESG-linked securities do seem to be financing new investments into aligned projects.

When it comes to social housing, our preliminary findings point to unequal access to ESG finance. Countries such as the UK where social housing providers have been accessing private funding for decades seem to be more accommodating to ESG reporting requirements. For example, Peabody, a large London-based provider, has issued a 12-year £350m green bond under its new sustainability

financing framework specifically targeting the energy transition and housing stock renovation. In other countries such as the Netherlands where most social housing associations are funded via loans from the Local Authorities and the Water Banks the implementation of ESG criteria seems to be taking place at the financial intermediary level. Similarly, in France, the Caisse de Dépôts(CDC), a bank providing low-interest loans to housing associations, has issued a green bond that has been used for housing renovation by a Parisian housing association. Preliminarily, the capacity of ESG finance to bring additional funding to social housing renovation seems to be path-dependent hinging on national institutional arrangements and prior direct access to capital markets.

References:

Alessi, L., & Battiston, S. (2022). Two sides of the same coin: Green Taxonomy alignment versus transition risk in financial portfolios. *International Review of Financial Analysis*, 102319.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.irfa.2022.102319>

Bongaerts, D., & Schoenmaker, D. (2019). The Next Step in Green Bond Financing. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3389762>

Fatica, S., & Panzica, R. (2021). Green bonds as a tool against climate? *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 30(5), 2688–2701. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2771>

Keywords: ESG, Social Housing, Energy Transition, Green Finance, Sustainability

Fernández, A., Elsinga, M., & Haffner, M. (2023). *Three contradictions between ESG finance and social housing decarbonisation: a comparison of five European countries*. *Housing Studies*, 2023, 1-27.

Abstract: The regulation of financial markets according to Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) criteria has become a priority for the European Union (EU). Recent legislation, such as the EU Green Taxonomy, aims to identify sustainable investments enhancing transparency and accountability while steering private finance toward environmental objectives. The introduction of ESG criteria poses specific questions for Social Housing Organisations (SHOs), particularly as the decarbonisation of the housing stock is also incorporated into national legislation. This article contributes to the social housing finance literature by breaking ground on ESG, an area of intensive legislative activity currently re-shaping financial markets. The study draws from interviews with SHOs' finance directors, banking officers, rating agencies and public officials to answer the question: How does the introduction of ESG legislation affect the financing of social housing decarbonisation? First, the results show that ESG legislation is broadening reporting responsibilities while producing only limited additional finance ultimately geared towards large and commercially oriented SHOs. Second, the expansion of energy-efficiency requirements is resulting in higher costs creating tensions with SHOs' social mission of building homes at affordable rents. Third, the adoption of ESG financing is producing inequalities in access to capital across national financing systems and individual providers.

References:

Aalbers, M. B. (2017) The variegated financialization of housing, *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research*, 41, pp. 542–554.

Aalbers, M. B. (2022) Towards a relational and comparative rather than a contrastive global housing studies, *Housing Studies*, 37, pp. 1054–1072.

Aalbers, M. B., Taylor, Z. J., Klinge, T. J. & Fernandez, R. (2023) In real estate investment We trust: State De-risking and the ownership of listed US and German residential real estate investment trusts, *Economic Geography*, 99, pp. 312–335.

Bertoldi, P., Economidou, M., Palermo, V., Boza-Kiss, B. & Todeschi, V. (2021) How to finance energy renovation of residential buildings: Review of current and emerging financing instruments in the EU, *WIREs Energy and Environment*, 10, pp. e384.

Bindslev, J. (2018) New Financing of Social Housing Strengthens the Market for Danish Government Securities (Denmark: Danmarks National Bank).

https://www.nationalbanken.dk/en/publications/Documents/2018/12/ANALYSIS_no%2024_New%20financing%20of%20social%20housing%20strengthens%20the%20market%20for%20Danish%20government%20securities.pdf (accessed December 2023).

Blackwell, T. & Bengtsson, B. (2023) The resilience of social rental housing in the United Kingdom, Sweden and Denmark. How institutions matter, *Housing Studies*, 38, pp. 269–289.

BNG Bank (2021) Annual Report 2021. BNG. <https://www.bngbank.com/Financials/Annual-report-2021> (accessed December 2023).

Boelhouwer, P. & Van der Heijden, H. (1992) *Housing Systems in Europe: Part I* (Delft, The Netherlands: Delft University Press).

Boelhouwer, P. J. (Ed.). (1997) *Financing the Social Rented Sector in Western Europe* (Delft, The Netherlands: Delft University Press).

CBI (2021) \$500bn Green Issuance 2021: Social and sustainable acceleration: Annual green \$1tn in sight: Market expansion forecasts for 2022 and 2025. <https://www.climatebonds.net/2022/01/500bn-green-issuance-2021-social-and-sustainable-acceleration-annual-green-1tn-sight-market> (accessed December 2023).

Clarion (2020) Clarion Housing Group raises £350m in record breaking sustainable bond issue. <https://www.clarionhg.com/news-and-media/2022/04/11/clarion-350m-in-record-breaking-sustainable-bond-issue> (accessed December 2023).

Conrads, C. (2022) Policy and regulation in the area of tension between shaping the ESG transformation and growing regulatory pressure, in: T. Veith, C. Conrads & F. Hackelberg (Eds) *ESG and Real Estate: A Practical Guide for the Entire Real Estate and Investment Life Cycle* (Freiburg, Germany: Haufe-Lexware). <https://ebookcentral-proquest-com.tudelft.idm.oclc.org/lib/delft/detail.action?docID=6998863#> (accessed December 2023).

Cortellini, G. & Panetta, I. C. (2021) Green bond: A systematic literature review for future research agendas, *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 14, pp. 589.

Doranzo, R., Siracusa, V. & Antonelli, S. (2021). Green bonds: the sovereign issuers' perspective, Bank of Italy Markets, Infrastructures, Payment Systems Working Paper No. 3. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3854966> or doi: 10.2139/ssrn.3854966.

Droste, C. & Knorr-Siedow, T. (2014) Social housing in Germany, in: K. Scanlon, C. Whitehead, & M. F. Arrigoitia (Eds.), *Social Housing in Europe*, pp. 183–202 (Oxford, UK: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd).

Economidou, M., Todeschi, V., Bertoldi, P., D'Agostino, D., Zangheri, P. & Castellazzi, L. (2020) Review of 50 years of EU energy efficiency policies for buildings, *Energy and Buildings*, 225, pp. 110322.

EIB (2019) Austria: EIB and Erste Bank promote affordable housing. <https://www.eib.org/en/press/all/2019-133-eib-and-erste-bank-promote-affordable-housing-in-austria> (accessed December 2023).

Elsinga, M. & Wassenberg, F. (2014) Social housing in the Netherlands. In K. Scanlon, C. Whitehead, & M. F. Arrigoitia (Eds), *Social Housing in Europe*, pp. 21–40 (Oxford: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd).

European Central Bank (2022) Good Practices on Climate-Related and Environmental Risk Management: Observations from the 2022 Thematic Review (Frankfurt, Germany: Publications Office). <https://doi.org/10.2866/417808>

European Commission. Joint Research Centre. Institute for Energy and Transport (2014) Overcoming the Split Incentive Barrier in the Building Sector: Workshop Summary (Ispra, Italy: Publications Office). <https://doi.org/10.2790/30582>

Fama, E. F. & French, K. R. (2007) Disagreement, tastes, and asset prices, \$. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 83, pp. 667–689.

Fatica, S. & Panzica, R. (2021) Green bonds as a tool against climate change? *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 30, pp. 2688–2701.

Galvin, R. (2023) Do housing rental and sales markets incentivise energy-efficient retrofitting of Western Germany's post-war apartments? Challenges for property owners, tenants, and policymakers, *Energy Efficiency*, 16, pp. 25.

Hachenberg, B. & Schiereck, D. (2018) Are green bonds priced differently from conventional bonds?, *Journal of Asset Management*, 19, pp. 371–383.

Haffner, M. E. A. (2021) Pathways of Dutch and German social renting, in: S. Tsenkova (Ed.) *Cities and Affordable Housing*, 1st ed., pp. 247–258 (New York, NY: Routledge).

Haffner, M. E. A., Hoekstra, J., Oxley, M. J. & Heijden, H. v d (2009) *Bridging the Gap Between Social and Market Rented Housing in Six European Countries?* (Amsterdam, The Netherlands: IOS Press).

Haffner, M., Hoekstra, J., Oxley, M. & Heijden, H. V. D. (2010) Universalistic, particularistic and Middle way approaches to comparing the private rental sector, *International Journal of Housing Policy*, 10, pp. 357–377.

Housing Europe. (2020) *The Cost of the Renovation Wave*. <https://www.housingeurope.eu/file/948/download> (accessed December 2023).

Kadi, J. & Lilius, J. (2022) The remarkable stability of social housing in Vienna and Helsinki: A multi-dimensional analysis, *Housing Studies*, pp. 1–25.

Kleniewski, N. & Harloe, M. (1996) The people's home? Social rented housing in Europe and America, *Contemporary Sociology*, 25, pp. 75.

Knuth, S. (2016) Seeing green in San Francisco: City as resource frontier: Seeing green in San Francisco, *Antipode*, 48, pp. 626–644.

Kofner, S. (2017) Social housing in Germany: an inevitably shrinking sector?, *Critical Housing Analysis*, 4, pp. 61–71.

Kössl, G. (2022) Affordable housing and social inclusion - The case of Vienna and Austria, in: O. Heckmann (Ed.), *Future Urban Habitation*, 1st ed., pp. 115–129 (Oxford, UK: Wiley).

Lawson, J. (2013) *The use of guarantees in affordable housing investment—A selective international review* (Melbourne, Australia: Australian Housing and Urban Research Institute).

Lévy-Vroelant, C., Schaefer, J.-P. & Tutin, C. (2014) Social housing in France, in: K. Scanlon, C. Whitehead, & M. F. Arrigoitia (Eds.), *Social Housing in Europe*, pp. 123–142 (Oxford, UK: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd).

Lunde, J. & Whitehead, C. (2016) Following on from a quarter of a century of mortgage debt, in: J. Lunde & C. Whitehead (Eds.), *Milestones in European Housing Finance*, pp. 433–446 (Oxford, UK: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd).

- Mangold, M. & Mjörnell, K. (2022) Swedish public and private housing companies' access to the capital market for financing energy renovation, *Journal of Housing and the Built Environment*, 38, pp. 673–697.
- Mundt, A. & Springler, E. (2016) Milestones in housing finance in Austria over the last 25 years, in: J. Lunde & C. Whitehead (Eds.), *Milestones in European Housing Finance*, pp. 55–73 (Oxford, UK: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd).
- Norris, M. & Byrne, M. (2021) Funding resilient and fragile social housing systems in Ireland and Denmark, *Housing Studies*, 36, pp. 1469–1489.
- NWB Bank (2021) Annual Report 2021. NWB.
https://nwbbank.com/application/files/9816/5468/9535/NWB_Bank_Annual_report_2021.pdf
(accessed December 2023).
- OECD (2020) Social Housing: A key part of past and future housing Policy. https://read.oecd-ilibrary.org/view/?ref=137_137578-34brg1nxua&title=Social-Housing-A-Key-Part-of-Past-and-Future-Housing-Policy (accessed December 2023).
- Reuters (2022) German officials raid Deutsche Bank's DWS over "greenwashing" claims.
<https://www.reuters.com/business/german-police-raid-deutsche-banks-dws-unit-2022-05-31/>
(accessed December 2023).
- Ruonavaara, H. (1993) Types and forms of housing tenure: Towards solving the comparison/translation problem, *Scandinavian Housing and Planning Research*, 10, pp. 3–20.
- S&P. (2022) Ratings Direct: Waarborgfonds Sociale Woningbouw (Stockholm, Sweden: Global Ratings).
https://www.wsw.nl/uploads/tx_dddload/S_P_Global_juli_2022.pdf (accessed December 2023).
- Scanlon, K., Whitehead, C. & Arrigoitia, M. F. (2015) Social housing in Europe, *European Policy Analysis*, 17, pp. 1–12.
- Schaefer, J.-P. (2003) Financing social housing in France, *Housing Finance International*, 17, pp. 27–34.
<https://www.proquest.com/docview/216202047/fulltextPDF/25E7219DA494494EPQ/1?accountid=27026> (accessed December 2023).
- Tutin, C. & Vorms, B. (2016) Milestones of housing finance in France between 1988 and 2014: Is the French Credit System a Gallic Oddity?, in: J. Lunde & C. Whitehead (Eds.), *Milestones in European Housing Finance*, pp. 165–181 (Oxford, UK: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd.)
- van Hal, A., Coen, M. & Stutvoet, E. (2019) Energy performance fee to cover investments in the energy efficiency of affordable housing The Netherlands, in: G. van Bortel (Ed.), *Affordable Housing Governance and Finance: Innovations, Partnerships and Comparative Perspectives* (Oxford, UK: Routledge).
- Vonovia (2023) FY 2022: Earnings Call Presentation. <https://investoren.vonovia.de/en/news-and-publications/presentations/> (accessed December 2023).
- Wainwright, T. & Manville, G. (2017) Financialization and the third sector: Innovation in social housing bond markets, *Environment and Planning A: Economy and Space*, 49, pp. 819–838.
- Whitehead, C. (2014) Financing social rented housing in Europe, in: K. Scanlon, C. Whitehead, & M. F. Arrigoitia (Eds.), *Social housing in Europe*, pp. 315–330 (Oxford, UK: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd).
- Whitehead, C. M. E. (1999) The provision of finance for social housing: The UK experience, *Urban Studies*, 36, pp. 657–672.
- Zerbib, O. D. (2019) The effect of pro-environmental preferences on bond prices: Evidence from green bonds, *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 98, pp. 39–60.

Keywords: Social Housing, ESG, Renovation, Comparative Policy, European Policy

Furman, S., Martínez, A., & Martín, X. (2024). *Social Housing Retrofit: Case studies in resident engagement*. Proceedings of the RE-DWELL Conference “Sustainable Living, Affordable Homes”, 16 May 2024, Barcelona, Spain.

Abstract: Social housing retrofit is gaining momentum throughout Europe, in a bid to meet the Net-0 energy targets by 2050. A 2021 recast of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive stipulates targeting retrofits to those “living in social housing” (European Commission, 2021, p.14). Movements including the Green New Deal’s Renovation Wave and Fit for 55 are supported by funding schemes such as the UK’s Social Housing Decarbonisation Fund and the EU’s Next Generation Fund. Whole-house deep energy retrofitting (DER) has been popularised by top-down initiatives including Passivhaus’ EnerPHit certification, Energy Performance Certificates, and EnergieSprong. However, performance gaps after retrofits can be as high as five times the predicted energy consumption (Traynor, 2019), driven by the rebound effect, the prebound effect, occupant behaviour, improper installation, and simulation uncertainties.

The literature shows that social housing residents are those best placed to describe the way they live and therefore determine their housing needs (Awwal et al., 2022; Boess, 2022; Gianfrate et al., 2017; Lucchi & Delera, 2020; van Hoof & Boerenfijn, 2018; Walker et al., 2014). Residents prioritise non-energy benefits (NEBs) over energy-related benefits (Broers et al., 2022), particularly social housing residents whose needs differ from homeowners (Santangelo & Tondelli, 2017). Resident engagement is therefore a vital component of holistic sustainability in social housing retrofit—social, environmental, and economic—and can increase energy performance, health and wellbeing, quality of life, and user empowerment, thus closing the performance gap.

References:

Awwal, S., Soliman-Junior, J., Ayo-Adejuyigbe, M., Tzortzopoulos, P., & Kagioglou, M. (2022). Social Housing Retrofit Living Lab: Methodological Approach. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 1101(5), 052020. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/1101/5/052020>

Boess, S. (2022). Let’s Get Sociotechnical: A Design Perspective on Zero Energy Renovations. *Urban Planning*, 7(2), 97–107. <https://doi.org/10.17645/up.v7i2.5107>

Broers, W., Kemp, R., Vasseur, V., Abujidi, N., & Vroon, Z. (2022). Justice in social housing: Towards a people-centred energy renovation process. *Energy Research and Social Science*, 88. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102527>

European Commission. (2021). 2021/0426 (COD) Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Energy Performance of Buildings (recast). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52021DC0550&from=EN>

Gianfrate, V., Piccardo, C., Longo, D., & Giachetta, A. (2017). Rethinking social housing: Behavioral patterns and technological innovations. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 33, 102–112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2017.05.015>

Groat, L., & Wang, D. (2013). *Architectural Research Methods* (2nd ed.). Wiley.

Lucchi, E., & Delera, A. C. (2020). Enhancing the historic public social housing through a user-centered design-driven approach. *Buildings*, 10(9). <https://doi.org/10.3390/BUILDINGS10090159>

Santangelo, A., & Tondelli, S. (2017). Occupant behavior and building renovation of the social housing stock: Current and future challenges. *Energy and Buildings*, 145, 276–283. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2017.04.019>

Traynor, J. (2019). *ENERPHIT: A step by step guide to low energy retrofit*. RIBA Publishing.

van Hoof, J., & Boerenfijn, P. (2018). Re-inventing existing real estate of social housing for older people: Building a new De Benring in Voorst, The Netherlands. *Buildings*, 8(7).

<https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings8070089>

Walker, S. L., Lowery, D., & Theobald, K. (2014). Low-carbon retrofits in social housing: Interaction with occupant behavior. *Energy Research and Social Science*, 2, 102–114.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2014.04.004>

Keywords: Social Housing, Retrofit, Case Studies, Resident Engagement

Furman, S. (2022). *Upgrading social housing to meet the socio-economic needs of today's dwellers, and the environmental needs of the planet: A framework beyond retrofit*. In *New Housing Researchers Colloquium (NHRC) at the European Network for Housing Research (ENHR) Conference 2022*. Barcelona, Spain.

Abstract: Increased resident satisfaction is a vital agenda for sustainable social housing retrofit, and a multidimensional challenge. The project concerns upgrading existing social housing stock in line with the triple bottom line of sustainability: social, environmental, and economic.

Commodification of housing has migrated social housing to the private sector, leaving mixed-tenure 'pepper-pot' buildings and disagreement over retrofit decisions. Currently, affordable housing is too expensive for some socio-economic groups. The large-scale retrofit of residential building stock must provide homes people can 'afford'. Housing associations, local authorities, large housing providers and other stakeholders need to be convinced that large-scale retrofit is necessary and will provide a return on investment through lower maintenance costs, reduced crime rates, increased educational attainment, wellbeing, and mental and physical health. Long-term affordability should be considered throughout renovation to deter gentrification.

The research objective is to develop a matrix for mid- to large-scale social housing retrofit to deliver affordable and sustainable housing. Under broad categories such as 'sustainability', the framework will identify key improvements including building envelope and energy efficiency.

The sets of criteria will be informed by 1) successes and failures of some partly-renovated post-war European social housing, 2) deeper case studies identified through consultations with INCASÒL and Housing Europe.

The following questions will be addressed during case study analysis: How long should evaluation of each case study take place? What problems were identified by renovations and how were solutions found? What did the renovators want to achieve? How do the renovations align with sustainability agendas such as the SDG's? How has renovation impacted residents' lives, post occupancy?

From the results, I will originate a comprehensive multi-criteria framework that suggests what renovations should occur, why they should occur, and identify the multiple actors and stakeholders that will benefit, along with a best practice guide for easily digestible information.

References:

Agliardi, E., Cattani, E., & Ferrante, A. (2018). Deep energy renovation strategies: A real option approach for add-ons in a social housing case study. *Energy and Buildings*, 161, 1–9.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2017.11.044>

European Commission. (2020). *A Renovation Wave for Europe -greening our buildings, creating jobs, improving lives*.

European Commission. (2020). Stepping up Europe's 2030 climate ambition: Investing in a climate-neutral future for the benefit of our people.

Elkington, J. (1997). *Cannibals With Forks: Triple Bottom Line of 21st Century Business*. Oxford.

Garnier, S., Pittini, A., del Pero, C., & Vallan, A. (2020). HEART D9.9 - Evaluation of building users' acceptance and satisfaction - I.

Grecchi, M. (2022). Building Renovation and Reuse Existing Buildings to Save Energy and Respond to New Needs (B. Pernici, S. della Torre, B. M. Colosimo, T. Faravelli, R. Paolucci, & S. Piardi, Eds.). Springer.

Gupta, R., & Gregg, M. (2015). Do deep low carbon retrofits actually work? *Energy Procedia*, 78, 919–924. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2015.11.019>

Institute for Sustainability, & UCL Energy Institute. (2012). Retrofit strategies. Key Findings: Retrofit project team perspectives. https://www.instituteforsustainability.co.uk/uploads/File/2236_KeySummary03.pdf

Lucchi, E., & Delera, A. C. (2020). Enhancing the historic public social housing through a user-centered design-driven approach. *Buildings*, 10(9). <https://doi.org/10.3390/BUILDINGS10090159>

Oevermann, H., Degenkolb, J., Dießler, A., Karge, S., & Peltz, U. (2016). Participation in the reuse of industrial heritage sites: The case of Oberschöneweide, Berlin. *International Journal of Heritage Studies*, 22(1), 43–58. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13527258.2015.1083460>

Pierpoint, D., Rickaby, P., & Hancox, S. (n.d.). *Social Housing Retrofit Toolkit MODULE 3: Housing Retrofit Policy Summary*.

Scuderi, G. (2019). Retrofit of residential buildings in Europe. *Designs*, 3(1), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.3390/designs3010008>

STBA. (2016). What is Whole House Retrofit?

Xue, Y., Temeljotov-Salaj, A., & Lindkvist, C. M. (2022). Renovating the retrofit process: People-centered business models and co-created partnerships for low-energy buildings in Norway. *Energy Research and Social Science*, 85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2021.102406>

Keywords: Social Housing, Affordable Housing, Retrofit, Sustainability

Horvat, M. (2024). *Improving housing affordability through housing allowances: a pilot project in Croatia*. Proceedings of the RE-DWELL Conference “Sustainable Living, Affordable Homes”, 16 May 2024, Barcelona, Spain.

Abstract: Housing affordability is one of the most pressing social problems in most EU Member States. Cities, especially capital cities, are experiencing a significant influx of inhabitants, leading to an increase in housing costs. This gradual densification process combined with slow housing construction is exacerbating affordability inequality for average earners, with the gap widening for those on below average incomes, leaving more and more European households unable to afford adequate housing.

The inability of younger generations and the precariously employed to buy their own home is forcing them into the rental market, earning them the label "Generation Rent". The phenomena of financialisation and privatisation, particularly in CEE countries, have contributed to the high proportion of homeowners in societies. This worsens housing affordability since many housing units are converted into short-term rental properties, limiting long-term rental options and driving up rental prices. In urban

centres, especially in capital cities, there is often a shortage of affordable housing options such as public or rental housing.

In this paper we will look at housing allowances, a special type of demand-side intervention that has characteristics of both a housing subsidy and an income subsidy. We will evaluate a Croatian pilot project in which housing allowances are distributed as a measure to increase housing affordability. Finally, we will recommend policy measures that should be considered for a greater impact of the housing allowances in Croatia.

References:

Bežovan, G. (2010). Analiza sustava subvencioniranja najamnina i troškova stanovanja te prakse gradnje socijalnih stanova u Hrvatskoj [Analysis of the rent subsidy system and housing costs, and the practice of building social housing in Croatia], Hrvatska i komparativna javna uprava: časopis za teoriju i praksu javne uprave, Vol. 10 No. 3, 2010.

Bežovan, G. (2013). The Social Housing Search Delayed by Postwar Reconstruction. In Hegedüs, J., Lux, M. & Teller, N. (Eds.) Social Housing in Transition Countries (pp. 128- 146). London: Routledge. ISBN 9781138809567

Bežovan, G. & Jakovčević, D. (2023). Učinci stambenog zbrinjavanja mlađe populacije na demografske trendove u Zagrebu. [The effects of providing housing for the younger population on demographic trends in Zagreb.], Revija za socijalnu politiku, 30 (1), 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.3935/rsp.v30i1.1800>

Central office for demography and young. (2023). Pilot project public call- local self- government units for financial support aimed at co-financing costs housing for young families and young people in 2023 <https://demografijaimladi.gov.hr/UserDocImages//Dokumenti//PILOTP~1.PDF>

Central office for demography and young. (2023a). Notice on subsidizing housing costs for full-time students <https://demografijaimladi.gov.hr/vijesti-4693/obavijest-o-subvenciji-troskova-stanovanja-redovitim-studentima/6698>

Croatian Bureau of Statistics. (2022). The final results of the Census 2021 have been published. Address <https://dzs.gov.hr/vijesti/objavljeni-konacni-rezultati-popisa-2021/1270>, accessed on 15.2.2024

Coldburn, G. (2019). The use of markets in housing policy: a comparative analysis of housing subsidy programs, Housing Studies 36(1):1-34. <http://doi.org/10.1080/02673037.2019.1686129>

Deloitte (2022). Property Index - Overview of European Residential Markets. 11th edition, August 2022

Eerola, E., & Lyytikäinen, T. (2021). Housing Allowance and Rents: Evidence from a Stepwise Subsidy Scheme. Scandinavian Journal of Economics, 123(1), 84–109. <https://doi.org/10.1111/sjoe.12396>

Eurostat. (2023). Glossary: Housing cost overburden rate https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Glossary:Housing_cost_overburden_rate&lang=en

Government of Croatia (2023). Zajamčena minimalna naknada. <https://gov.hr/hr/zajamcena-minimalna-naknada/714>

Griggs, J., & Kemp.: A. (2012). Housing Allowances as Income Support: Comparing European Welfare Regimes. 12(4), 391– 412. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616718.2012.711987>

Haffner, M. E. A., & Boelhouwer.: J. (2006). Housing allowances and economic efficiency. International Journal of Urban and Regional Research, 30(4), 944–959. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2427.2006.00699.x>

Hegedüs, J., (2007). “Social Housing in Transition Countries.” Social Housing in Europe. London: LSE.

Hyslop, D. R. & Rea, D. (2019). Do housing allowances increase rents? Evidence from a discrete policy change, *Journal of Housing Economics*, Volume 46, December 2019, 101657

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhe.2019.101657>

Institute of Economics in Zagreb & Croatian Ministry of Physical Planning, Construction and State Assets (2023). Pregled tržišta nekretnina Republike Hrvatske [en. Overview of the real estate market in the Republic of Croatia], Institute of Economics in Zagreb, ISSN 2706- 476X

Susin, S. (2002). Rent vouchers and the price of low-income housing, *Journal of Public Economics*, 83, 109–152.

Keywords: Affordable Housing, Housing Allowance, Housing Policy

Horvat, M., & Bežovan, G. (2024). *Sustainability and Capacity Analysis of Croatian Homeless Service Providers*. *European Journal of Homelessness*, 18(2). 67-94.

Abstract: Homelessness is a complex phenomenon in today's societies. As such, it is both a manifestation of extreme poverty and social exclusion and a symptom of globalisation and systemic changes in the world economy. Nevertheless, there is a significant research gap regarding the financial, institutional, and social sustainability of homeless service providers, which are the main type of service providers in most EU Member States, especially in Eastern European countries such as Croatia. This study addresses this gap with a mixed methods approach that includes a literature review, a survey of all Croatian homeless service providers, and a focus group with selected providers. The result is that the temporary funding of projects is one of the main problems in attracting and retaining staff and volunteers and ensuring the longevity of the service. We find that civil society organisations (CSOs) from large cities have better financial prospects and find it easier to find adequate staff than those in smaller cities. In terms of social sustainability, much of the success is based on the commitment and social capital of the individual members of the CSOs. We propose that the current project-based funding scheme is changed on the national level into a contract-based funding system to enable a stable financial structure, a more attractive working environment, and a better social reintegration rate for users.

References:

Albrecht, T.L., Johnson, G.M., and Walther, J.B. (1993) Understanding Communication Processes in Focus Groups, in: D.L. Morgan (Ed.) *Successful Focus Groups: Advancing the State of the Art*, pp. 51-65. (Newbury Park: Sage).

Aleksanyan, A. (2020) Civil Society as a Phenomenon of Post-Soviet Political Life: A Threat or a Guarantor of National Security, in: A. Mihr (Ed.) *Transformation and Development Studies in the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe (OSCE) Member States*, pp.29-50. (Switzerland: Springer).

Anheier, H.K. (2005) Measure for Measure: A Commentary on Heinrich and the State of Civil Society Indicators Research, *Journal of Civil Society* 1(3) pp.241-246.

Ayed, N., Akther, S., Bird, V., Priebe, S., and Jones, J. (2020) How is Social Capital Conceptualised in the Context of Homelessness? A Conceptual Review using a Systematic Search 1, *European Journal of Homelessness* 14(2) pp.99-136.

Baptista, I. and Marlier, E. (2019) *Fighting Homelessness and Housing Exclusion in Europe: A Study of National Policies* (Issue October) (Brussels: Publication Office).

- Bežovan, G. and Matančević, J. (2011) CIVICUS Civil Society Index in Croatia – Policy Action Brief. Available at: <https://ceraneo.hr/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/CIVIL-SOCIETY-INDEX-IN-CROATIA-FOR-2010.-Annex.pdf>.
- Bežovan, G. and Zrinščak, S. (2006) Postaje li civilno društvo u Hrvatskoj čimbenikom društvenih promjena? [Is Civil Society Becoming a Driver of Societal Change in Croatia?] *Rev. soc. polit.* pp.1-27.
- Bežovan, G. (2012) Croatia: The Social Housing Search Delayed by Postwar Reconstruction, in: J. Hegedüs, M. Lux, and N. Teller (Eds.) *Social Housing in Transition Countries*, pp.125-143. (New York: Routledge).
- Bežovan, G. (2019) *ESPN Thematic Report on National Strategies to Fight Homelessness and Housing Exclusion – Croatia* (Brussels: European Commission).
- Bežovan, G., Baturina, D., and Horvat, M. (2023) Evolution and Evaluation of the State of Social Rights of the Homeless in Croatia, *Criminology and Social Integration* 31(1) pp.55-77.
- Bilinović Rajačić, A. and Čikić. (2021) *Beskućništvo teorija, prevencija, intervencija* [Homelessness theory, prevention, intervention] The Faculty of Philosophy, University of Novi Sad. ISBN 978-86-6065-647-8
- Božac, M. (2020) *Udruge u Hrvatskoj sazrijevaju: rast usporava, prihodi rastu, ali uz nejednakosti* (Associations in Croatia: Growth Slowing Down, Revenues Are Increasing But Along With Inequalities) Available at: <https://markobozac.com/analiza/udruge-hrvatska-analiza-civilno-drustvo/>.
- City of Zagreb (2022) *Naknada za troškove stanovanja* [Compensation for Housing Cost]. Available at: <https://www.zagreb.hr/naknada-za-troskove-stanovanja/6759>.
- City of Zagreb (2021) *Zagrebačka strategija borbe protiv siromaštva i socijalne isključenosti od 2021. do 2025* [Zagreb's Strategy for the Fight Against Poverty and Social Exclusion from 2021 to 2025]. Available at: <https://www.zagreb.hr/zagrebacka-strategija-borbe-protiv-siromastva-i-so/170235>.
- Cooper, B. (1995) *Shadow People: The Reality of Homelessness in the '90s* (Sydney: Sydney City Mission).
- Cordes, J. and Vogel, R. (2022) Comparing Employer Attractiveness of Public Sector Organizations to Nonprofit and Private Sector Organizations: An Experimental Study in Germany and the U.S. *Review of Public Personnel Administration* 43(2) pp.260-287.
- Civil Society Sector – CSS. (n.d.). How to ensure financial sustainability for CSOs? Accessed from http://siviltoplumsektoru.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/financialbrochure_en.pdf (15.9.2022)
- Družić Ljubotina, O., Kletečki Radović, M., and Ogresta, J. (2022) Kvaliteta usluga za beskućnike iz perspektive korisnika prihvatilišta i prenočišta [The Quality of Services for the Homeless from the Perspective of Users of Shelters and Overnight Shelters], *Bogoslovska smotra* 92(4) pp.697-728.
- Družić Ljubotina, O., Kletečki Radović, M., and Ogresta, J. (2022a) Determinants of Causal Attributions of Homelessness in Croatia, *Rev. soc. polit.* 29(2) pp.163-190.
- Dunn, L. (2022) *75 Ways to Prevent Homelessness: A Collection of Practical Examples to Share, Inspire and Add To* (Scotland: Crisis Scotland).
- E-Građani (2023) *Prihvatilišta za beskućnike* [Homeless Shelters]. Available at: <https://gov.hr/hr/prihvatilista-za-beskucnike/718>.
- Eurostat (2022) *Living Conditions in Europe – Housing*. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Living_conditions_in_Europe_-_housing&action=statexp-seat&lang=hr.

FEANTSA (2017) European Typology of Homelessness Ethos and Housing Exclusion. Available at: <https://www.feantsa.org/download/ethos2484215748748239888.pdf>.

Fehér, B. and Teller, N. (2016) An Emerging Research Strand: Housing Exclusion in Central and South East Europe, *European Journal of Homelessness* 10(3) pp67-85.

Ferenčuhová, S. and Vašát, P. (2022) Ethnographies of Urban Change: Introducing Homelessness and the Post-Socialist City, *Urban Geography* 42(9) pp.1217-1229.

Filipovič Hrast, M., Somogyi, E., and Teller, N. (2009) The Role of NGOs in the Governance of Homelessness in Hungary and Slovenia, *European Journal of Homelessness* 3(1) pp.101-126.

Fitzpatrick, S. and Davies, L. (2021) The 'Ideal' Homelessness Law: Balancing 'Rights Centred' and 'Professional-Centred' Social Policy, *Journal of Social Welfare and Family Law* 43(2) pp.175-197.

Forest, R. (2019) How Can We Support Local CSOs To Be Financially Sustainable? Available at: <https://www.bond.org.uk/news/2019/05/how-can-we-support-local-csos-to-be-financially-sustainable>.

Government of Croatia (2023) Guaranteed Minimum Benefit. Available at: <https://gov.hr/en/guaranteed-minimum-benefit/714>.

Green, S.N. (2017) Civil Society at a Crossroads: Exploring Sustainable Operating Models. A Report on the CSIS Human initiative (Washington D.C.: CSIS).

Heinrich, V.F. and Fioramonti, L. (2008) CIVICUS Global Survey of the State of Civil Society, Volume 2: Comparative Perspectives (Boulder, CO: Kumarian Press).

Heinrich, V.F. (2006) Studying Civil Society Across the World: A Rebuttal, *Journal of Civil Society* 2(1) pp.79-82.

Howard, M.M. (2005) Conceptual and Methodological Suggestions for Improving Cross-National Measure of Civil Society: Commentary on Heinrich, *Journal of Civil Society* 1(3) pp.229-233.

Ingram, G. (2020). Civil society: An essential ingredient of development. Brookings. Accessed from <https://www.brookings.edu/blog/up-front/2020/04/06/civil-society-an-essential-ingredient-of-development/>. (13.9.2022)

Kostelić, K. and Peruško, E. (2021) Skupine čimbenika i njihov utjecaj na važne životne odluke: beskućnici u Puli [Groups of Factors and their Influence on Important Life Decisions: Homeless People in Pula], *Ljetopis socijalnog rada* 28(1) pp.273-299.

Krueger, R.A. (1994) *Focus Groups: A Practical Guide for Applied Research* (2nd Ed.) (Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications).

Lisbon Declaration (2021) Lisbon Declaration on the European Platform on Combatting Homelessness. Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/social/BlobServlet?docId=24120andlangId=en>.

Manning, R.M. and Greenwood, R.M. (2019) Understanding Innovation in Homeless Service Provision: A Study of Frontline Providers' Values-Readiness for Change, *Administration and Policy in Mental Health and Mental Health Services Research* 46(5) pp.649-659.

Ministry of Justice and Public Administration, Croatia (2022) Register of Associations. Available at: <https://mpu.gov.hr/register-of-associations/25235>.

Nelson, G., Aubry, T., Estecahandy, P., Laval, C., O'Sullivan, E., Shinn, M., and Tsemberis, S. (2021) How Social Science Can Influence Homelessness Policy: Experiences from Europe, Canada, and the United States. Part I – Problem and Solutions, *European Journal of Homelessness* 15(1) pp.131-158.

O'Sullivan, E. (2022) Key Elements in Homelessness Strategies to End Homelessness by 2030: A Discussion Paper, European Platform on Combatting Homelessness (Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union).

Paidakaki, A. and Lang, R. (2021) Uncovering Social Sustainability in Housing Systems Through the Lens of Institutional Capital: A Study of Two Housing Alliances in Vienna, Austria, *Sustainability* (Switzerland) 13(17) p.9726.

Pleace, N. (2016) *Housing First Guide Europe* (Brussels: FEANTSA).

Pleace, N., Baptista, I., Benjaminsen, L., and Busch-Geertsema, V. (2018) *Homelessness Services in Europe – Comparative Studies on Homelessness* (Brussels: European Observatory on Homelessness).

Renoir, M. and Guttentag, M. (2018) *Facilitating Financial Sustainability. Understanding the Drivers of CSO Financial Sustainability* (London: LINC).

Robić, N.G. (2017) Dvadeset godina beskućništva u Hrvatskoj (1991. – 2011.) te mogućnosti za istraživanja povijesti beskućništva [Twenty years of homelessness in Croatia (1991 – 2011) and opportunities for research into the history of homelessness], *Revija Za Socijalnu Politiku* 24(2) pp.219-237.

Robson, C. (2002) *Real World Research: A Resource for Social Scientists and Practitioner-Researchers* (2nd Ed.) (Oxford: Blackwell Publishers Ltd).

Salamon, L. M. and Sokolowski, S. W. (2006). Second commentary on Heinrich: Studying civil society across the world. *Journal of Civil Society*, 2(1): 85-88

Skoko, B. and Benković, V. (2009) Znanstvena metoda fokus grupa – mogućnosti i načini primjene [Scientific Method Focus Group – Possibilities and Applications], *Politička misao* 46(3) pp.217-236.

Social Welfare Act 18/22 (2024) Zakon o socijalnoj skrbi 18/22 [Social Welfare Act 18/22]. Available at: <https://www.zakon.hr/z/222/Zakon-o-socijalnoj-skrbi>.

Šikić-Mičanović, L. (2023) Pathways to Homelessness and Social Exclusion: Research with Rough Sleepers in Croatia, *Stud. ethnol. Croat.* 35 pp.95-114.

Šikić-Mičanović, L. and Geiger Zeman, M. (2011) Rodne asimetrije i beskućništvo u Hrvatskoj [Gender Asymmetries and Homelessness in Croatia] (Zagreb: Institut društvenih znanosti Ivo Pilar, Vlada Republike Hrvatske, Ured za ravnopravnost spolova).

Šikić-Mičanović, L., Sakić, S., and Stelko, S. (2020) Kvaliteta usluga za beskućnike: prikaz trenutnog stanja i izazova u Hrvatskoj [Quality of Services for the Homeless: An Overview Current Situation and Challenges in Croatia], *Rev. soc. polit.* 27(3) pp.233-248.

Šoštarić, M. (2013) Homelessness in the Republic of Croatia: A Review of the Social Welfare System for Homeless People, *European Journal of Homelessness* 7(2) pp.287-301.

Tipple, G. and Speak, S. (2005) Tipple and Speak, Definitions of Homelessness in Developing Countries, *Habitat International* 29(2) pp.337-352.

Tsemberis, S. (2010) *Housing First: The Pathways Model to End Homelessness for People with Mental Illness and Addiction Manual* (Center City: Hazelden).

United Nations (UN) (2009) Enumeration of Homeless People (New York City: United Nations Economic and Social Council). Available at <https://unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/stats/documents/ece/ces/ge.41/2009/7.e.pdf>.

United Nations Global Compact (UNGC) (2022) Social Sustainability. Available at: <https://www.unglobalcompact.org/what-is-gc/our-work/social>.

USAID (2020) 2020 Civil Society Organization Sustainability Index Central and Eastern Europe and Eurasia 24th Edition – September 2021 (Washington D.C.: USAID).

West Africa Civil Society Institute (WACSI) (2022) Key Achievements. Available at: <https://wacsi.org/km-achievements/>.

Keywords: Homeless, Service Providers, Social Service, Civil Organisations, Sustainability

Panagidis, A., & Roussou, E. (2024) *Clientelism and infrastructural gaps in Southern Europe: The implications on housing and urban governance. Proceedings of the RE-DWELL Conference “Sustainable Living, Affordable Homes”, 16 May 2024, Barcelona, Spain.*

Abstract: Unaffordable and unsustainable housing is widely regarded as a harsh side-effect of the failure of pro-market policies. The issue is often used to articulate the flaws of dominant responses through political-economic ties that tend to reconstruct new cases of dispossession (Dikeç, 2007). When exploring the ongoing housing crisis, the dominant narratives of urgent fixes to the problem enabled governments face when enacting policy without questioning the insecure foundations of uneven spatial development (Heslop & Ormerod, 2020).

The inability of the state to protect disenfranchised groups, and the deficiencies of public-private neoliberal models of urban governance have contributed to rising levels of distrust in governance institutions. Adding to the widely regarded problem of the global affordable housing gap (Reid, 2023), the infrastructural gap in the Mediterranean region is identified by the deficits (gaps) in the infrastructures required to mitigate overlapping challenges of sustainable development in general (Dalakoglou, 2016). Moreover, the growing role of the private sector in urban governance and public-private alliances, promoting urban entrepreneurialism (Phelps & Miao, 2020), provide private actors with speculative interests greater degrees of influence in the development of urban infrastructure than society as a whole. A continuation of neoliberal urban planning places real barriers to meaningful citizen participation in the development of sustainable cities.

References:

Aretaki, M. (2013, April 5). The Mall Athens: Σκάνδαλο όπως και αν το δεις [The Mall Athens: No matter how you look at it, it's a scandal]. The Press Project. Retrieved from <https://thepressproject.gr/the-mall-athens-skandalo-opos-kai-an-to-deis/>

Dalakoglou, D. (2016). Infrastructural gap: Commons, state and anthropology. *City*, 20(6), 822–831. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13604813.2016.1241524>

Dikeç, M. (2007). *Badlands of the Republic: Space, Politics and Urban Policy*. Blackwell Publishing. Doi:10.1002/9780470712788

DW News. (2017, July 20). Mafia Capitale: Rome racket convicted. Retrieved from <https://www.dw.com/en/mafia-capitale-rome-court-convicts-racket-leaders-who-extorted-city-officials/a-39774910>

Efimerida ton Sidakton. (2021, March 24). Τρία σκάνδαλα σε συσκευασία ενός [Three scandals packaged as one]. Retrieved from https://www.efsyn.gr/politiki/i-apopsi-tis-efsyn/286895_tria-skandala-se-syskeyasia-enos

Ferrera, M. (1996). The “Southern Model” of Welfare in Social Europe. *Journal of European Social Policy*, 6(1), 17-37. <https://doi.org/10.1177/095892879600600102>

Fung, A. (2015). Putting the Public Back into Governance: The Challenges of Citizen Participation and Its Future. *Public Administration Review*, 75(4), 513–522. doi:10.1111/puar.12361

Heslop, J., & Ormerod, E. (2020). The Politics of Crisis: Deconstructing the Dominant Narratives of the Housing Crisis. *Antipode*, 52(1), 145–163. <https://doi.org/10.1111/anti.12585>

Lamda Development. (n.d.). The Hellinikon. Retrieved from <https://www.lamdadev.com/en/investment-portfolio/the-hellinikon.html>

Lawhon, M., Nilsson, D., Silver, J., Ernstson, H., & Lwasa, S. (2018). Thinking through heterogeneous infrastructure configurations. *Urban Studies*, 55(4), 720–732. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0042098017720149>

Lawson, J., Denham, T., Dodson, J., Flanagan, K., Jacobs, K., Martin, C., Van Den Nouwelant, R., Pawson, H., & Troy, L. (2019). Social housing as infrastructure: Rationale, prioritisation and investment pathway. In *AHURI Final Report* (Issue 315). <https://doi.org/10.18408/ahuri-5314001>

Lemanski, C. (2020). Viewpoint infrastructural citizenship: (de)constructing state-society relations. *International Development Planning Review*, 42(2), 115–125. <https://doi.org/10.3828/idpr.2019.39>

Loeffler, E., & Bovaird, T. (2017). From Participation to Co-production: Widening and Deepening the Contributions of Citizens to Public Services and Outcomes. In E. Ongaro, S. Van Thiel (Eds.), *The Palgrave Handbook of Public Administration and Management in Europe*, 403–423. doi:10.1057/978-1-137-55269-3_21

Maloutas, T., Siatitsa, D., Balampanidis, D. (2020). Access to Housing and Social Inclusion in a Post-Crisis Era: Contextualizing Recent Trends in the City of Athens. *Social Inclusion*, 8(3), 5–15. doi:10.17645/si.v8i3.2778

Paidakaki, A. (2021). Social Innovation in the Times of a European Twofold Refugee-Housing Crisis . Evidence from the Homelessness Sector. *European Journal of Homelessness*, 15(1), 24.

Phelps, N. A., & Miao, J. T. (2020). Varieties of urban entrepreneurialism. *Dialogues in Human Geography*, 10(3), 304–321. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2043820619890438>

Ponce, J. (2010). Affordable housing as urban infrastructure: A comparative study from a European perspective. *The Urban Lawyer*, 42(4), 223-245.

Power, E. R., & Mee, K. J. (2020). Housing: an infrastructure of care. *Housing Studies*, 35(3), 484–505. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02673037.2019.1612038>

Reid, A. (2023). Closing the Affordable Housing Gap: Identifying the Barriers Hindering the Sustainable Design and Construction of Affordable Homes. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(11). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15118754>

Savini, F., & Bertolini, L. (2019). Urban experimentation as a politics of niches. *Environment and Planning A*, 51(4), 831–848. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0308518X19826085>

Savva, G. (2014, February 14). Ατιμώρητες εταιρείες που βάσει απόφασης Δικαστηρίου είχαν εμπλοκή στην υπόθεση ΣΑΠΑ, λέχθηκε στην Επ. Θεσμών. CNA. <https://www.cna.org.cy/article/6231885/atimorites-etaireies-poy-vasei-apofasis-dikastiriou-eichan-ebloki-stin-ypothesi-sapa-lechthike-stin-ep-thesmon>

Swenson, K. (2017, July 21). The last king of Rome: How a one-eyed gangster conned the Italian capital into a debt crisis. *The Washington Post*. Retrieved from <https://www.washingtonpost.com/news/morning-mix/wp/2017/07/21/the-last-king-of-rome-how-a-one-eyed-gangster-conned-the-italian-capital-into-a-debt-crisis/>

The Ellinikon. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://theellinikon.com.gr/en/about-us/the-ellinikon/>

The Press Project. (2020, February 2). Με τη σφραγίδα του ΣτΕ νομμο το μέχρι πρότινος αυθαίρετο «The Mall Athens» [By order from the national assembly The Mall Athens gains legal status]. Retrieved from

<https://thepressproject.gr/me-ti-sfragida-tou-ste-nomimo-to-mechri-protinis-afthereto-the-mall-athens/>

The Press Project. (2021, June 29). «Υφαρπαγή δημόσιας περιουσίας» και «παράδοση του Ελληνικού χωρίς προϋποθέσεις στη Lamda» [“Embezzlement of public property” and “unconditional delivery of Ellinikon to Lamda”]. Retrieved from <https://thepressproject.gr/yfarpagi-dimosias-periousias-kai-paradosi-tou-ellinikou-choris-proypotheseis-sti-lamda/>

Tondo, L. (2023, November 20). More than 200 mobsters convicted in Italian mafia maxi-trial. The Guardian. Retrieved from <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2023/nov/20/more-than-200-mobsters-convicted-in-italian-mafia-maxi-trial>

TVXS. (2009, May 7). Mall: "Το μεγαλύτερο αυθαίρετο της Ευρώπης" [Mall: "The largest illegal structure in Europe"]. Retrieved from <https://tvxs.gr/news/ellada/mall-to-megalytero-aythaireto-tis-eyropis/>

Keywords: Clientelism, Southern Europe, Infrastructure, Participation

Pappa, A., & Paio, A. (2023). *The role of commons-oriented policies in the transformation of urban governance: The case of the participatory budget BIP/ZIP in Lisbon*. In 2nd Conference on Participatory Design. Transforming the City: Public Space & Environment, Inequalities & Democracy. Athens, Greece.

Abstract: This study is part of an ongoing PhD research that explores the significance of urban commons in the social and urban sustainability of urban neighbourhoods. This part focuses on the role of commons-oriented local strategies in urban regeneration, in transforming the urban governance through enabling local organisations and community groups, especially the most disadvantaged, to participate in local decision-making processes. The research is situated in Lisbon and the participatory budget program of BIP/ZIP.

References:

Quintuple helix | LabGov. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://labgov.city/tag/quintuple-helix/>

Allegretti, G., & Hartz-Karp, J. (2017). Participatory budgeting: A methodological approach to address sustainability challenges. *Methods for Sustainability Research*, 203–216.

Crespo, J. L., & Caetano, L. (2021). BIP/ZIP program: Intervention in the neighborhoods and priority areas in Lisbon. *Urban Maestro, New Governance Strategies for Urban Design*.

Keywords: Urban Governance, Participatory Budget, Neighbourhoods

Roussou, E., Ricchiardi, A. (2024). *Enclaves of commoning across the divide: self-organised spaces against divisions*. In AESOP Symposium: “Constructing Peace through Public Space: What publics? Whose commons?”. Nicosia, Cyprus.

Abstract: Contemporary Nicosia is characterised by overlapping layers of division. The rising neoliberalisation resulting in intensified touristification and commodification of resources, paired with the tangible division between north and south, and the limited social safety nets for incoming migrants and refugees, widen the socio-economic gaps among different communities. This situation also fuels an increasingly precarious terrain of social and spatial enclosures for urban dwellers to navigate. Against this backdrop, there is a proliferation of bottom-up, self-organised, horizontally managed, non-commercial spaces that operate in the margins of everyday life in Nicosia across the divide. While

these enclaves of “commoning” may vary in terms of scope of activities, members or target audience, they all share similar ideological positioning and socio-ecological values, thus forming a network of alternative forms of encounters. This work explores the factors enabling the emergence of these commons and the ways in which they operate to overcome the various layers of division. By adopting a spatial mapping and ethnographic approach, we look into both spatialities and processes, exploring motivations, intents, actions/activities and methods towards self-sustenance and intercommunal outreach. The exploration highlights commoning practices and discusses their potential in creating bridges across divisions.

Keywords: Commoning, Nicosia, Self-Organised, Spatial Mapping

Tzika, Z. (2024). *Housing as Community Infrastructure: Case Study Analysis of Catalonia’s Grant-of-Use Cooperative Housing*. Presented at the European Network for Housing Research (ENHR) Conference 2024, Delft, the Netherlands.

Abstract: Over the last decades, Barcelona has witnessed the emergence of the grant-of-use cooperative housing model, driven by the socio-political aftermath of the financial crisis. Originating from grassroots efforts, the movement addresses the pressing demand for affordable and adequate housing while responding to the evolving demographics and lifestyles of the population. Progressively the model is opening up geographically to the rest of Catalonia, but also in terms of diversity and inclusion. Among the projects we recognise differences reflecting variations in group values and motivations (such as affordability, neighbourhood revitalization, ecological concerns, and gender perspectives), demographic compositions (age, gender, number of units), land access and tenure types (collective property, social housing), building characteristics (construction systems, typologies), and community living arrangements (private and communal areas, activities). This study aims to shed light on how these groups pursue their housing objectives by analysing the processes of developing the projects, employing a conceptual framework rooted in the capability approach. After a quantitative analysis of 66 ongoing projects, six representative cases were selected for comparison. The projects are selected based on their diversity in relation to their location, their governance and management process, and the architectural result. By comparing the case studies through the conceptual framework of the capabilities approach, we look at the processes, relationships and practices that each group followed in order to understand the conditions that make possible such a project. To do that we look at the motivations, the resources, the conversion factors, choices and conflicts and the final outcomes.

References:

- Alkire, S. (2002). *Valuing Freedoms: Sen’s Capability Approach and Poverty Reduction*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/0199245797.001.0001>
- Biggeri, M., Ferrannini, A., & Arciprete, C. (2018). Local Communities and Capability Evolution: The Core of Human Development Processes. *Journal of Human Development and Capabilities*, 19(2), 126–146. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19452829.2017.1411896>
- Cabré, E., & Andrés, A. (2018). La Borda: a case study on the implementation of cooperative housing in Catalonia. *International Journal of Housing Policy*, 18(3), 412–432. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19491247.2017.1331591>
- Clapham, D., Foye, C., & Blyth, R. (2019). How should we evaluate housing outcomes?
- Clark, D. A., Biggeri, M., & Frediani, A. A. (Eds.). (2019). *The Capability Approach, Empowerment and Participation. Concepts, Methods and Applications*. Springer.
- Coates, D., Anand, P., & Norris, M. (2015). *A Capabilities Approach to Housing and Quality of Life: The Evidence from Germany (78; Open Discussion Papers in Economics)*.

- Corbin, J., & Strauss, A. (1998). *Basics of qualitative research: Techniques and procedures for developing grounded theory*. (2nd edition). Sage publications.
- Czischke, D., Carriou, C., & Lang, R. (2020). Collaborative Housing in Europe: Conceptualizing the Field. *Housing, Theory and Society*, 37(1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14036096.2020.1703611>
- Etxezarreta, A., Merino, S., Cano, G., Dol, K., & Hoekstra, J. (2019). The emergence of housing cooperatives in Spain. In *Affordable housing governance and finance: innovations, partnerships and comparative perspectives* (pp. 25–40).
- Frediani, A. A. (2015). “Participatory Capabilities” in *Development Practice*. www.bartlett.ucl.ac.uk/dpu
- Frediani, A. A. (2019). Participatory Research Methods and the Capability Approach: Researching the Housing Dimensions of Squatter Upgrading Initiatives in Salvador da Bahia, Brazil. In *The Capability Approach, Empowerment and Participation* (pp. 261–288). Palgrave Macmillan UK. https://doi.org/10.1057/978-1-137-35230-9_10
- Frediani, A., & Boano, C. (2012). Processes for Just Products: The Capability Space of Participatory Design. In I. Oosterlaken & J. van den Hoven (Eds.), *The Capability Approach, Technology and Design*. Springer.
- Fromm, D. (1991). *Collaborative communities : cohousing, central living, and other new forms of housing with shared facilities*. Van Nostrand Reinhold.
- Fromm, D. (2012). Seeding Community: Collaborative housing as a strategy for social and neighbourhood repair. *Built Environment*, 38(3), 364–394. <https://doi.org/10.2148/BENV.38.3.364>
- Groat, L., & Wang, D. (2013). *Architectural research methods*. Wiley.
- Haffner, M., & Elsinga, M. (2019). Housing Deprivation Unravelling: Application of the Capability Approach. *European Journal of Homelessness*, 13(1).
- Hansen, J. (2015). Locating capabilities in the built environment: socio-spatial products and processes and the capability approach. In *The Capability Approach in Development Planning and Urban Design* (pp. 77–98). www.bartlett.ucl.ac.uk/dpu
- Harvey, D. (2008). *Rebel Cities*. Verso.
- Hayden, D. (1981). *The Grand Domestic Revolution. A History of Feminist Designs for American Homes, Neighborhoods and Cities*. MIT Press.
- Kimhur, B. (2020). How to Apply the Capability Approach to Housing Policy? Concepts, Theories and Challenges. *Housing, Theory and Society*, 37(3), 257–277. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14036096.2019.1706630>
- Kleine, D. (2010). ICT4What?-Using the Choice Framework to operationalise the Capability Approach to Development. *Journal of International Development*, 22, 674–692.
- Landman, K. (2010). Gating the streets in South Africa. In A. Madanipour (Ed.), *Whose Public Space? International case studies in Urban Design and Development*. Routledge.
- Lang, R., Carriou, C., & Czischke, D. (2018). Collaborative Housing Research (1990–2017): A Systematic Review and Thematic Analysis of the Field. *Housing, Theory and Society*, 37(1), 10–39. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14036096.2018.1536077>
- Lefebvre, H. (1968). *Le Droit À La Ville*. Anthropos.
- Lefebvre, H. (1991). *The production of space*. Blackwell.

Martinez-Vargas, C., Walker, M., Melis Cin, F., & Boni, A. (2022). A Capabilitarian Participatory Paradigm: Methods, Methodologies and Cosmological Issues and Possibilities. *Journal of Human Development and Capabilities*, 23(1), 8–29. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19452829.2021.2013173>

Nussbaum, M. (2011). *Creating Capabilities: The Human Development Approach*. Harvard University Press.

Power, E. R., & Mee, K. J. (2019). Housing: an infrastructure of care. *Housing Studies*, 35(3), 484–505. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02673037.2019.1612038>

Robeyns, I. (2005). The Capability Approach: a theoretical survey. *Journal of Human Development*, 6(1), 93–117. <https://doi.org/10.1080/146498805200034266>

Salama, I. (2019). Social Production of Habitat: The Emergence of a Paradigm Shift in the Making of Cities. In J. Hawley & D. Roussopoulos (Eds.), *Villages in Cities: Community Land Ownership, Cooperative Housing, and the Milton Parc Story* (pp. 122–129).

Schmid, S. (2019). *A History of Collective Living Forms of Shared Housing*. Birkhäuser.

Sen, A. (1999). *Development as Freedom*. Oxford University Press.

Tavory, I., & Timmermans, S. (2014). *Abductive Analysis: Theorizing Qualitative Research*. University of Chicago Press.

Tummers, L. (2015). Understanding co-housing from a planning perspective: Why and how? *Urban Research and Practice*, 8(1), 64–78. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17535069.2015.1011427>

Tummers, L. (2016). The re-emergence of self-managed co-housing in Europe: A critical review of co-housing research. *Urban Studies*, 53(10), 2023–2040. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0042098015586696>

Turner, J. (1976a). *Housing by people*. Marion Boyars.

Turner, J. (1976b). *Housing By People: Towards Autonomy in Building Environments*. Pantheon Books.

Viskovic Rojs, D., Hawlina, M., Gračner, B., & Ramšak, R. (2020). Review of the Participatory and Community-Based Approach in the Housing Cooperative Sector. In J. Nared & D. Bole (Eds.), *Participatory Research and Planning in Practice*. The Urban Book Series. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-28014-7_6

Williams, J. (2005). Designing neighbourhoods for social interaction: The case of cohousing. *Journal of Urban Design*, 10(2), 195–227. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13574800500086998>

Yin, R. K. (2018). *Case Study Research and Applications*. Design and methods (6th edition). SAGE.

Keywords: Affordable, Sustainable, Community-Led, Collaborative, Capability Approach

Tzika, Z., Sentieri, C. & Martinez, A. (2024) Key topics and challenges for creating community-led, inclusive and sustainable housing: Catalonia's grant-of-use cooperative housing in Catalonia. Proceedings of the RE-DWELL Conference "Sustainable Living, Affordable Homes", 16 May 2024, Barcelona, Spain.

Abstract: Over the last two decades, Barcelona has witnessed the emergence of a cooperative housing movement, known as the grant-of-use model, spurred by the socio-political context following the global financial crisis. This movement is part of a broader trend seen across Europe (Czischke et al., 2020; Tummers, 2016). Originating from grassroots efforts, it primarily seeks to address the pressing demand for affordable and adequate housing, while also responding to demographic shifts and the evolving housing needs within the population (Cabré & Andrés, 2018). The model has spread from the

city of Barcelona to the rest of the territory, reaching smaller cities and rural areas (Tzika et al., 2023). The main characteristic of the grant-of-use cooperatives is the long-term right to use a home rather than own it, promoting non-speculative housing and positioning it as a collective endeavour. Residents actively participate in decision-making processes, reinforcing this model's collaborative nature (Avilla-Royo et al., 2021; Sostre Civic, 2017). By reconsidering the architectural typologies of housing through the incorporation of communal spaces and facilities, while parallelly creating more communal ways of living, these communities reshape the concept of dwelling and transform the social dynamics among residents (Lacol et al., 2018). Given the diverse project values and aims of the groups (affordability, neighbourhood revitalisation, ecological considerations, gender perspective), their demographic composition (age, gender, number of units), land access and tenure type (collective property, social housing), building characteristics (construction system, typology, rehabilitation), and community living (private and communal areas, activities), the approaches of each group and their collaboration with external entities can vary significantly (Lang et al., 2020). This article aims to identify the key challenges shaping the cooperative housing landscape in Catalonia and explore how different groups navigate these challenges.

References:

- Avilla-Royo, R., Jacoby, S., & Bilbao, I. (2021). The building as a home: Housing cooperatives in Barcelona. *Buildings*, 11(4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/BUILDINGS11040137>
- Bresson, S., & Labit, A. (2020). How Does Collaborative Housing Address the Issue of Social Inclusion? A French Perspective. *Housing, Theory and Society*, 37(1), 118–138. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14036096.2019.1671488>
- Brysch, S. L., & Czischke, D. (2021). Affordability through design: the role of building costs in collaborative housing. *Housing Studies*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02673037.2021.2009778>
- Cabre, E., & Andres, A. (2018). La Borda: a case study on the implementation of cooperative housing in Catalonia. *International Journal of Housing Policy*, 18(3), 412–432. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19491247.2017.1331591>
- Czischke, D., Carriou, C., & Lang, R. (2020). Collaborative Housing in Europe: Conceptualizing the Field. *Housing, Theory and Society*, 37(1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14036096.2020.1703611>
- Ferreri, M., & Vidal, L. (2021). Public-cooperative policy mechanisms for housing commons. *International Journal of Housing Policy*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19491247.2021.1877888>
- Fraser, N. (2016). Contradictions of Capital and Care. *New Left Review*, 100.
- Fromm, D. (2012). Seeding Community: Collaborative housing as a strategy for social and neighbourhood repair. *Built Environment*, 38(3), 364–394. <https://doi.org/10.2148/BENV.38.3.364>
- Groat, L., & Wang, D. (2013). *Architectural research methods*. Wiley.
- Huisman, C., & Czischke, D. (2023). Between Self-organization and Formal Participation: Increasing Tenants' Influence through Self-management?—A Dutch Case-study. *Housing, Theory and Society*, 40(2), 219–237. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14036096.2022.2150681>
- Jarvis, H. (2011). Saving space, sharing time: Integrated infrastructures of daily life in cohousing. *Environment and Planning A*, 43(3), 560–577. <https://doi.org/10.1068/a43296>
- Jarvis, H. (2015). Community-led housing and “Slow” opposition to corporate development: Citizen participation as common ground? *Geography Compass*, 9(4), 202–213. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gec3.12206>
- Jupp, E., Bowlby, S., Franklin, J., & Hall, S. M. (2019). *The new politics of home: Housing, Gender and Care in Times of Crisis* (1st ed.). Bristol University Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctvighvp4>

Lacol, La Ciutat Invisible, & La Dinamo Fundació. (2018). Habitar en comunidad : la vivienda cooperativa en cesión de uso. Catarata.

Lang, R., Chatterton, P., & Mullins, D. (2020). Grassroots innovations in community-led housing in England: the role and evolution of intermediaries. *International Journal of Urban Sustainable Development*, 12(1), 52–72. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19463138.2019.1663525>

Sørvoll, J., & Bengtsson, B. (2018). The Pyrrhic victory of civil society housing? Co-operative housing in Sweden and Norway. *International Journal of Housing Policy*, 18(1), 124–142. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616718.2016.1162078>

Sostre Civic. (2017). Les claus de l'habitatge cooperatiu en cessió d'ús. https://sostrecivic.coop/biblio/biblio_5.pdf

Tavory, I., & Timmermans, S. (2014). *Abductive Analysis: Theorizing Qualitative Research*. University of Chicago Press.

Tummers, L. (2016). The re-emergence of self-managed co-housing in Europe: A critical review of co-housing research. *Urban Studies*, 53(10), 2023–2040. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0042098015586696>

Tzika, Z., Sentieri, C., & Martínez, A. (2023). Towards collective forms of dwelling: the grant-of-use housing cooperatives in Catalonia. *Revista de Arquitectura*, 28(45), 54–75. <https://doi.org/10.5354/0719-5427.2023.70003>

Williams, J. (2005). Designing neighbourhoods for social interaction: The case of cohousing. *Journal of Urban Design*, 10(2), 195–227. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13574800500086998>

Yin, R. K. (2018). *Case Study Research and Applications. Design and methods (6th edition)*. SAGE.

Keywords: Collaborative Housing, Participation, Capability Approach, Inclusion

Tzika, Z., & Sentieri, C. (accepted, 2024). *Housing as Community Infrastructure: Analysis of Senior Cooperative Housing Using the Capability Approach*. *Journal of Housing and the Built Environment*.

Abstract: Over the last decade, Barcelona has witnessed the emergence of a cooperative housing movement, known as the grant-of-use model. The phenomenon was spurred by the socio-political context following the global financial crisis. The movement appeared from the bottom up, primarily to address the pressing demand for affordable and adequate housing and to respond to demographic shifts and the evolving housing needs of the population. The projects advocate for non-speculative housing, positioning it as a collective endeavour. Residents actively participate in decision-making, suggesting more communal ways of living, and exploring new arrangements of private and common spaces within housing. These projects reconsider the concept of dwelling by reimagining the architecture of housing and proposing alternative typologies that incorporate shared spaces and facilities. Furthermore, they reconsider the 'social architecture', emphasizing the importance of care within communities. Senior cooperative housing has appeared as such a case within Barcelona's broader cooperative housing context, exemplifying a paradigm shift for communities of adults over 55 years old. This article seeks to analyse the process through which a senior cooperative housing project in Barcelona navigates the challenges and opportunities in achieving its spatial and relational housing outcomes. Employing the Capability Approach as a conceptual framework, this study identifies the key factors that facilitated and hindered the group's progress. Through a case study analysis, the paper explores how the community's capabilities were developed, the critical junctures in the process, and the implications for the broader landscape of housing provision. The findings aim to shed light on the

complexities of collective housing initiatives and contribute to a deeper understanding of community-led housing models.

References:

Alexander, C., Ishikawa, S., & Silverstein, M. (1977). *A Pattern Language Towns, Buildings, Construction*. Oxford University Press.

Alkire, S. (2002). *Valuing Freedoms: Sen's Capability Approach and Poverty Reduction*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/0199245797.001.0001>

Allen, J., Barlow, J., Leal, J., Maloutas, T., & Padovani, L. (2008). *Housing and Welfare in Southern Europe*. *Housing and Welfare in Southern Europe*, 1–228. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470757536>

Amin, A. (2014). *Lively Infrastructure*. *Theory, Culture & Society*, 31(8), 137–161. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0263276414548490>

Arnold, P., & Quintas, N. (2020). *Global study: Community-Led Housing in the COVID-19 context*.

Arnstein, S. (1969). *A Ladder Of Citizen Participation*. *Journal of the American Planning Association*, 35(4), 216–224.

Attia, M., & Edge, J. (2017). *Be(com)ing a reflexive researcher: a developmental approach to research methodology*. *Open Review of Educational Research*, 4(1), 33–45. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23265507.2017.1300068>

Avilla-Royo, R., Jacoby, S., & Bilbao, I. (2021). *The building as a home: Housing cooperatives in Barcelona*. *Buildings*, 11(4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/BUILDINGS11040137>

Baldwin, C., Dendle, K., & McKinlay, A. (2019). *Initiating Senior Co-Housing: People, Place, and Long-Term Security*. *Journal of Housing for the Elderly*, 33(4), 358–381. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02763893.2019.1583152>

Biggeri, M., Ferrannini, A., & Arciprete, C. (2018). *Local Communities and Capability Evolution: The Core of Human Development Processes*. *Journal of Human Development and Capabilities*, 19(2), 126–146. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19452829.2017.1411896>

Bruun, M. H. (2018). *The financialization of Danish cooperatives and the debasement of a collective housing good*. *Critique of Anthropology*, 38(2), 140–155. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0308275X18761960>

Brysch, S. L., & Czischke, D. (2021). *Affordability through design: the role of building costs in collaborative housing*. *Housing Studies*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02673037.2021.2009778>

Cabré, E., & Andrés, A. (2018). *La Borda: a case study on the implementation of cooperative housing in Catalonia*. *International Journal of Housing Policy*, 18(3), 412–432. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19491247.2017.1331591>

Can 70, López, D., & Farré, L. (2019). *Cures en la convivència de persones grans*. 6th guide of Sostre Civic.

Chatterton, P. (2013). *Towards an agenda for post-carbon cities: Lessons from lilac, the UK's first ecological, affordable cohousing community*. *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research*, 37(5), 1654–1674. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2427.12009>

Clapham, D., Foye, C., & Blyth, R. (2019). *How should we evaluate housing outcomes?*

Clark, D. A., Biggeri, M., & Frediani, A. A. (Eds.). (2019). *The Capability Approach, Empowerment and Participation. Concepts, Methods and Applications*. Springer.

Coates, D., Anand, P., & Norris, M. (2015). *A Capabilities Approach to Housing and Quality of Life: The Evidence from Germany (78; Open Discussion Papers in Economics)*.

Col·lectiu Punt6. (2023). Xarxa comunitària de cures.

Comas d' Argemir, D. (2017). Cuidados, género y ciudad en la gestión de la vida cotidiana. In *La erosión del espacio público en la ciudad neoliberal* (p. 873).

Corbin, J., & Strauss, A. (1998). *Basics of qualitative research: Techniques and procedures for developing grounded theory*. (2nd edition). Sage Publications.

Czischke, D., Carriou, C., & Lang, R. (2020). Collaborative Housing in Europe: Conceptualizing the Field. *Housing, Theory and Society*, 37(1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14036096.2020.1703611>

Devlin, P., Douglas, R., & Reynolds, T. (2015). Collaborative design of older women's co-housing. *Working with Older People*, 19(4), 188–194. <https://doi.org/10.1108/WWOP-08-2015-0018>

Droste, C. (2015). German co-housing: An opportunity for municipalities to foster socially inclusive urban development? *Urban Research and Practice*, 8(1), 79–92. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17535069.2015.1011428>

Durrett, C. (2009). *The senior cohousing handbook: a community approach to independent living*. New Society Publishers. <https://archive.org/details/seniorcohousingh0000durr>

Ehlenz, M. M. (2018). Making Home More Affordable: Community Land Trusts Adopting Cooperative Ownership Models to Expand Affordable Housing. *Journal of Community Practice*, 26(3), 283–307. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10705422.2018.1477082>

Etxezarreta, A., Merino, S., Cano, G., Dol, K., & Hoekstra, J. (2019). The emergence of housing cooperatives in Spain. In *Affordable housing governance and finance: innovations, partnerships and comparative perspectives* (pp. 25–40).

Fernández, A., & Miró, I. (2016). *L' economia social i solidària a Barcelona*.

Fernández Arrigoitia, M., Ferreri, M., Hudson, J., Scanlon, K., & West, K. (2023). Toward a feminist housing commons? Conceptualising care - (as) - work in collaborative housing. *Housing, Theory and Society*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14036096.2023.2247414>

Fernández Arrigoitia, M., West, K., & Peace, S. (2018). Towards Critical Intersections of Ageing, Housing and Well-Being. *Home Cultures*, 209–221. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17406315.2019.1690274>

Ferreri, M., & Vidal, L. (2021). Public-cooperative policy mechanisms for housing commons. *International Journal of Housing Policy*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19491247.2021.1877888>

Frediani, A. A. (2015). "Participatory Capabilities" in *Development Practice*. www.bartlett.ucl.ac.uk/dpu

Frediani, A. A. (2021). *Cities for Human Development*. In *Cities for Human Development*. PRACTICAL ACTION PUBLISHING. <https://doi.org/10.3362/9781788531504>

Fromm, D. (1991). *Collaborative communities: cohousing, central living, and other new forms of housing with shared facilities*. Van Nostrand Reinhold.

Fromm, D. (2012). Seeding Community: Collaborative housing as a strategy for social and neighbourhood repair. *Built Environment*, 38(3), 364–394. <https://doi.org/10.2148/BENV.38.3.364>

García-Lamarca, M. (2023). Housing and Welfare in Catalonia, Spain. In M. Grander & M. Stephens (Eds.), *The Routledge handbook of housing and welfare*. Routledge.

Girbés-Peco, S., Foraster, M. J., Mara, L. C., & Morlà-Folch, T. (2020). The role of the democratic organization in the La borda housing cooperative in Spain. *Habitat International*, 102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.HABITATINT.2020.102208>

Glass, A. P. (2013). Lessons Learned From a New Elder Cohousing Community. *Journal of Housing for the Elderly*, 27(4), 348–368. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02763893.2013.813426>

- Glass, A. P. (2019). Sense of community, loneliness, and satisfaction in five elder cohousing neighborhoods. *Journal of Women and Aging*, 32(1), 3–27. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08952841.2019.1681888>
- Groat, L., & Wang, D. (2013). *Architectural research methods*. Wiley.
- Haffner, M., & Elsinga, M. (2019). Housing Deprivation Unravelling: Application of the Capability Approach. *European Journal of Homelessness*, 13(1).
- Hayden, D. (1986). *Redesigning the American Dream: The Future of Housing, Work and Family Life*. Norton Professional Books.
- Hudson, J., Scanlon, K., Udagawa, C., Arrigoitia, M. F., Ferreri, M., & West, K. (2021). 'A Slow Build-Up of a History of Kindness': Exploring the Potential of Community-Led Housing in Alleviating Loneliness. *Sustainability*, 13(20), 11323. <https://doi.org/10.3390/SU132011323>
- Jarvis, H. (2011). Saving space, sharing time: Integrated infrastructures of daily life in cohousing. *Environment and Planning A*, 43(3), 560–577. <https://doi.org/10.1068/a43296>
- Jarvis, H. (2015). Community-led housing and “Slow” opposition to corporate development: Citizen participation as common ground? *Geography Compass*, 9(4), 202–213. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gec3.12206>
- Jarvis, H. (2019). Sharing, togetherness and intentional degrowth. *Progress in Human Geography*, 43(2), 256–275. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0309132517746519>
- Jupp, E., Bowlby, S., Franklin, J., & Hall, S. M. (2019). *The new politics of home: Housing, Gender and Care in Times of Crisis* (1st ed.). **Bristol University Press**. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctvjghvp4>
- Keller Garganté, C., & Ezquerro Samper, S. (2021). Viviendas colaborativas de personas mayores: democratizar el cuidado en la vejez. REVERSCO Revista de Estudios Cooperativos, 137.** <https://doi.org/10.5209/REVE.71867>
- Khatibi, M. (2022a).** A socio-spatial approach to the first legal hall dwelling setting in Switzerland: the case study of Hallenwohnen in Zurich. *Journal of Housing and the Built Environment*, 38(2), 979–998. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10901-022-09980-y>
- Khatibi, M. (2022b). Socio-spatial interactions of a cluster-house concept apartment in mehr als wohnen project in Zurich, Switzerland. *Frontiers of Architectural Research*, 11(2), 191–202. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foar.2021.10.002>
- Kimhur, B. (2020). How to Apply the Capability Approach to Housing Policy? Concepts, Theories and Challenges. *Housing, Theory and Society*, 37(3), 257–277. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14036096.2019.1706630>
- Labit, A. (2015). Self-managed co-housing in the context of an ageing population in Europe. **Urban Research & Practice**, 8(1), 32–45. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17535069.2015.1011425>
- Lacol, La Ciutat Invisible, & La Dinamo Fundación. (2018). Habitar en comunidad : la vivienda cooperativa en cesión de uso.** Catarata.
- Lang, R., Carriou, C., & Czischke, D. (2018). Collaborative Housing Research (1990–2017): A Systematic Review and Thematic Analysis of the Field. *Housing, Theory and Society*, 37(1), 10–39. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14036096.2018.1536077>
- Lang, R., Chatterton, P., & Mullins, D. (2020). Grassroots innovations in community-led housing in England: the role and evolution of intermediaries. *International Journal of Urban Sustainable Development*, 12(1), 52–72. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19463138.2019.1663525>
- Lefebvre, H. (1991). *The production of space*. Blackwell.

Leyva del Río, S. (2022). Conceptualising the commons as a relational triad: Lessons from the grant of use cooperative housing model in Barcelona. *Geoforum*, 136, 112–121.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2022.09.007>

López, D., & Estrada, M. (2016). ¿Cómo avanzan las dinámicas de senior cohousing en España?. *Edades En Transición. Envejecer En El Siglo XXI*, 21, 227–237.

Martinez-Vargas, C., Walker, M., Melis Cin, F., & Boni, A. (2022). A Capabilitarian Participatory Paradigm: Methods, Methodologies and Cosmological Issues and Possibilities. *Journal of Human Development and Capabilities*, 23(1), 8–29. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19452829.2021.2013173>

Mogollón García, I., & Fernández Cubero, A. (2016). **Arquitecturas del cuidado. Emakunde.**

Fraser, N. (2016). Contradictions of Capital and Care. *New Left Review*, 100.

Nussbaum, M. (2011). *Creating Capabilities: The Human Development Approach*. Harvard University Press.

Pareja-Eastaway, M., & Sánchez-Martínez, T. (2017). More social housing? A critical analysis of social housing provision in Spain. *Critical Housing Analysis*, 4(1), 124–131.

<https://doi.org/10.13060/23362839.2017.4.1.331>

Parera, Mireia. (2023). *Teixir comunitats : invitació per pensar la vida en comú*. Pollen Edicions.

Power, E. R., & Mee, K. J. (2019). Housing: an infrastructure of care. *Housing Studies*, 35(3), 484–505.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/02673037.2019.1612038>

Prytula, M., Rexroth, S., Lutz, M., & May, F. (2020). Cluster-Wohnungen für Baulich und Sozial Anpassungsfähige Wohnkonzepte einer Resilienten Stadtentwicklung. **Fraunhofer IRB Verlag.**

<https://www.fh-potsdam.de/forschung-transfer/projekte/cluster-wohnen>

Puplampu, V., Matthews, E., Puplampu, G., Gross, M., Pathak, S., & Peters, S. (2020). The Impact of Cohousing on Older Adults' Quality of Life. *Canadian Journal on Aging*, 39(3), 406–420.

<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0714980819000448>

Rapoport, A. (1995). A Critical Look at the Concept Home. In *The home: words, interpretations, meanings and environments*. (pp. 25–52).

Reyes, A., Novoa, A. M., Borrell, C., Carrere, J., Pérez, K., Gamboa, C., Daví, L., & Fernández, A. (2022). Living Together for a Better Life: The Impact of Cooperative Housing on Health and Quality of Life. *Buildings*, 12(12). <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings12122099>

Robeyns, I. (2005). The Capability Approach: a theoretical survey. *Journal of Human Development*, 6(1), 93–117. <https://doi.org/10.1080/146498805200034266>

Rojo-Perez, F., Rodriguez-Rodriguez, V., Molina-Martinez, M. A., Fernandez-Mayoralas, G., Sanchez-Gonzalez, D., Rojo-Abuin, J. M., Ayala, A., Rodriguez-Blazquez, C., Calderon-Larrañaga, A., Ribeiro, O., & Forjaz, M. J. (2022). Active ageing profiles among older adults in Spain: A Multivariate analysis based on SHARE study. *PLoS ONE*, 17(8 August). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0272549>

Scanlon, K., & Fernández Arrigoitia, M. (2015). Development of new cohousing: Lessons from a London scheme for the over-50s. *Urban Research and Practice*, 8(1), 106–121.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/17535069.2015.1011430>

Scanlon, K., Hudson, J., Fernández Arrigoitia, M., Ferreri, M., West, K., & Udagawa, C. (2021). Community-led housing and loneliness: Research into the impact of community-led housing and co-housing solutions.

- Scheller, D., & Larsen, H. G. (2019). Urban activism and co-housing. In *Contemporary Co-housing in Europe: Towards Sustainable Cities?* (pp. 120–139). Taylor and Francis Inc.
<https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429450174-7>
- Scheller, D., & Thörn, H. (2018). Governing ‘Sustainable Urban Development’ Through Self-Build Groups and Co-Housing: The Cases of Hamburg and Gothenburg. *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research*, 42(5), 914–933. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2427.12652>
- Schmid, S. (2019). *A History of Collective Living Forms of Shared Housing*. Birkhäuser.
- Sen, A. (1999). *Development as Freedom*. Oxford University Press.
- Star, S. L. (1999). The Ethnography of Infrastructure. *American Behavioral Scientist*, 43(3), 377–391.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/00027649921955326>
- Tavory, I., & Timmermans, S. (2014). *Abductive Analysis: Theorizing Qualitative Research*. University of Chicago Press.
- Thörn, H., Larsen, H. G., Hagbert, P., & Wasshede, C. (2020). Co-housing, sustainable urban development and governance: An introduction. In *Contemporary Co-housing in Europe: Towards Sustainable Cities?* (pp. 1–20). Routledge.
- Tummers, L. (2016). The re-emergence of self-managed co-housing in Europe: A critical review of co-housing research. *Urban Studies*, 53(10), 2023–2040. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0042098015586696>
- Tummers, L. C. (2017). Learning from co-housing initiatives — Between Passivhaus engineers and active inhabitants. *A+BE | Architecture and the Built Environment*, 7(14), 1–282.
<https://doi.org/10.7480/abe.2017.14.1858>
- Turner, J. F. C. (1972). Housing as a Verb. In *Freedom to Build, dweller control of the housing process* (pp. 148–175).
- Tzika, Z., Sentieri-Omarrementeria, C., & Martínez-Duran, A. (2023). Towards collective forms of dwelling: the grant-of-use housing cooperatives in Catalonia. *Revista de Arquitectura*, 28(45), 54–75.
<https://doi.org/10.5354/0719-5427.2023.70003>
- Vestbro, D. U. (2010, May). Living together-cohousing ideas and realities around the world. *Proceedings from the International Collaborative Housing Conference in Stockholm*.
- Vidal, L. (2018). The politics of creditor–debtor relations and mortgage payment strikes: The case of the Uruguayan Federation of Mutual-Aid Housing Cooperatives. *Environment and Planning A: Economy and Space*, 50(6), 1189–1208. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0308518X18775107>
- Viskovic Rojs, D., Hawlina, M., Gračner, B., & Ramšak, R. (2020). Review of the Participatory and Community-Based Approach in the Housing Cooperative Sector. In J. Nared & D. Bole (Eds.), *Participatory Research and Planning in Practice*. The Urban Book Series. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-28014-7_6
- Weeks, L. E., Bigonnesse, C., McInnis-Perry, G., & Dupuis-Blanchard, S. (2020). Barriers Faced in the Establishment of Cohousing Communities for Older Adults in Eastern Canada. *Journal of Aging and Environment*, 34(1), 70–85. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02763893.2019.1627267>
- Williams, J. (2005). Designing neighbourhoods for social interaction: The case of cohousing. *Journal of Urban Design*, 10(2), 195–227. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13574800500086998>
- Yin, R. K. (2018). *Case Study Research and Applications*. Design and methods (6th edition). SAGE.
- Zimmerman, M. A. (2000). Empowerment Theory Psychological, Organizational and Community Levels of Analysis. In *Handbook of community psychology* (pp. 43–63). Springer.

Keywords: Grant-of-Use, Co-Housing, Affordable Housing, Sustainable Housing, Collaborative Housing, Care, Participation

Tzika, Z., & Sentieri, C. (2023). *Towards collective forms of dwelling: Analysis of the characteristics of the emerging grant-of-use housing cooperatives in Catalonia*. In 2nd Participatory Design Conference. Transforming the City: Public Space & Environment, Inequalities & Democracy. Athens, Greece.

Abstract: The cooperative housing model that has emerged in Catalonia since 2015, has received interest as an alternative form of housing, originating from grassroots initiatives and placing the emphasis on community. Cooperative housing appears during periods when prevailing housing markets fail to provide adequate solutions. Groups are engaging in self-organisation, and collective decision-making, to assess their needs, negotiate resources, and co-create alternative housing options. While affordable housing access remains a core objective, cooperative housing goes beyond that, challenging individualistic living norms and emphasizing community relationships. Based on the analysis, it is observed that Catalonia’s cooperative housing model has been evolving towards greater diversity, offering new possibilities for dwelling and fostering community-oriented housing. This evolution is evident in both the spatial characteristics of the houses and their social organisation. However, despite efforts from the cooperative housing groups and non-profit organisations in the sector to address challenges related to inclusion, long consolidation processes and financial barriers, there is still room for improvement.

References:

Buil, D. M. (2018). The reterritorialization of the housing and habitat sector in Barcelona and Madrid towards a new urban governance of housing? *Sud-Ouest Europeen*, 2018-January(46), 23–38.

<https://doi.org/10.4000/SOE.4612>

Ehlenz, M. M. (2018). Making Home More Affordable: Community Land Trusts Adopting Cooperative Ownership Models to Expand Affordable Housing. *Journal of Community Practice*, 26(3), 283–307.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/10705422.2018.1477082>

Etxezarreta, A., Cano, G., & Merino, S. (2018). Housing cooperatives on “assignment of use”: Emerging experiences in Spain. *CIRIEC-Espana Revista de Economia Publica, Social y Cooperativa*, 92, 61–86.

<https://doi.org/10.7203/CIRIEC-E.92.9266>

Ferreri, M., & Vidal, L. (2021). Public-cooperative policy mechanisms for housing commons. *International Journal of Housing Policy*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19491247.2021.1877888>

García-Lamarca, M. (2017). From Occupying Plazas to Recuperating Housing: Insurgent Practices in Spain. *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research*, 41(1), 37–53. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2427.12386>

Hoekstra, J., Saizarbitoria, I. H., & Etxarri, A. E. (2010). Recent changes in Spanish housing policies: Subsidized owner-occupancy dwellings as a new tenure sector? *Journal of Housing and the Built Environment*, 25(1), 125–138. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10901-009-9169-6>

Jarvis, H. (2015). Towards a deeper understanding of the social architecture of co-housing: Evidence from the UK, USA and Australia. *Urban Research and Practice*, 8(1), 93–105.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/17535069.2015.1011429>

Jupp, E., Bowlby, S., Franklin, J., & Hall, S. M. (2019). *The new politics of home: Housing, Gender and Care in Times of Crisis* (1st ed.). Bristol University Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctvjghvp4>

Mendoza Ayala, H. (2019). Exclusion of the housing market in Barcelona: effects on the vital trajectories of middle-class people. **Perifèria. Revista d'investigació i Formació En Antropologia**, 24(2), 36. <https://doi.org/10.5565/rev/periferia.697>

Power, E. R., & Mee, K. J. (2019). Housing: an infrastructure of care. *Housing Studies*, 35(3), 484–505. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02673037.2019.1612038>

Keywords: Collective Housing, Affordable Housing, Community, Participation, Communal Living